

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH "DEMOKRITOS"

 ESReDA | European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

65th ESReDA Seminar

on

From risk imagination to safety intervention - Managing risks with knowledge

November 14th – 15th, 2024

NCSR Demokritos, Athens, Greece

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Abstract

These proceedings are the outcome of the 65th ESReDA Seminar “From risk imagination to safety intervention - Managing risks with knowledge” that took place at the National Center for Scientific Research ‘DEMOKRITOS’ in Athens, Greece, on 13 – 14 November 2024.

The main objective of this seminar was to identify the enablers and barriers to the production of knowledge concerning safety risks and resilience and its effectiveness in decision-making and other management and operational activities. A broad spectrum was covered, with sessions addressing different industrial and infrastructural sectors: energy and process industry, transport sector, natural disasters, materials, critical infrastructures and cyber systems. The key problematic question that the seminar tried to answer was: *‘What does a management team, a regulator or a front-line operator need to know and can use to manage risks effectively?’*

This seminar brought together researchers, practitioners and decision-makers from academia, operators, industry and governing bodies to discuss theories, concepts, and experiences of knowledge management and risk. The proceedings include 4 plenary speeches, 1 industry talk, 16 full papers or extended abstracts and the results of the interactive section that was performed during the first day of the seminar.

The editorial work for this volume was supported by the Institute for Nuclear and Radiological Sciences and Technology, Energy and Safety (INRASTES) in the frame of NCSR Demokritos support to ESReDA activities.

Acknowledgements

The authors of this report are particularly thankful for the support of the Institute for Nuclear and Radiological Sciences, Energy, Technology and Safety (INRASTES) and of NCSR Demokritos Innovation Office. The authors are very thankful for the time and attention from ESReDA Board of Directors and in particular ESReDA President Dr. Mohamed Eid and General Secretary Prof. Antonio Guillen.

This seminar would not be possible without the sponsorship of Helleniq Energy and the support of the European Safety and Reliability Association (ESRA).

We would like to thank every participant for attending and contributing to the 65th ESReDA Seminar. We hope that the seminar gave participants a forum for thought-provoking, productive conversation and that they were able to use the opportunity to build new, cooperative relationships and to exchange information and applications between scientists and industrial engineers.

We would like also to acknowledge the continuous effort of the members of the PG “Risk, Knowledge and Management” for the successful organization of the seminar and for conducting the interactive session.

Special thanks go to Klio Makrigiannaki, Institute Executive Secretary and Eleni Bairachtari, Institute Accounting Manager, for their unwavering commitment, tremendous work, and inventiveness in resolving multiple issues.

The last, but not least ‘thank you’ goes to the Technical Programme Committee for their efforts during the review process of the seminar contributions.

Myrto Konstantinidou, Chair of the 65th ESReDA Seminar

For the Risk, Knowledge, Management project group

About ESReDA

European Safety, Reliability & Data Association (ESReDA) is a European Association established in 1992 to promote research, application and training in Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS). The Association provides a forum for the exchange of information, data and current research in Safety and Reliability. The contents of ESReDA seminar proceedings do not necessarily reflect the position of ESReDA. They are the sole responsibility of the authors concerned. ESReDA seminar's proceedings are designed for free public distribution. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

ESReDA membership is open to organisations, privates or governmental institutes, industry researchers and consultants, who are active in the field of Safety and Reliability. Membership fees are currently 1000 EURO for organisations and 500 EURO for universities and individual members. Special sponsoring or associate membership is also available.

For more information and available ESReDA proceedings please consult <http://www.esreda.org/>

About ESReDA Project Group on Risks, Knowledge and Management

In 2020, ESReDA launched a project group to address the relationships between risks, knowledge and management. The scope defined is of interest to system designers, operators, managers, maintenance, lawyers, insurers, regulators, and many others working on safety and security including natural hazard management. The scope covers the safety, reliability and security related to multiple hazards and threats (natural, high-risk industry, critical infrastructure, communication and transport systems over different territories etc.) involving all stakeholders (public, operators, regulators and government). Risk management integrates all activities and disciplines related to assessment, identification of early warning signs and emerging risks, foresight, investigation of events and lessons to be learned, management of barriers and lines of defense, reliability, and change of policies and culture. In this context, the keyword knowledge defines the main topic of the project: the endeavour to use knowledge to improve the management and governance of risks (from design to operation and dismantling/decommissioning).

About NCSR “Demokritos”

Founded in July 1961 as a Research Centre for Nuclear Research, “**Demokritos**” is today the largest multidisciplinary Research Centre of Greece. It has approximately 180 Researchers in tenured and tenure-track positions, and over 500 Research Personnel working in projects funded mainly by grants from State Funds, the European Union and Private Industries. The Centre consists of five independent Institutes focusing on different scientific fields. The **Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences and Technology, Energy & Safety (INRASTES)** is an interdisciplinary R&D establishment pursuing basic, translational and applied research to address challenges of great scientific and socioeconomic impact in a broad spectrum of scientific and technological fields.

The **System Reliability and Industrial Safety Laboratory (SRISL)** is part of the **Institute of Nuclear & Radiological Sciences & Technology, Energy & Safety Radiation Protection** of NCSR “Demokritos”. The laboratory has been conducting top research on the safety and reliability of industrial systems for almost **35 years** providing industry with relevant tools for the analysis of occupational and industrial accidents, the identification of hazards in industrial installations and the quantitative assessment of risks. SRISL, in collaboration with other European research organisations, focuses its research efforts on problems addressing the support of decisions concerning the management of risk, the land use planning around dangerous sites, the evaluation of the role of the organisational and management systems of a company on the safety of the installations, the assessment and management of emerging risks, and the collection, and analysis of accident data towards increased prediction and prevention of future accidents.

Introduction

These proceedings are the outcome of the 65th ESReDa Seminar hosted by NCSR Demokritos, in its premises in Athens on the 14th and 15th November 2024. The purpose of the seminar was to reflect upon the following topics:

- Organisational characteristics that promote the ability to invest in identifying new threats, in imagining risks in a context of uncertainty.
- Tools and frameworks that facilitate evidence-based decision-making and effective safety interventions.
- Individual and collective capabilities and non-technical skills relevant to the sharing of information (including inconvenient truths) between the sharp-end of operations and the blunt-end where systems are designed; plans, schedules and standards are established; tradeoffs are made, and resources are allocated.
- Anticipate and manage the information and knowledge that will be needed at different stages of the system life-cycle; evidence the added value of building synergy between safety and knowledge management;
- Recognise and reward the diverse types of expertise needed to identify early warning signs, interpret observations, analyse data, communicate information, and preserve knowledge.
- Specific challenges to ensure that valid information, relevant knowledge, ‘proofs’ but also ‘doubts’ are available to regulators, the justice control, the media, and the public.
- Technological innovation for risk knowledge management to improve safety and resilience analysis.
- Democratisation of knowledge through participatory approaches and accessibility of information to non-specialists
- Combination and usage of distributed knowledge in complex risk scenarios for crisis management.
- The importance and the role of technology to analyse and to manage adequately risk knowledge as well as to communicate it effectively.
- The role of culture in risk management and the importance of risk communication.

The 65th ESReDA seminar was a forum for exploring the above mentioned and other related questions.

The seminar shared 21 contributions in oral sessions, 4 of which were Key Notes:

- Professor John Stoop, Kindunos Safety Consultancy Ltd
- Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz, University of Western Australia
- Bill Hewlett, MA CEng FICE FIET
- Professor Maria Chiara Leva, Technical University of Dublin

and one Industry Talk by:

- Asterios Lialios, HSE Director Elefsina Industrial Complex, Hellenic Petroleum RSSOPP S.A., Hellenic Energy S.A

These proceedings contain 16 full papers and extended abstracts, with authors representing several domains. The seminar attracted a good mix of academic and industrial participants from many European and overseas countries. There were authors coming from universities, research institutes and industrial companies in Australia, Belgium, Denmark, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Malaysia, Netherlands, Romania, Spain, United Kingdom and the United States of America.

An interactive session has been held during the first day and its results have been presented during the closing session of the seminar. The summary of the results is also included in these proceedings.

We wish to thank the Technical Programme Committee for their efforts during the review process of the contributions, and all the authors during the presentations and the final stages of paper preparation. We look forward to future opportunities for collaboration and hope to see you at future events.

The editorial work for this report was supported by the Institute of Nuclear and Radiological Sciences & Technology, Energy and Safety (INRASTES) in the frame of NCSR Demokritos support to ESReDA activities.

Dr. Myrto Konstantinidou

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Keynote Presentations

Keynote 1. Professor John Stoop

Kindunos Safety Consultancy Ltd

It is the assumption that kills you

John Stoop graduated as an aerospace engineer at Delft University of Technology. He is one of the founding fathers of the Safety Science Group at this university and did his PhD on the role of safety in the design process. He has been involved in establishing an independent safety investigation board in the Netherlands. In 2007 he became a professor in forensic engineering and safety investigation at Lund University in Lund, Sweden. His main interest lies in the methodology of safety investigations and the relation with the engineering design community in transport, infrastructure and logistics. To validate the theoretical notions and concepts, he was involved in a series of safety assessment surveys of major transport and infrastructure projects. To this purpose he also is a member of several international safety expert networks such as ESReDA. In this community, he contributed to the development of the notion of Foresight, a proactive and prospective assessment of safety and risks. He is an accredited air safety investigator and member of the International Society of Air Safety Investigators. Together with his PhD's he is finalizing two books; one on safety investigations and one on generative design methodologies. After his retirement, he got involved in the integral safety aspects and inherent risks of major wind turbine developments and their contribution to national policy making options on energy transition.

It is the assumption that kills you

John Stoop, Kindunos Safety Consultancy Ltd, Stoop@Kindunos.nl
and affiliated PhD graduate references

Abstract

This contribution reflects on the development of safety science in transport, infrastructure and logistics over a period of 40 years at Dutch universities, professional safety institutes and international networks. The contribution heavily relies on the work of the successive ESReDA Working Groups on safety investigation, the transport safety domain as deployed at Lund University in Sweden, the Delft University of Technology and the University of Applied Sciences in Amsterdam. Resulting in a series of graduate student projects, PhD studies and the author's participation in the international aviation investigation community. This contribution identifies the cornerstones for a generative design perspective, challenging a paradigm shift in safety thinking. Four new tools are introduced, materializing this challenge. Based on initial developments in aviation, maritime and agriculture, these notions are extrapolated to wind farming applications in particular in view of the EU Directive (EU) 2022/2557 on the resilience of critical entities (EU 2024).

1. Introduction

Safety and risk management heavily rely on past performance. The experience, tacit knowledge, expertise and best practices gained in the past, invite to extrapolate existing risk and safety notions and strategies to cope with future challenges. In a stable and constant technological and operating environment, such extrapolation is served by the concept of derivative design and best practices. However, in case of innovation, additional functionalities and (legal) changes in the operational environment, such a concept is questionable with respect to its validity boundaries. Theories and models may be confronted with their limitations by hidden assumptions, simplifications and extrapolations beyond their original specifications and contexts. In such cases of a disruptive approach, also the knowledge bases and repositories are to be scrutinized. Unfortunately, such scrutiny is fueled by hindsight from findings from safety investigations, forensic engineering analysis and risk acceptance considerations. As stated by a senior aviation safety investigator: it is the assumption that kills you (or users, your crews and passengers).

Based on a series of investigations, deficiencies in safety critical knowledge and safety knowledge management were identified in several major events in transport, logistics and infrastructure. This contribution elaborates not only on contributing factors and conditions during safety events. It primarily explores systemic aspects and levels that are beyond the visible scope of regular accident investigation practices. Change drivers, market developments, legal frameworks, governmental arrangements, policy demands on green sustainability and circular economy represent hidden complexities and couplings behind the horizon in life cycle, short and long term systems developments. Such dynamics require Foresight, Precaution and Prospective systems design and development, integrating content and process simultaneously in the architecture of systems from a multi-actor and stakeholders perspective. Such dynamics require teaching young safety and risk professionals new (designing) tricks of the trade in both theoretical and practical professional performances in order not to forget the lessons already learned by previous generations of safety and risk engineering professionals from tragic outcomes in the past. This contribution extrapolates several 'lessons learned' by asking provocative questions about energy transition developments on land, at sea and in the air, in particular with respect to nowadays wind turbine upscaling and deployment. In order to secure the planet for future generations, a systemic Generative Design Perspective is proposed, rather than restoring -if possible at all- the damage done by Regeneration, Resilience Engineering and Recovery in its existing operating envelope.

2. Retrospections

A retrospection on the notions of safety and risk demonstrate a gradual paradigm shift from accident investigation and event analysis to safety management strategies and organizational change at the corporate level. Inherently, a shift occurred from an engineering dominance to managerial and organizational perspectives, supported by the introduction of a series of new notions and schools of thinking. Several 'belief' systems were introduced to support such a transition into 'socio-technical' system thinking. Simultaneously, social scientists raised doubts about a scientific validity of safety as a science, questioning notions of 'cause' and 'prevention', in favor of an operational risk management paradigm (Safety Science 2017). New sets of tools, techniques and theories were developed, such as Key Performance Indicators, data analysis models such as FRAM and STAMP, system models such as Cynefin, Resilience Engineering theory and democratic participation of operators by Work as Done versus Work as Imagined contradictions, weak signal detection and organizational learning. Such theories were favored by a diversion from cause towards consequences, depriving control over occurrences. An undefined and compiled notion of 'complexity' generated a disguise to understand 'emergent properties' -as defined by Rasmussen-, and dynamics of 'complex systems with tight couplings' as defined by Perrow-, which might -according to Turner-, create a 'drift into failure' due to 'human error' as defined by Reason, causing Perrows' 'normal accidents'. An exclusive control over organizational safety performance by corporate management replaced comprehension and oversight, sharing an undefined responsibility to evade liability and accountability. According to Farrier, introducing such new concepts such as Safety Management Systems, Safety Cases and State Safety Programs puts the two principles of safety management and safety investigations in opposition instead of leveraging their respective advantages. By discarding safety investigations from the analytical toolkit, such safety investigations are expelled from foresight and forced into a role of adversary whistle blowers. This discarding has three serious consequences. First, a consensus based interpretation of findings based on investigative reconstruction of events is no longer connected with managerial responsibilities and intervention strategies. Second, investigative recommendations based on these findings are no longer incorporated in their specific corporate, stakeholder and governmental context. As stated by Hollnagel, 'in the learning process, one should learn from what went right, not from what went wrong'. In losing oversight over the context specific setting, design trade-offs and operational feedback on a triggering event, remedial control options are lost as well, both for the event as well as the system itself. Third, if no lessons learned are drawn from previous life cycle phases or are expelled from the knowledge repository, undesirable events will manifest themselves as 'emergent properties' rather than system inherent properties, designed into the system. Such events stem from previous design requirements, optimization considerations and trade-offs. Clarifying such decisions and subsequent properties should be part of the investigative process and system diagnosis. Otherwise only rescue, recovery and resilience approaches are available in the aftermath of events to remedy system deficiencies in a strict retrospective manner. Since an equivalent of Environmental Impact Assessment legislation does not exist for assessing integral safety in transport, logistic and infrastructure project decision making, the only option is to develop an engineering design methodology, incorporating the safety dimension (TCI 2004).

A first conclusion is that a dialectic stall in scientific notions and knowledge occurred during this transition. Derivative approaches from socio-psychological and organizational disciplines provided an anti-these for the technological engineering design theses, but were not able to deliver a synthesis in a scientific paradigm shift for safety thinking in (design) context and operational environment

3. An ESReDA remedial response

An ESReDA remedy response to this stall preferred a disruptive approach which, according to Vincenti (1990), might perform better than derivative adaptations and linear extrapolations, given the changes in the operating environment. Socio-economic and technological environments change according to market development, governmental (legal) arrangements and public-policy demands. Such changes are triggered by societal demands

on circular economy, climate responsive changes, proactive adaptation and regenerative design options to accommodate 'foresight and providence' in a neo-liberal economy (ESReDA 2020).

A second conclusion is the necessity to develop a new systems methodology: incorporating safety investigations, user knowledge based and value chain based system design and operations.

To facilitate foresight, a stepwise approach should be favored: first understand, then comprehend, explore beyond the event and add system architecture, complexity and dynamics to the analysis, provide a timely transparency in the factual functioning of the (sub)systems, and diagnose system problems to identify solution spaces beyond the event level during operations.

To enable such a disruptive system approach, two primary conditions have to be fulfilled:

- explore the basics of a safety investigation methodology
- Identify the assumptions, (design) knowledge deficiencies and correlations in the subsystems.

During the journey of several ESReDA working groups, the safety investigative methodology and processes have been unraveled and structured to fulfil the first condition.

The *investigation processes* contains 3 phases:

1. The investigative reconstruction of the event in its environment

This phase contains a factual description of the system components, aspects and dimensions to facilitate the step from description to explanation of the event in its context, given the available data and operational conditions

2. The analytic interpretation of facts and findings

This phase is mobilizing knowledge and expertise about states, deficiencies, design and operational assumptions, models, simplifications, interactions to facilitate the step from understanding to sustainable change and performance enhancement: foresight by hindsight and insight.

3. The adaptive intervention by learning, recommending and change

This phase is categorizing change options in the event and the system as derivative, disruptive or prospective adaptations, applying system engineering design and change management principles to facilitate the step from recommending to implementing knowledge and value based solution spaces and operational envelopes.

The adaptive intervention copes with the *system architecture, -complexity and -dynamics*. To address these characteristics, during the system analysis, efforts should be dedicated to clarify the system-constraints itself:

- Change the focus to conceptual change rather than form and function variation
- Identify assumptions, simplifications and extrapolations
- Identify knowledge deficiencies in design expertise and operational experiences
- identify and validate system boundaries: technological, social, institutional, ecosystem
- Identify the operating envelope, also on the long term
- Apply the full information paradigm: combine feedforward and feedback
- Lessons learned or lessons forgotten, denied or dismissed
- Identify political-societal change agents, change drivers and bifurcation, subsystem points.

Putting events in their systemic context and operating envelope facilitates an assessment of the event as a 'normal' accident within or outside the intended design and operating envelope. Recommendations on remedies for such events may reflect a necessity to make derivative or disruptive adaptations during subsequent system revisions.

A third conclusion is to develop a Prospective, Future Proof approach, by Foresight and by a Generative Design Methodology, on land, at sea and in the air. Does this approach foresee future safety performance without abundant feedback from safety occurrences?

4. The windturbine energy case study

In this contribution, wind turbine energy transition practices during the 2030 – 2050 period in the Netherlands are applied to demonstrate the distinction between event safety investigations and system safety investigations. Since hardly any safety related events have occurred during the introduction of wind turbine generated energy transition process, safety has been absent in the public debate and governmental and policy making processes. Rather than based on factual information and system based analysis, safety assumptions have been made, based on ‘belief’ systems and minor collateral damage assumptions, such as collisions with bats and birds, noise abatement and flickering shadow nuisance. Wind turbine inherent technical safety aspects are considered proprietary expertise and are left out of the equation in the public debate. Safety is reduced to ‘external safety’ as an environmental component and assessed as a public perception issue (Weteringe 2023, Elze van Hamelen 2024). Basic scientific domains such as aerodynamics, meteorology, geophysics and acoustics are not admitted to the public debates and considered proprietary expertise of turbine manufacturers, while democratic participation, sustainability, operating envelopes and operating conditions are not taken into account. Publicly accessible data registration systems are fully absent. Instead, linear extrapolations of turbine dimensions, power generation, spatial planning and land use issues are preferred by the turbine industry: ‘bigger is always better’. This assumption however, proves to be questionable (GCube 2023). Performance standards on noise and nuisance and environmental impacts in the public domain are submitted to legal, ad-hoc procedures and judicial verdicts as the basis for a public debate in a massive deployment of this high energy density industry.

Pilot holes

Wind turbine farm anomaly

According to insurance market experts, there has been a rapid commercialization of ‘prototypical technologies’, by an accelerated leap in turbine dimensions and performance from a 3-8 MW to a 8-18 MW category of turbines. This leap creates financial pressure on manufacturers, supply chain and insurance markets. The industry is reaching a vertical limit, where the ‘bigger is better’ assumption is to the detriment of safety, quality, reliability and sustainability (GCube 2023). Could this have been foreseen by mobilizing knowledge from scientific domains and research institutes that were not involved in the public debate? Was the knowledge already ‘in the market’, similar to experiences in high tech industries such as aviation and maritime or were new entrants in the industry dominant in a ‘hard’ insurance market with increasing risks and losses?

Finally, what are the consequences of extracting huge amounts of energy from the lower levels of the atmosphere? The impact of such a large scale extraction of energy on weather and climate conditions has hardly been explored. New phenomena are emerging, such as pilot holes and wind turbine farm anomalies in various layers of the atmosphere. Are such anomalies accidental emergent phenomena, only observable in practice, to be labelled as ‘serendipities’, such as the Horns windfarm case in Denmark? Do they represent new unforeseen inherent properties, challenging the assumptions on the adiabatic nature of atmospheric processes?

Figure 1. The Horns Rev Photo Case of 2008

A Quick Scan on scientific literature on satellite observations, aerial photography and climate modelling reveals a wealth of experience and expertise, directly accessible in geosciences, meteorology, climate change and energy transition literature (Klotzbach et.al. 2009, Miller et.al. 2011, Hasager et.al. 2013). Such scientific knowledge indicate the limits of growth of energy transition challenges, uncertainties and deficiencies in large scale wind farming developments. Such knowledge was foreseeable at the practical introduction of major windfarm initiatives since the 2010's, but not explored, leaving windfarming a 'perpetuum mobile' (Kleidon 2021). It assumed windfarming an unlimited source of energy, ignoring thermodynamics, geosciences, meteorology and aerodynamics knowledge domains. In particular the role of turbulence and dynamic interactions between the inner and outer layer of the atmospheric boundary layer is to be scrutinized in order to understand the recovery of the energy content of the boundary layer after the 'harvesting' of kinetic energy by wind turbines. Such harvesting impacts the humidity, precipitation, temperature, velocity and pressure, which requires downstream airflow recovery distances of hundreds of kilometers. Mutual windfarm interactions by wake propagation is significant and influences energy production efficiency over long distances (Baas 2024).

A fourth conclusion is that a systemic analysis reveals that each of these performance aspects contain knowledge deficiencies, unvalidated assumptions and undisclosed subsystem correlations. Primary system safety characteristics however, are hardly addressed.

A system analysis reveals deficiencies and serve as a foresight enabler before the turbine industry has reached maturity. Such a disruptive introduction of systems approach in the analytic diagnosis of events however, is not enough to accommodate foresight in technological innovation and system transition challenges. To achieve a prospective approach in complex and dynamic socio-technical systems, principles of First Time Right and Zero Defect should be applied. However, such an approach does not yet exist in transportation systems design (TCI 2004). Transportation systems are characterized as High Energy Density Systems and are 'never dying systems' due to their 24/7 operational availability in open access, global networks. In addition they are characterized by a constant change in technology, organization, control and legislative arrangements and hybrid nature during transition periods. Designing such transportation, infrastructure and logistic systems in a sustainable, future and climate robust manner, requires the development of foresight enablers, developed as specific notions, tools and proactive assessment techniques, in a context of institutional arrangements, supranational oversight and governmental control mechanisms. The wind turbine industry should also adhere to such a systemic approach, belonging to the High Energy Density system category.

This contribution indicates several perspectives and conditions under which such a toolkit can be used to design the future. These perspectives are derived from engineering design methodologies and safety science as developed in aviation, the maritime and agricultural domains.

5. Towards a generative design perspective

5.1 Foresight enablers

In this contribution two enablers of foresight are elaborated:

- Forensic engineering and safety investigations
- Socio-technical system engineering design methodologies.

These enablers are materialized by the introduction of a new system design perspectives, four new tools and identification of key success factors. Such enablers facilitate the expansion of the design envelope in both a horizontal and vertical direction. The horizontal expansion of the design envelope copes with an integral approach of all relevant design aspects, matching 'hard' and 'soft' design requirements alike. The vertical expansion copes with higher order system requirements, such as dynamic-adaptive anticipation of future priorities and robust, future proof frameworks. For each of these expansions and adaptations of the design methodology, specific tools are developed. Additional disciplines and actors are introduced, each with their preferred values, goals and disciplinary knowledge and expertise. Such an approach requires the (re-) introduction of a systems architect in the role of a system integrator being an initiator of cooperation and communication (TCI 2004).

First, forensic engineering and safety investigations as foresight enablers require a stepwise upgrade of the factfinding phase of the investigation process from the single event to the level of system design and operations. Such a factfinding mission starts with identification of single issue safety aspects and is data driven. Such a mission focuses on derivative form variations, deviant or normal, related to the intended design parameters and assumptions. During the analysis and interpretation of the findings of this mission, multiple issues can be explored, driven by business model considerations, balancing various aspects of a People, Profit and Planet based nature. This investigation phase considers the impact of disruptive functionalities on the subsystem level and their appearance during intended operations.

Second, based on socio-technical systems engineering design methodologies in various transportation and infrastructure domains, Knowledge Based and Value Based driven considerations are to be identified. They serve as triggers for change and adaptation to redesign the system as compatible to modifications in goal based concepts, future proof and climate change. Analyzing the potential of a prospective 'foresight' approach, the expansion of the analysis to higher system levels and objectives creates a reference framework for the analysis of the event. In this framework, the assumptions, limitations, interactions and correlations across the system as a whole can be identified. The analytic focus expands from an operational event reconstruction towards a life cycle based system approach, covering design, development and operations. A transfer occurs from a static-reactive focus towards a dynamic-adaptive focus, anticipating future priorities and transition robust frame works (Safety Science 2017).

5.2 New tools

To facilitate such a transition in upgrading diagnostic potential to the system level, four new tools were developed to provide structure and control mechanisms to guide the design process:

1. The Design – Control – Practice diagram. This diagram puts the design, control and practice interrelations in a systemic context. The system life cycle provides relations between design, development, construct and operation to adaptation and decommissioning. The systems level of control relates operator compliance with management control and governmental oversight at the micro, meso and macro level. The engineering design cycle deals with successive design phases of goal, function and form. The diagram allocates positions of methods, tools and techniques, enabling a navigation through the safety landscape and their solution domains.

Figure 2. The DCP diagram

- the CEDI sustainability matrix (Veenstra 2024) identifies the primary design dimensions and their hard as well as soft performance parameters which are to be incorporated in the Program of Requirements and are to be specified and allocated to modular design subsystems.

Figure 3. The CEDI matrix

CEDI variation selection matrix -1 decarbonisation

CEDI ranking	1	2	3	4	5
Part I					
MDV-1 re-design concepts	Twin-rig beamer (OD 6)	Twin-rig sterntrawler (MDV-1 to 5)	Twin-rig sterntrawler (MDV-5 - 10)	Twin-rig stern trawler (MDV-10-20)	Twin-rig stern trawler (MDV- Circular)
Level of marine fuel decarbonisation	benchmark Diesel-direct +gearbox	Diesel-electric / AC/DC motor, thrust bearings	Single/dual fuel LNG/BIO gas engines-hybrid electric. LNG-BIO-E	Liquefied hydrogen-fuel cell-electric	Battery electrification + renewablejettyrecharging AE
Power	DD Dieselengine	DE E-motor	Gasengine	Fuel cell	Batteries
Fuel tanks	50 m ³	25 m ³	60 m ³	80 m ³	-
Layout/length	30-40 m	30-32 m	32-35 m	35 m	35 m
Fuel/100 hrs.	18.000 ltr.	6500 - 7000 ltr	6000 - 6500 ltr	10.000 ltr.	-
ton CO ₂ per yr	2880	1040	825	-	-
CO ₂ reduction	-	63 %	70 %	100 %	100 %
Additional CE-Investments:					
-equipment			400.000	700.000	1.000.000
-storage, safety			500.000	600.000	700.000
-layout adapt.			200.000	300.000	400.000
Percentage		parent vessel	+23 %	+36 %	+47 %
Estimated new	6 - 8 Meuro	4.5 Meuro	5.6 Meuro	6.1 Meuro	6.6 Meuro

This CEDI approach is a system-design methodology taking into account business and climate responsive design choices in the early design phase, like here for an engine room subsystem. The CEDI index explores which sustainable solutions are becoming available in the chosen timeframe 2030-2050. By ranking (semi)proven, rapidly emerging green technologies, the linear MDV-1 design process is evolving into a more flexible modular and circular MDV-1 design process with, for short and long term change potentials the estimated subsystem refitting costs.

- The ESReDA cube aims at bridging the gap between interpretation and intervention by application of design principles, control strategies and over various aspects of evidence and information on knowledge based solutions concerning the structure, context and content of design and control over operational processes.

Figure 4. The ESReDA Cube

4. The MCIM model serves as a technical-social-customized model, identifying the necessary cooperation between scientific, technical, product and market dimensions in order to achieve a successful introduction of cyclic innovative processes and products.

Figure 5. The MCIM model

Throughout several PhD projects in transportation and major infrastructure initiatives in the Netherlands, a series of critical key success factors were identified:

- Apply a safety and sustainability problem orientation
- Share knowledge with participatory choices regarding modelling, functionality and goals
- Identify assumptions, limitations and simplifications
- Communicate and coordinate across users and multi-stakeholders
- Generate component innovations, subsystem optimization and overall system concept integration
- Acknowledge safety investigators as system architect counterparts.

6. Conclusions

A Fifth conclusion can be drawn from the experiences with successively applying knowledge and value based design in aviation, flexible modular and sustainable design in the maritime industry and regenerative design methodologies in agriculture sector. Foresight cannot be achieved with such methodologies in isolation. A future proof and change robust systems design requires a new, prospective design paradigm, combining elements of engineering design methodology, change, adaptation and foresight.

Rather than continuing a stalled debate across disciplines, stakeholders and perspectives, a synthesis of notions, theories and intellectual constructs is required. To foresee a future functioning of manmade artefacts, safe and sustainable. A main prerequisite is to provide transparency for each of the disciplines and perspectives.

This paper extrapolated the 'lessons learned' from transport, infrastructure and logistic system engineering designs to the energy transition and wind farming developments in the Netherlands. Taking into account the system architecture at all levels and aspects, four new tools could be applied. From a Generative Design Perspective the case study results in three provocative questions on developments on land, at sea and in the air:

- On land: questions are raised in the public debate about land use planning and environmental policy making with respect to location and configuration selection criteria regarding integral safety and risk perception of large turbines and their local *wind climate* impact in the lower atmospheric boundary regions
- At sea: questions are debated in aerodynamic research and engineering communities which are hardly communicated with public and governance entities, regarding wake and turbulence interferences within and across wind farm dimensions and locations, causing efficiency losses and their impact on *weather changes* in the downwind dispersion of their effects in the upper parts of the atmospheric boundary regions
- In the air: questions are debated in geophysical and meteorological communities regarding the total solar energy influx balance, its dissipation across atmospheric and maritime modes, their inherent physical limits for energy transition goals and the impact on *climate changes* in the long term at the global level.

Reducing these questions to a debate on benefits of wind farming in general according to a 'bigger is better' and a 'race to scale' level is applying a 'Procrustean Bed' solution: an arbitrary standard forcing anybody to an exact conformity.

Finally, the future begins at investigating current deficiencies in system design methodologies in order to eliminate their inherent assumptions, limitations and simplifications and to achieve foresight over future developments. The new EU Directive on Resilience of Critical Entities, combined with the new school of safety thinking in Generative Design Perspectives may support such foresight, otherwise these deficiencies will kill you.

Acknowledgements

In addition to these key references, many papers and presentations are provided by the PhD graduates in the transportation and infrastructure safety domain. Without their contributions, this paper would not have been written. In alphabetic order; Wim Beukenkamp, Geert Boosten, Arthur Dijkstra, Erik van Kleef, Frederic Mohrmann and Frans Veenstra.

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It is the assumption that kills you

John Stoop et.al.
Kindunos Safety Consultancy Ltd

65th ESReDA Seminar
From risk imagination to safety intervention – Managing risks with knowledge

14 – 15 November 2024
Athens, Greece

A retrospection on safety and risk

A paradigm shift:

- From Accident Investigation towards Safety Management
- From deficiencies in design towards operational performance
- From technology towards organisation and governance
- From qualified and independent investigation to operational safety excellence
- From learning by failure towards success evaluation (Hollnagel, Dekker)

Consequences of this shift:

- Focus transfer from investigation feedback towards operational best practices (Farrier)
- Replacing notions of cause, prevention and precaution (Hollnagel)
- Introduction of 'belief' systems notions: system complexity, Cynefin model
- Work as Done/Work as Imagined (Reason)
- Creating a new set of tools and (re)design requirements:
 - ▀ Key Performance Indicators
 - ▀ Resilience engineering
 - ▀ system modelling: the CATS model
 - ▀ big data analysis
 - ▀ democratic participation

A shift in context and operational environment

- A new socio-economical environment: post-neoliberalism
- = see previous work of our ESReDA project groups on investigative methodology
- = new market relations: privatisation, delegation, the Boeing 737 case
- = decay in learning potential: suppressing 'weak' signals (Kletz)
- = reinstalling liability and accountability over learning and oversight

But most of all

- Legitimized by 'scientific' theories at the higher systems levels: Turner, Reason, Hollnagel, Rasmussen, et. al.
- 'New school' paradigms in socio-technical systems engineering and emerging policy analysis:
- = process overrules content
- = market overrules knowledge
- = participation overrules expertise
- and scientific hobby horses flourish in this battle for recognition of new scientific domains

Conclusion 1:

- A dialectic stall in scientific development occurs.
- Derivative approaches provide thesis and antithesis, but do not deliver a synthesis

An ESReDA remedial response

According to Vincenti:

given changes in the socio-economical and technological environment, disruptive adaptations might perform better than derivative extrapolations

What are these changes:

market developments, governmental arrangements, policy demands on sustainability, circular economy, climate responsive and resilience capacity

An ESReDA remedy in 3 steps?

- = understanding investigative notions and methodology: forensic sciences
- = future proof systems change and transition: foresight by hindsight and insight
- = applying a systems architecture: the ESReDA Cube and CIM model

This means:

- A disruptive approach in focus
- A stepwise approach: first understand, then comprehend
- Explore beyond the event: add the system to the scope
- Provide a timely transparency in the factual functioning of complex systems
- Diagnosing (sub)system problems to identify solution spaces

Conclusion 2:

Develop a new system methodologies: Safety Investigations, Knowledge Based and Value Based system design and operations

The ESReDA Safety Investigation Methodology

The investigation processes contain 3 phases

1. The investigative reconstruction of the event in its environment

factual description of the system components, aspects and dimensions to facilitate the step from description to explanation of the event in its context, given the available data and conditions

2. The analytic interpretation of facts and findings

Mobilizing knowledge and expertise about states, deficiencies, design and operational assumptions, models, simplifications, interactions to facilitate the step from understanding to sustainable change and performance enhancement

3. The adaptive intervention by learning, recommending and change

Categorizing change options in the event and the system as derivative, disruptive or prospective adaptations, applying system engineering design and change management principles to facilitate the step from recommending to implementing knowledge based solution spaces

What are the constraints?

Change the focus to conceptual change rather than form and function variation
Identify and validate system boundaries: technological, social, institutional, ecosystem
Identify knowledge deficiencies in expertise and experience
Apply the full information paradigm: combine feedforward and feedback
Identify the operating envelope, also on the long term
Identify assumptions, simplifications and extrapolations
Lessons learned or lessons forgotten, denied or dismissed
Identify change agents, change drivers and bifurcation points

Conclusion 3:

Develop a Prospective, Future Proof approach,
by Hindsight, Insight and Foresight
by a Generative Design Methodology

How does this apply in a case based practice?

The Wind turbine energy transition case

The Wind turbine energy transition Foresight enablers

Information provided: Newspapers articles, Scientific and professional papers, Participation sessions on Energy Transition
Lacking information from: turbine manufacturers, consultants, market share holders, project management teams
Assessing the nature of information: specific or generic, factual or 'belief' based

Raise questions on What About:

Existing knowledge and experience in the participation process
Operating environment, local and regional land use conditions
Preferred design options: big, bigger, biggest, maximizing performance by linear extrapolation
Balancing of primary design pillars: power generation, storage, transport, consumers
Primary Design Knowledge domains: materials, aerodynamics, geofysics, meteorology
Lessons learned: Foresight analogies with Tower of Bable, Titanic, Deep Water Horizon, B737 MAX
Risk and impact assessment: event data, population at risk, catastrophic failure rate, accident scenarios
Sustainability and life cycle demands: carbon footprint, upcycling waste, rescue and emergency
Operational excellence: occupational hazards, automated stability and control
Incident reporting, alerting and response, operating limits, corporate inspections and governance oversight
Business model: network configuration, return on investments, insurance, upgrades, decommission and disposal
Introducing atmospheric aberrations: pilot holes and windturbine park anomalies

Conclusion 4: Each of these aspects contain knowledge efficiencies, unvalidated assumptions and undisclosed correlations

Towards a Generative Design Perspective Forensic Engineering and Safety Investigation; enablers of Foresight

A stepwise upgrade of socio-technical systems design perspective:

1. Single issue safety: OSHE aspects, data driven and derivative form variation
2. Multiple issues: business driven Triple P by People, Planet, Profit and disruptive functional integration
3. Value chain driven: prospective foresight by Triple Zero. Zero accidents, Zero emission and Zero waste, goal based concepts, future proof and climate change compatible

Design focus:

1. Technical optimization, performance parameters, integrating safety performance indicators
1. Flexible modular design, primary design pillars and short term change potential
1. Transfer from static towards dynamic adaptation, anticipating future priorities, adaptive approaches

New tools and key success factors

New tools:

1. The Design – Control – Practice diagram
2. Performance indicators, both soft and hard. The CEDI matrix: Circular Economy Design Index
3. System architecture and dynamic interaction across level: the ESReDA Cube as a reference framework
4. Innovation and transition change triggers and drivers: the MCIM model, intervention potential

Key success factors:

1. A sustainability and safety problem oriented approach
2. Sharing knowledge with participatory choices regarding modeling, functionality and goals
3. Clarify assumptions, limitations and simplifications
4. Communication with users and multi-stakeholders
5. Generation of component innovation, subsystem optimization and overall system concept integration
6. Safety investigators as system architect counterparts

Conclusion 5: The future begins at investigating designing towards a Generative Design Perspective

Keynote 2.

Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz

*Faculty of Engineering and Mathematical
Sciences*

University of Western Australia

Technical Language Processing – unlocking information in safety data

Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz came to academic from industry having held roles in operations and maintenance. Her expertise is in maintenance, reliability and safety but over the years she has become increasingly interested in information extraction from unstructured texts to support analysis and predictive work in these domains. Her team's work in AI is supporting her to ask, and answer, questions with improved confidence in the result (reduce the human error element) and in a fraction of time over manual approaches. The UWA NLP-TLP team produces many open-source tools to assist industry in this area <https://nlp-tlp.org/>

Melinda's past roles have included the Australian National Offshore Petroleum Safety and Environmental Regulator (NOPSEMA) Advisory Board (2017-2022), a \$2M BHP Fellow for Engineering for Remote Operations (2016-2022), METS Ignited Advisory committee, Chair Standards Australia MB19 committee ISO 55000-2 Asset Management (2012-215), and visiting Fellow at the Alan Turing Institute in the UK. She is currently active representing Australia in ISO TC 184 SC4 Industrial Data committee and in the development and publication of the ISO CD 23726 Industrial Data Ontology. More about her background is <https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/persons/melinda-hodkiewicz>

Abstract

In the safety domain we look back to inform the way forward. Our approach to identifying and prioritising risks, the controls we select, and the measures we use to assess the effectiveness of these controls is informed by what has happened in the past. In practice this has meant a reliance on the memories of our people and their life experiences. Quantitative estimates have come from limited and out-of-date generic data sets.

This situation is changing rapidly. Industrial organisations (and regulators) can now data mine information from their own internal historical records. They can extract information from unstructured texts such as incident reports and root cause analyses. These developments will unlock a treasure trove of historical data for safety professionals to examine.

In this talk Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz will discuss this Technical Language Processing opportunity, current developments that enable it, and suggest areas where regulators and organisations would benefit from collaboration in this non-competitive area for the benefit of all.

Technical Language Processing – unlocking (machine-readable) information in safety data

Presenter: Professor Melinda Hodkiewicz CEng, FTSE

65th ESReDA Seminar: "From Risk Imagination to Safety Intervention - Managing Risks with Knowledge

Athens, 14-15 November 2024

1

Historical (and current) safety data challenges

- Most event identification, labelling and classification is **done by humans** - seldom reviewed and checked.
- The meaning of labels is often **ambiguous** - leading to differences in interpretation and laborious alignment.
- **Limited quality control** on classification tasks – resulting (often incorrect) codes are used in all sorts of downstream analysis.
- People **rely on their experience** rather than the data - as data is too difficult to find and interpret.
- For quantitative data we rely on **generic data sets** - often out-of-date and poorly maintained.
- Exchange/ sharing of risk data is **problematic** – especially between countries.

2

Unstructured text is generated when an event occurs, or analysis is performed

Technical, human-generated text is **everywhere** in industry. >70% of data in enterprise systems is unstructured text.¹

Example 1: Event description

The incident occurred during nonroutine operational activities that introduced heat to a type of heat exchanger which was offline, creating an overpressure event while the vessel was isolated from its pressure relief device. The reboiler shell catastrophically ruptured, causing a boiling liquid expanding vapor explosion (BLEVE) and fire.

Example 2: Risk assessment tables

No.	Hazard	Se	Fr	Pr	Av	Cl	SIL	Safety Measures	Safe
1	Robot arm lunges forward, impacting person	3	5	2	1		8 SIL 1	SFD1: Personnel in zone	
2	Robot arm swinging, impacting person	4	5	3	1		9 SIL 2	SFD1: Personnel in zone	
3									
4									

No.	Comments
1	Se = 3 - Lunging can hit lower body, cause fracture. Fr = 5 - given the context, Pr = 2 - possible to get hit when entering area (less likely than swing), Av = 1 - probable to run.
2	Se = 4 - Swing can cause concussion in head leading to death based on speed. Fr = 5 - given the context, Pr = 3 - possible to get hit when entering area, Av = 1 - probable to run.
3	Take the higher SIL requirement for the safety function = SIL 2

1. Deloitte Report: Wisdom of Enterprise Knowledge Graphs <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/de/Documents/operations/knowledge-graphs-pov.pdf>

2

Question

Technically we can capture and extract information about safety and reliability, and classify events

BUT each group that does this, **does it in their own way.**

HOW to do this

- a) so, concepts can be **shared and reused**, and
- b) in a **machine-readable way?**

2

Text, image and multimodal AI has arrived

2

The world has changed

Narrow AI performs **specific tasks** with high proficiency.

Good for repetitive processes and patterns with narrow scope for which data is available

- Classification
- Translation
- Digital assistants
- Email filtering

Generative AI large language models perform **wide range** of tasks.

Good for generating responses by considering hundreds of potential completions for a given **prompt** and choosing the most likely one based on its training.

Logic-based AI is for **reasoning**.

Good when rigor is needed to draw conclusions from facts and rules, apply logical inference and for semantic interoperability.

ICONS from Noun Project: 6348230, 6418841, 4814710

6

Extracting knowledge from written technical texts with NLP

Annotated training data used to fine tune transformer model to extract triples at scale on 100,000s of unseen texts

Injured person was removing guard off of drive shaft to work on transmission and felt pain in his **groin**. He did not request medical attention until 02/02/06 and was diagnosed with an inguinal hernia. Physician placed **injured person** on restricted duty and referred to a specialist/general surgeon. The specialist will do surgery at end of February.

A roof **fall** occurred in the intersection of the #2 entry of J-main #2 at spud 41-05. The **fall** measured approx. 100' x 20' x 6'. The **fall** did extend beyond the horizon of the anchor bolts.

Injured person was helping repair a **continuous miner** conveyor chain. He was holding a hammer against the chain while another **injured person** was striking it to drive in coupling link. The **injured person** **striking** the coupling link struck the **injured person** on **left hand** fracturing the 5th digit.

Texts from WA Dept of Mines and Petroleum incident records

Knowledge graph can be queried to address specific questions

Query examples:

1. Find all serious accidents involving female and male operators on haul trucks resulting in back injuries.
2. Given a serious accident occurred what is the probability that it involved equipment?
3. How many driving accidents involved males aged 25-34?

Dr. Michael Stewart's work 2020. Demo available at <https://aquila.nlp-tlp.org/projects/dashboard>

7

Causal analysis

Automatically extract structured causal information from *long text* records

- What are the **most frequent**, or **most costly**, or **most recent** CAUSES of centrifugal pump **failures** at my facility (from 98,000 notifications)

Long text record

Brief description of what occurred (e.g. basic sequence of events and impacts, avoiding the use of personnel names):

The burner has faulted several times when attempting to relight the H2 plant due to misalignment of the striker. It appears the collar on the shaft, that should limit travel, has slipped down causing the end of the ram to bend. See attached photos.

Immediate action taken

E/I Techs are currently bridging the top proxy sensor to get burner to light when required.

Define work requirements; including known materials, specialist labour, special tools that are required:

Dismantle ram and burner arm and straighten all components. Reposition collar on shaft and retighten. 2 x E/I techs, 6hrs.

Knowledge graph

Hershowitz, B., Hodkiewicz, M., Bikaun, T., Stewart, M. and Liu, W., 2024. Causal knowledge extraction from long text maintenance documents. *Computers in Industry*, 161, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0166361524000381>

8

Classification of failure modes

- **Large Language Models** (LLMs) such as **ChatGPT** exhibit excellent performance on a wide range of tasks.
- Early work shows good performance on classification of equipment failures with **fine-tuned models to ISO 14224 codes**.
- Work is being extended to event classification in safety records

Failure mode	Narrow AI	GPT-3.5	GPT-3.5 (FT)
Breakdown	0.37	0.44	1.00
Electrical	0.67	0.50	0.67
Leaking	0.67	0.86	1.00
Minor in-service problems	0.73	0.11	1.00
Structural deficiency	0.60	0.57	1.00
Vibration	0.67	1.00	1.00
Micro-F1	0.60	0.46	0.81
Macro-F1	0.46	0.53	0.62

motor runs for a while and trips → electrical (failure mode)

Ref: Large Language Models for Failure Mode Classification: An Investigation 2024: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.08181>

9

Narrow and Gen Ai pipeline for extracting event sequence information from accident reports

Accident Summary	Cause
The pilot stated that, during the climb to cruise altitude, he noticed a loss of engine oil pressure. He declared an emergency with air traffic control (ATC) and requested to return to the airport. [...]	The mechanic's improper installation of the turbocharger assembly, which resulted in oil starvation and a subsequent total loss of the engine power.

Create and query a KG for event sequence

Use the NLP and Gen AI to annotate the raw texts

Constrain entities and relationship to top-level ontology

Allowed Entities	Allowed Relationships
PhysicalObject	hasParticipant
Person	hasPart
Activity	occursBefore
Event	contributesTo

Knowledge graph of entities and relationships

Linked Data concepts

European data

data.europa.eu The official portal for European data

Home | Data | EU Open Data Days | Academy | Community

Home > Publications > Data stories > Linking data: what does it mean?

01 August 2022

Linking data: what does it mean?

Linked data is a set of design principles for publishing **structured machine-readable data/ meta-data** that allow to link it with other data.

<https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/datastories/linking-data-what-does-it-mean>

Without standardisation there is chaos

Without guidelines or constraints, how information is captured is idiosyncratic.

e.g. the computer will not treat 'corrosion' and 'extensive corrosion' as two different nodes. Multiple verbs (predicates/ edges) are created.

2

Leading to incorrect answers

When we ask the graph ...

“How many valves have had corrosion?”

The **answer is zero** as the computer does not 'know' that a control and butterfly valves are both types of valve unless we have 'told' it so.

2

Solution: Linked Data

Use RDF (subject-predicate-object) – W3C open data standard

Use curated, managed, open ontologies and reference data libraries

Use International Resource Identifiers (IRI's) as names for things

2

Where is the Semantic layer for safety and reliability data?

One of a number of possible architectures for Linked data

"An ontology defines a **common vocabulary** for researchers who need to share information in a domain. It includes **machine-interpretable** definitions of basic **concepts** in the domain and **relations** among them".

(Noy & McGuinness, 2001)

15 min YouTube video on Linked Data
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qXUGA4yptXo>

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Hunting for open, shared, managed, versioned, downloadable 'safety' ontologies and RDLs

Web pages

EU Ontocommons Portal
 No safety concepts
<https://industryportal.enit.fr/ontologies>

OBO Foundry
 Only one safety-related ontology
<https://obofoundry.org/>

- Health Surveillance Ontology
- <https://github.com/SVA-SE/HSO>

Journal literature

None

BUT many, many, many published ontologies

WITHOUT GitHub links to instantiations and implementations

WITHOUT Persistent namespaces

NOT open and shared

No safety-specific RDLs mentioned in

https://www.cdbb.cam.ac.uk/files/industry_data_models_and_reference_data_libraries_0.pdf

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Re-Use existing resources

Open, shared ontology hosted on EU Ontocommons site

<https://industryportal.enit.fr/ontologies/IOF-MAINTENANCE>

synonym	failure
natural language definition	event that causes an item to lose its ability to perform a required function
example	explosion, seizure, loss of power, loss of control
explanatory note	the event can be the loss of the primary function or a combination of functions

Dereferenceable IRI – the definition can be found at a web address

<https://spec.industrialontologies.org/ontology/202401/maintenance/Maintenance/FailureEvent>

18

How can these current and emerging AI language tools be used safely and productively to improve how we manage safety?

And is there a role for ESREDA in this?

19

How can these current and emerging AI language tools be used safely and productively to improve how we manage safety?

And is there a role for ESREDA in this?

Can ESReDA be more than just a 'forum' for the **exchange of information, data** and current research in **Safety and Reliability**

Can **EsReDA actively engage** in the **development of Safety Linked Data and Ontologies?**

20

Examples of industry-specific open-source tools for cleaning, extracting and querying information from unstructured & structured texts

		<p>MaintNorm Corpus and benchmark model for lexical normalisation & masking of maintenance short text https://github.com/nlp-tlp/maintnorm</p>		
<p>QuickGraph Entity and relation annotation for KG extraction https://quickgraph.tech/</p>	<p>Redcoat Collaborative annotation for MWOS nlp-tlp.org/redcoat</p>	<p>MaintIE Fine-Grained Annotation Schema and Benchmark for IE from Low-Quality Maintenance Short Texts https://github.com/nlp-tlp/maintie</p>	<p>CleanGraph Error correction in KGs https://github.com/nlp-tlp/CleanGraph</p>	<p>Docs2KG Data Integration Tool https://github.com/AI4WA/Docs2KG</p>
<p>Lexiclean Lexical normalisation noisy corpora https://github.com/nlp-tlp/lexiclean</p>	<p>PUGGLE NER&R.Json to KG conversion python package https://pypi.org/project/puggle/</p>	<p>MUDLARK Cleaning CSV datasets that contain technical language https://pypi.org/project/mudlark/</p>	<p>Open Source LLM Chats https://llm.nlp-tlp.org/chat</p>	<p>JARV5 Multimodal Conversation https://llm.nlp-tlp.org/jarv5</p>

Thank you

- For list of papers please see <https://nlp-tlp.org/> and on Google Scholar
- For Code <https://github.com/nlp-tlp> and <https://github.com/uwasystemhealth>
- For Models <https://huggingface.co/nlp-tlp>
- Information on Centre for Transforming Maintenance through Data Science (CTMTDS) <https://www.maintenance.org.au/display/PUBLIC>
- Thank you to Dr. Caitlin Woods, Tyler Bikaun and Dr. Michael Stewart for permission to re-use and adapt their slides
- Contact details Melinda.Hodkiewicz@uwa.edu.au and <https://www.linkedin.com/in/melinda-hodkiewicz-b6bbba7/>

Keynote 3. Asterios Lialios

HSE Director

Elefsina Industrial Complex

Hellenic Petroleum RSSOPP S.A., Hellenic Energy S.A.

Safety Manager of the year 2024

Industry Talk

I have started my career as a Process Engineer in Petrola Hellas Refinery in 2000. I served as an Operations Engineer or as a Head of Dept. in various functions (Production, Oil Movement, Marine). Since 2012 I have been a Health, Safety, Fire Safety and Environment Manager in the Aspopyrgos and/or Elefsina refineries of HELPE. Since then I have been striving for the continuous improvement of the HSE performance of the refineries with a strong focus on standardization, innovation and human behaviour.

Having served in the Oil & Gas industry for more than 23 years and worked with renowned experts from companies like Shell and ExxonMobil, I have the conviction that Safety is not just “a priority” or “a company value”: it is the only sustainable way to operate.

Furthermore, I truly believe that Safety is not just about procedures, certifications and machinery: it is mainly about people, their beliefs, their behaviour and, ultimately, their life. Thus, I believe that the key function of the Health & Safety Manager is communication; with colleagues, with contractors and with society as a whole. For those reasons openness is not a “plus”, it is a “must” in order to cultivate a culture of trust, cooperation and transparency which in turn is the basis for a sustainable Safety Culture.

Keynote 4. Bill Hewlett

MA CEng FICE FIET, Civil & structural engineer

A science of professional engineering practice: our next step towards a safer engineering industry.

Bill built his career in construction, working for leading contractors Costain and Laing O'Rourke. At Costain he held the Group Technical Director position for 14 years. He has worked across most types of civil and structural engineering, in building construction, infrastructure, nuclear and petro-chem. From 2020 he developed his career as a consultant, incorporating the role of Technical Director at the British Board of Agrément 2021-2023. BBA provides fitness for purpose certification of construction products, a process involving detail product assessments, analyses and testing.

From 2009 - 2013 Bill served as a Vice President of the Institution of Civil Engineers and in 2015 was elected to the Board of the Engineering Council, as the ICE's representative. In 2016 he became Chair of SCOSS, the Standing Committee on Structural Safety. In 2010 Bill founded the Temporary Works Forum, which he chaired until 2007; TWf has 200+ corporate members. He has served on a number of Boards including for Thomas Telford Ltd, the Forensic Engineering Journal, Lloyds Register Foundation and the Hazards Forum. He contributes to academic work across the fields of procurement, safety science, engineering management and the philosophy of engineering. He holds an honorary chair at Cardiff University Business School.

Bill's quest is for better engineering. He is recognised for his understanding of engineering safety, and his delivery of organisational competence for engineering success.

Abstract

Society, now and for the foreseeable future, relies on engineering. Engineering performance, and thereby the benefit that it can bring, has been much enhanced by work in the underpinning social, economic and physical sciences. The work of ESReDA, for instance, which has done much to develop safety science, evidences this. But to deliver impact in a project or practical instance of engineering endeavour, we need at least satisfactory performance in all underpinnings, not only perfection in one or a few. A balanced scorecard if you will. So some basic questions emerge: What is the full set of underpinning sciences, are we missing one or two and thereby, for practical purposes, undermining the rest? Are there some other underpinnings we need to recognise? What level of maturity is needed in each underpinning, and what are their relative importance in different circumstances? Added to these questions are complexities created by, for instance, having to balance commercial drivers and societal good, the individual and the team, a highly diverse epistemology, inadvertent influences from client, regulator and others, the call for certainty alongside the imperative to innovate. The speaker has made a career as a practitioner navigating and leading in this complex field. In this keynote he will explain the tools he uses and go on to propose a science of professional engineering practice as a route to assuring safety in, and from, the future practice of engineering.

**A Science of Engineering Practice:
Our next step towards a safer
engineering industry**

**Bill Hewlett – ESReDA 15 November
2024**

Early career

University

Site engineering

Temporary works engineering

Site engineering

Operational safety control

Cologne, 2009
(or HEX,
or Nicholl Highway)

Operational safety control

If I am working on a deep excavation like Cologne, a collapse would be catastrophic, but how likely is it to occur?

1. Daily near me
2. Daily across industry
3. Once a year nationally
4. Rare nationally
5. Rare globally

Operational safety control

Cynefin framework

Figure 1. The Cynefin Sensemaking Framework (Kurtz and Snowden, 2003; Snowden and Boone 2007).

From Gosling et al (2022) Complex Systematic Failures in the Edinburgh Schools Case from EngineeringX Safer Complex Systems Case Studies pp126-134 RAEng (London)

Cynefin framework

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From Gosling et al (2022) Complex Systematic Failures in the Edinburgh Schools Case from EngineeringX Safer Complex Systems Case Studies pp126-134 RAEng (London)

Engineering history and safety science

Generational forgetfulness

Generational forgetfulness

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Briefing: Temporary Works Forum: how history and narrative shaped a major safety initiative
Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Forensic Engineering
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13689597.2023.2282071>

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Keywords: temporary works; temporary works

Forensic Engineering **ice Publishing**

Briefing: Temporary Works Forum: how history and narrative shaped a major safety initiative

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Chair 2009–2017, Temporary Works Forum, London, UK
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The Temporary Works forum was founded to give a place for professionals to come together and share their experience and learning about temporary works. 2019 marked its 10th anniversary. In this article, the founding chair reflects on why he, and the founding secretary, launched the forum, and draws lessons from its success: an understanding of historic context and a respect for narrative are considered to have been vital. Building on a sound

Timeframe analysis

Depending on your role, what is your timeframe to impact (in regard to construction phase or operational safety)?

1. Seconds/minutes
2. Hours/day
3. Week
4. Month
5. Quarter
6. Year
7. Decade
8. Century

Timeframe analysis – Grenfell – market control & incentivisation

Philosophy and engineering – Edinburgh Course

The poster for the University of Edinburgh's Leading Major Programmes (MSc | PgCert | PgDip) features a photograph of a cable-stayed bridge. The text on the poster includes 'THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH' at the top and 'Leading Major Programmes MSc | PgCert | PgDip' at the bottom.

- change at all these levels; and
- **Philosophy** to realise the value of the right types of thinking and thought-ecosystems to successful leadership.

Knowledge in operational engineering

Following Donald A Schön, Michael Davis & Samuel C Florman

Knowledge in operational engineering

Conclusion

Engineering control

**A Science of Engineering Practice:
Our next step towards a safer
engineering industry**

Discussion

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Keynote 5. Maria Chiara Leva

Senior Lecturer

Lead of the Human factors in Safety and Sustainability (HFISS)

Technical University of Dublin

**Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems.
A human-centred perspective.**

Maria Chiara Leva is the Lead of the Human factors in Safety and Sustainability (HFISS) research group in Technological University Dublin and a Senior Lecturer in the School of Environmental Health for the same institution. She is a visiting research Fellow in the Centre for Innovative Human systems in Trinity College Dublin. She is the co-founder of Tosca Solutions (www.toscasolutions.com) a Spin out campus company based in NDRC and Trinity College Dublin to offer support for implementing risk management tools customised specifically to the needs of highly regulated environments. Her area of Expertise is Human factors and Safety Management Systems. Chiara holds a PhD in Human factors conferred by the Polytechnic of Milano Department of Industrial Engineering. She is the former chair of The Irish Ergonomics Society and current co-chair of the technical committee for Human factors in the European Safety and Reliability Association.

Abstract

“Organizations that use machines merely to displace workers through automation will miss the full potential of AI...Tomorrow’s leader will instead be those that embrace collaborative intelligence, transforming their operations, their industries and - no less important - their workforces.” H.J. Wilson and P.R. Daugherty (Human + Machine: Reimagining Work in the Age of AI Harvard Business Review Press, 2018)

The need for human in the loop automation is particularly relevant for safety critical industry where industrial accidents related to technological malfunctioning have been diminishing leaving the human error responsible for up to 80% of the accidents. However, even if one of the main aims of introducing automation is often to improve safety by reducing or eliminating human errors; it is often argued that this may simply induce new types of errors.

To take full advantage of human machine collaboration, companies must understand how humans can most effectively augment machines, how machines can enhance what humans do best, and how to redesign business processes to support the partnership.

The opportunity is that the proliferation of wearable sensors that can track human factors in a non-intrusive manner coupled with the abilities of modern AI systems to integrate heterogeneous data to identify anomalies and safety critical situation can now transform the role of the human in the loop for safety critical systems also.

To address this changing and exciting landscape there is a need to consider the followings multidisciplinary aspects:

- 1) Capability to understand our own limitation as human being and cope/use them as another element of live data for Industry 4.0 (to understand what aspect of human performance can be assessed and monitored considering the new capabilities offered by Neuroergonomics tool such as EEG and Eye tracking and what can be considered a

legitimate and ethical aspect to assess. Whether for mutual performance monitoring in a teaming environment or for also self-monitoring and feedback.)

- 2) Capability to harness and analyse live data from for industry 4.0 for control of safety critical process to train new AI algorithms to anticipate safety critical scenarios.
- 3) Capability to create novel hybrid collaborative intelligence frameworks to combine the two main key live data sources to support decision and or anticipate critical scenarios in Human-machine Performance optimizations, whereby the human and the intelligent and or autonomous agents can really work as a team.

In the present talk we will just briefly present some areas of application and the key challenges and opportunities they raise in terms of function allocation, dependability and overall system performance. In this sense a collaborative intelligent creative gesture is an innovation that required a combined effort from an intelligent, robotic or autonomous agent and a human.

These projects were funded by the European Commission

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems: challenges and opportunities

CISC
Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020. No. 955901 &
Maria Chiara Leva
Technological University Dublin, City Campus, Ireland

H2020-Grant Agreement Number 957402

The people making this possible

<p>Aayush JAIN Hosting Institution: IMR - Supervisor: Prof. Philip LONG in</p>			
<p>Naira LÓPEZ CAÑELLAS Hosting Institution: European DIGITAL SME Alliance - Supervisor: Prof. Apha KERR in</p>			
<p>Inês FERNANDES RAMOS Hosting Institution: URIM - Supervisor: Prof. Gabriele GIANNI in</p>			

Collaborative intelligence

"Organizations that use machines merely to displace workers through automation will miss the full potential of AI... Tomorrow's leaders will instead be those that embrace collaborative intelligence, transforming their operations, their industries and –no less important– their workforces."

A "human-centric" approach to AI that collaborate with humans rather than replace them.**

Human contribution:

Train

Explain

Sustain

* Daugherty, P.R.&Wilson, H.J., 2018. Human+Machine: Reimagining Work in the Age of AI. Harvard Business Press.

** Leva, M.C., Podofilini, L. "Assessing Human Performance and Human Reliability in Collaborative Intelligence Scenarios: Upcoming Challenges and Opportunities" in Proceedings of ESREL2020-PSAM15

Collaborative intelligence

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Collaborative intelligence

A “human-centric” approach to AI that collaborate with humans rather than replace them.

AI Systems’ contribution:

Amplify

Interact

Embody

* Leva, M.C., Podofilini, L. “Assessing Human Performance and Human Reliability in Collaborative Intelligence Scenarios: Upcoming Challenges and Opportunities” in Proceedings of ESREL2020-PSAM15

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems

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The CISC Approach to DOE

The CISC Living Labs: collaborative intelligence examples

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems
*Grant Agreement 955901 - Collaborative Intelligence for safety Critical Systems (CISC). H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020.

6

Count of Alarms per 10 min

The graph illustrates the rate of alarms per 10 min over the period from 17 January to 21 February in a UK based Oil and Gas facility.

Count of Alarms per 10 min by Severity

The graph illustrates the count of alarms per 10 min over the period from 17 January to 21 February by level of Severity (100, 200, 300, 500)

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Clustering and Bayesian Network proof of concept

1. **Clustering of alarms** based on correlation and identification of alarms related to the shutdown of the valves of the wellhead
2. **Prediction of the trip** of the shutdown valves of the wellhead 15 second before it happened
3. **Root cause analysis** to prevent the shutting down of the wellhead valves and remove redundant alarms

1. Clustering of alarms

Identification of **clusters of alarms** to identify **scenarios**.

Possibility of **Grouping the alarms** base on high correlation to **reduce number of alarms** shown to the operator

These **groups of alarms** can be linked to a known cause and **labeled** using **expert knowledge**. The model can then display the causes of the alarms and assist in decision making in case of cognitive overload.

Figure: Correlation map between alarms of the wellheads. Lighter colors denotes higher correlations

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical systems

Bayesian Network

Powerful **machine learning** technique to model causal interaction between variables

BN model interaction between alarms in the systems. Can be used to **predict alarms, Trips** and **identify root causes**. Can **Estimate risk** and **cost** of a process upset.

The model allows **Transparency** in reasoning and **trustworthy decision**

Can be use for a short cuts to becoming an experience operator thank to the decision-making models.

ciscproject.eu

3. Possible Root cause analysis

Redundancy between the alarms to predict the trip of the wellhead.

3 alarms to predict the trip with 90% chance **over 38**

Possibility to **reduce the number of alarm** display to the operator.

Alarm prioritization in terms of increase of probability of TRIP

Top 3 Alarms (026 Gas compression system)
A_026BPZI070 Low Low Gas compression pressure indicator
026BF1064 Open Alarm Gas compression press flow indicator
026BPI047 Hight Gas compression pressure indicator

Table: Alarm order in term of increase of probability of the TRIP of the wellhead.

Experiment: alarm management & intervention simulator

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Live Lab 3 : Decision making support in control room

Type of plant - Chemical Process Industry (Formaldehyde production).
Alarm flood condition: present

Factors varied: Alarm design (Investigating problem 1)

Time	Event	Priority	State	Time	Tag	In
00:00:00	1 Active	Critical	Active	00:01:37	FAL11	H
00:00:00	2 Active	Medium	Active	00:04:38	TAH17	A
00:00:00	3 Active	Low	Active	00:05:40	FAH08	H
00:00:00	4 Active	Critical	Active	00:05:41	CAL20	A
00:00:00	5 Active	Medium	Active	00:05:53	FAL20	A
00:00:00	6 Active	Low	Active	00:06:02	FAL18	A
00:00:00	7 Active	Medium	Active	00:06:06	FAL08	H
00:00:00	8 Active	Low	Active	00:06:26	TAH18	A
00:00:00	9 Active	Medium	Active	00:06:34	TAH20	A
00:00:00	10 Active	Low	Active	00:06:54	TAH12	H

Micaela Demichela, Gabriele Baldissone, and Gianfranco Camunoli.
Risk-Based Decision Making for the Management of Change in Process Plants: Benefits of Integrating Probabilistic and Phenomenological Analysis. *Industrial Engineering Chemistry Research* 2017 56 (50), 14873-14887

This experiment is to

- investigate the **impact of decision support systems** on control room operators in safety critical status,
- analyse the **different factors** impacting **its ability to perceive and then respond** (conduct actions on the monitor) to **critical alarms**.
- There are four groups of participants (with different level of HMI support) and 3 scenarios with different level of complexity

What does human in the loop mean?

- There are different types of “humans” in the machine learning loop
- human-in-the-loop decision-making is where content is flagged by the AI and human moderators review what has been flagged and confirm whether the machine was correct in order to enhance the algorithm's decision-making? (**this is one of the most widely used concept..but often not working well..**)

True HITL automation allows human intervention to execute actions and control the entire workflow. By allowing ad hoc application of human judgment, it's more flexible and powerful. (Forbes technology council 2022)

The support Interface:

For GROUP 4 only it contains an AI generated recommendation system

The support interface will appear on the right monitor, and it shows 4 sections.

The top left, shows the list of alarms and their different characteristics (name, state, priority, time, tag, section and acknowledgement case where the participant should click to acknowledge it).

The top right, shows the procedures section. the participant should click on the specific section then the specific alarm to view its corresponding procedure.

The bottom left, is a graph that shows and the flow of water and product concentration in the absorber.

The bottom right, is the AI recommendation system

AI-Enhanced Recommendation System

Within Participants (Group 4)

24

Group 3 vs Group 4

25

- It was observed that the participant that follows through AI suggestions tend to **solve** the problem **earlier** with **lesser** task **load**.
- However, with **lower** situational **awareness** as compared to the other participant that followed screen procedures.

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Situation Awareness Observation protocol results

SPAM-adapted Questions:

1. Which of these alarms, in your opinion, requires to be verified first and why?
2. Why do you think the critical alarm is activated? And what do you intend to do?
3. After your actions, what do you think is going to change in the system? Why?

Results from S1

EEG correlation Matrix

Reaction time has been added to the correlation matrix. For the 5 mins Recording after main alarm for each scenario.

Future work

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- Redesign the AI DSS Display (only for summarising situation no details instructions)
- Redesign Digital Procedure
- Real-time Operator-System Interaction Modelling
- Labelled human action in historian or DCS logs to also correlate first response action to the alarm they refer to
- Identifying other possible way to solve situations.

Cross sectional aspects in collaborative intelligence applications

HRA models to understand humans

Mental workload is a variable closely connected with Human-System Performance. *

$$\Pr (X_{ni} = 1) = \frac{e^{b_n - d_i}}{1 + e^{b_n - d_i}}$$

Worker performance can be individually characterised by observable characteristics some of them obtained via bio-sensors. *

* Leva et al. "Task complexity, and operators' capabilities as predictor of human error" in ESREL 2018

Moving towards a more pervasive assessment of the humans in the systems

- IOT, wearable technologies and AI are enhancing capacity to assess the human in the system in a way that was not possible before.

5th

Mass customization & cyber physical cognitive systems

Continuous modeling of MWL (Milos)

A Deep learning approach for EEG data analysis to recognise high mental workload situations

- Instead of modeling MWL with custom tasks difficulties – make the NN learn tasks difficulties
- Problem Model that predict NASA MABT task does not perform well on assembly task

Conclusions Key challenges and opportunities

Collaborative Intelligence for Safety Critical Systems

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Welcome to ESREL SRA-E
in Stavanger, Norway!

15-19 June 2025

METHODOLOGIES

Accident and Incident Modeling

Decision Making under Uncertainty

Foundations of Risk and Reliability Assessment and Management

Human Factors and Human Reliability

Maintenance Modeling and Applications

Mathematical and Computational Methods in Reliability and Safety

Organizational Factors and Safety Culture

Prognostics and System Health Management

Resilience Engineering

Risk Assessment

Risk Management

Structural Reliability Applications

System Reliability Applications

Uncertainty Analysis

Human Factors and Human Reliability

The focus of this technical committee is the analysis of human performance for the safe and reliable operation of complex socio-technical systems. The technical committee fosters research and collaborations on methods, applications, and on the use of analysis results for decision-making.

This committee keeps together the human reliability analysis and human factors disciplines: the ESREL conference is one of the few occasions in which both communities meet. Our aim is to jointly benefit from sharing the latest advances of both fields.

Examples of topics of interest for the committee are:

- Characterization, measurement, and models of performance influencing factors
- Integration of the human component in risk and resilience engineering
- Human performance models and data in complex socio-technical systems
- Human reliability analysis

The committee maintains close links with the

- Human Reliability Analysis Society, <http://hrasociety.org/blog/>
- The Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Management (PSAM) Conference <http://www.apsam.org/>

Chair:
 Luca Podofillini - Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland

Co-Chair:
 Chiara Leva - Technological University Dublin, Ireland

Plenary Presentations

Management system for regulatory requirements applicable to environmentally classified industrial facilities

Emmanuel PLOT, emmanuel.plot@ineris.fr

Vassishtasai RAMANY, vassishtasai.ramany-bala-poubady@intradef.gouv.fr

Christophe COLL, christophe.coll@dekra.com

Frederic BAUDEQUIN, frederic.baudequin@interactive.fr

Abstract

We propose to present an approach to managing major industrial risks to the environment that we developed at Seveso high threshold sites for the storage of hydrocarbons, the manufacture of fertilisers or pyrotechnics, and at dams. The basic idea behind this approach is that these sites must demonstrate their ability to manage major risks, but that the risk analyses prove nothing until proof is provided of the truth of their premises, the logical validity of their arguments, the realism of their conclusions, and the effective implementation of the modelled risk control measures and tasks. Demonstrating risk control is therefore an ongoing process based on piloting and monitoring the correspondence between these items and the reality of industrial processes and their environments. Risk assessments are the basis, but not the complete demonstration. Is this a new idea? Certainly not. But what does seem new to us, and what we would like to present, is the risk management approach that we have built around this simple idea. The difficulty we have faced in achieving this is the implementation of a flexible digital platform, made necessary by the quantity and diversity of the data, methods, models, and regulatory requirements to be managed, and moreover by the number and diversity of the stakeholders. The design of the database came up against a major scientific obstacle, that of the diversity of representations of the various risk management stakeholders, and therefore of the different types of process for developing or using all these data, methods, models, and regulatory requirements; a source of richness but also of misunderstanding, mistrust and, ultimately, under certain conditions, of increased risk. This is the problem of the silos of expertise and disciplines in the face of the need for distributed/shared cognition to build up one database around a single and holistic risk model (a common operational picture). We would like to present the stages of our method and our Web IT tools.

Introduction

For ten years, Vassishtasai RAMANY, environmental manager and then deputy director of SNOI (the French part of NATO's oil pipeline network in Central Europe), Christophe COLL, environmental engineer specialising in risk assessment at Dekra Industrial, and Emmanuel PLOT, philosopher specialising in major risk management systems and IT at INERIS, worked closely together to design a method supported by IT tools to provide the transparency needed to manage the major risks for SNOI's network of 14 oil depots. Previously, Emmanuel PLOT had design a model of a good organisation for managing major risks (Plot, E., 2007), an integrated risk and critical task model for designing simulations in virtual environments (Plot 2010), and during the ten years of the SNOI project, he has been working on the SNOI method also with several colleagues, first as part of the European Tosca project (Leva, C., 2019), then with other industrial partners. Frederic Baudequin of Interactive, a French company, provided the IT foundation and continuous support.

The starting point is the need to comply with environmental regulations. It is difficult, because there is a profusion of themes (water, soil and subsoil, air, waste, noise, accidental and chronic risks, planning requirements or exemption requests, ageing monitoring) and applicable texts that are constantly evolving: decrees (ministerial, prefectural, municipal), agreements (collective or between two companies), administrative regulations (internal regulations, internal charters, employment or commercial contracts), professional guides) and, linked to this, numerous risk studies published in separate reports several hundred pages long. The Environment Code itself, which is supposed to provide a general framework, is extremely difficult to read, and its links with other codes, such as the Town Planning Code, are no easier to decipher (Morel, C., 2018). We have no reason to

complain about the number of standards. They have their *raison d'être*. But it is so difficult to deal with the multiplicity of regulatory aspects, the heterogeneity of deadlines and expectations, and the diversity of knowledge management cycles to be taken into account. The method consists of supporting the interpretation of the law, in order to achieve its strict application.

For this, risk analysis is the key, because they enable regulations to be interpreted in the light of the realities on the ground, they eliminate arbitrary decisions, and they organize cooperation to understand, prioritize and resolve problems. But risk analyses are not enough, because they prove nothing. Rather, they should be seen as promises. They are not demonstrations in the strict sense of the term. They must be supplemented by protocols designed to prove that they are in line with reality and that they remain so over time. These protocols take up the results of the risk analyses and verify their veracity, so that they are, strictly speaking, demonstrations of risk control. The introduction and dynamic monitoring of these protocols make risk management organizations more transparent and easier to manage (Leva, C., 2015). This is what the method is all about.

Presentation of the method

Step 1: List all the fundamental problems to be solved

The first step is to draw up a systematic list of all the fundamental issues that need to be addressed. What is the basis for this list? The answer that immediately springs to mind is the Environmental Code. It's a good idea, but difficult to put into practice. Because the Environment Code is huge. It covers so many subjects and so many subtleties. It would require an army of specialists. It's not realistic for an operator. It's not their job. The pragmatic solution chosen by the SNOI was to prefer to rely on prefectural operating authorization decrees. Aren't these supposed to include all the requirements established in accordance with the Environmental Code and the industrial processes studied in the risk analyses? In other words, aren't they the interface between the legal system and the reality on the ground? Wouldn't this be an excellent basis for avoiding any blind spots in terms of ICPE regulations? The work has already been done by the inspectorate. Valuable work on which operators can rely.

Step 2: Asking the right questions

Operating license requirements must be understood to be complied with. They cannot be applied automatically. First and foremost, it is important to identify the purpose of the requirement: why was it written in the first place? Then we need to think about the best ways of achieving it. It seems appropriate to consider these regulations as questions put to the operator, of the type: 'you, the operator, how do you go about complying with this or that? The first thing to do, then, is to 'slice and dice' the texts of the decrees to extract the list of questions that need to be answered.

Step 3: Answer

Clarifying the issues raised by the specifications

In many cases, it is necessary to interpret the requirements by delving into the risk analyses to which they refer, to fully understand them. The questions then become clearer:

- How can a given level of confidence be maintained in each barrier?
- How can we guarantee the validity of the estimated frequency of a given initiating event under a given condition?
- How can we guarantee that a given hazard potential will not be exceeded? How can we control the parameters considered in modelling a given hazardous event (pressure, temperature, etc.)?

- How can we ensure control of the parameters linked to certain exclusions in each part of a given risk analysis, or to potential changes in the issues at stake that are likely to have an impact on the estimate of severity?

In addition, very often the requirements are written in such a way that important aspects of the questions are not immediately understandable. In this case, the requirements need to be supplemented. For example, probabilistic aspects tend to disappear from operating license requirements when they require the implementation of a particular barrier without reference to acceptance of its probability of failure under stress, or to the safety architecture in which it fits. In addition, reference to the criticality of the hazardous phenomena affected by any failure of this barrier is generally omitted. This is particularly problematic when the failure of this barrier, given the frequencies of initiating events and other safety barriers, and given the importance of the issues at stake, degrades the level of risk control without making it unacceptable. Ultimately, risk management must systematically be based on an analysis of the criticality of accident scenarios. This criticality is dynamic (Amalberti, R., 1996). It changes according to several parameters (state of barriers, etc.), which makes it particularly complex to manage. By incorporating these parameters into a model, efforts can be concentrated on risk management and on the necessary continuous updating of operator representations (Amalberti, R. 1996).

Defining doctrines and critical tasks

The resulting questions are posed one by one to the organization. What are we doing about it? What are we doing about it? Is it sufficient? Satisfactory? Do we need to improve? The answers are written in the form of doctrines, i.e., management rules adapted to the organization in question, to be implemented to answer the questions. This is the structure of an organization manual.

As in any organization, these rules are translated into tasks, which are the subject of various procedures, instructions, or operating methods. These tasks can be described as critical. The doctrine is the most general level of organization, the task the most detailed. Tasks define the objectives that operators must achieve to control risks and demonstrate this control. They correspond to the definition of a job to be carried out, and to the prescribed and formal description of the actions to be carried out. A critical task is the description of an action whose failure reduces the level of risk control.

Doctrines and tasks must be thought out, designed, and developed with those who will be responsible for them, with their references, their good practices, and their cultures (at the risk of being unrealistic), and then assumed by Management. It is not up to the inspector to prescribe the means that the manufacturer must implement. That is not his role. He can, however, adopt the operator's good practices and include them in his instructions.

The challenge is obviously to deal with as many requirements as possible with as few doctrines and tasks as possible.

By carrying out risk analyses

Doctrines refer (or should refer) to the risk analyses that precede or extend them, just as regulatory requirements refer to or require risk analyses. These analyses make it possible to interpret regulations in the light of the realities on the ground, eliminate arbitrary decisions and organize cooperation to understand, prioritize and resolve problems.

This is why critical tasks:

- require risk analyses to be carried out,
- control:
 - the realism of their premises (based on the best available data, or the best available scientific knowledge or expertise),
 - the logical validity of their arguments (based on methodological references),

- the realism of their conclusions (based on indicators that are as independent as possible of the arguments),
- the effective implementation of risk control measures.

When the problems are simple, known, controlled and generic, these analyses are implicit and therefore do not need to be formalized. They are obvious and accepted by everyone. On the other hand, when the problems are complicated, poorly understood, and specific, they may be imposed on the operator by regulations or decided voluntarily. They are not opposed to regulations or doctrines but precede or specify them: they clarify questions and provide answers.

By establishing demonstration protocols that extend the risk analyses

Checking premises

These risk analyses are based on premises that need to be verified (Peschard I., et al, 2022). The aim is to check that reality corresponds to the facts considered by these analyses. This is an ongoing process because reality is always in flux. In practice, these verifications are carried out by means of initial or additional studies, each time calling on the expertise of specialists in the realities under consideration: laboratory tests, controls, and various studies. Of course, these complementary analyses generally build on each other.

The premises are validated on the basis of their consistency and complementarity. For example, the validity of a measure to monitor the presence of environmentally hazardous substances in the water of a piezometer located downstream of a site presupposes the coordinated validity of:

- an analysis specifying the safety functions to be ensured (in particular the type of substance to be monitored),
- a hydrogeological study to define the functional specifications of the piezometers,
- an engineering file to check compliance with these specifications in the field,
- the file for each piezometer, which specifies the operating procedure to be followed for the readings (frequency, parameters, and practices to be observed),
- the organization of the readings (who, what equipment and what skills),
- the organization of laboratory analyses,
- the skills of the experts who will read and interpret the results from a risk perspective.

Checking the logical validity of arguments

Checking the logical validity of arguments is traditionally the 'paper' work of third-party experts or inspectors. They check the logical rigour of the arguments and compliance with the principles defined in the reference methodological guides, such as the INERIS Omega. But the more voluminous the analyses, the more delicate the task. It is not easy to find the logic of the reasoning in hundreds of pages of PDF files. The documents often exceed 1000 pages (with their appendices), and often refer to other studies. It should also be noted that the referential integrity of proposals is all the more difficult to establish as their formulation or conception changes during the drafting process. It is difficult to be perfectly consistent when writing voluminous studies over several months, if only in the formulation of proposals. Even more so when the initial data - the premises - provided to the analysts on the processes and their environment are clarified or simply modified during the analysis, and whole sections of the argument must be reworked afterwards.

Checking conclusions

In addition to checking the premises and the rigour of the argument, it is necessary to verify, as far as possible, the realism of the results. This can be done either by tracking down aberrant conclusions, or by relying on indicators that are as independent as possible of the argumentative logic. Note that this is easier for the risks

of chronic emissions of pollutants, but more difficult, if not impossible, for major accident scenarios which, by definition, are simply possible and therefore undetectable or apprehensible in reality, independently of a model.

Checking the implementation of risk control measures

In addition to the above checks, which question the reliability and incompleteness of the demonstrations, the operational conclusions of the risk analyses must be drawn by implementing the measures identified to guarantee a level of control that is acceptable from the regulatory point of view.

It should be noted that this requirement can be considered as a sub-category of the premises control work. These measures make it possible to ensure that the risk studies correspond to the reality of the installations. The premises approach can be seen as simply more encompassing in that it also raises questions about the reliability and potentially incomplete nature of the elements on which the arguments justifying the importance of these measures are based.

By carrying out critical tasks

These protocols complete the system for answering questions raised by regulatory requirements. They complete the demonstration of risk control. They are made up of tasks or combinations of tasks linked together by dependency relationships. These tasks may be external to operational tasks, or intrinsically linked to production, maintenance, or logistics. They include:

- Tasks for controlling precise parameters, defined to ensure the ongoing validity of the premises of risk analyses concerning:
 - exclusions (including hazard potential threshold),
 - frequencies of initiating events
 - confidence level of barriers
 - modelling assumptions
 - severity of potential accidents.
- Or tasks that require additional analysis to refine the specifications of other tasks.
- Or tasks involving checking the risk analysis procedures themselves: checking the conditions under which these analyses are carried out or the methods used.
- Or tasks to check that the conclusions of the risk analysis are realistic (when they are chronic).

These tasks can be directly linked to the doctrines when the risk analyses are not formalized because the subject is simple, known and mastered.

The resources allocated to these tasks are managed:

- Management of the distribution of roles and responsibilities for carrying out the tasks
- Skills management
- Equipment management
- Management of methods, procedures, guides, operating modes, or instructions
- Management of task objective updates

These tasks are also associated with records that provide proof that they have been carried out correctly or that the desired results have been achieved.

By recording these tasks as evidence

Critical tasks are recorded. Some of these records can be used as evidence. These records, this evidence, are necessarily based on the choice of certain parameters, which are limited, considered to be genuinely relevant and likely to change over time. Not everything can be controlled or proven. We must admit this pragmatically,

without complexes, and try to make relevant and strategic choices, considering the costs/benefits in determining these parameters. These choices are up for discussion. They must be debatable, and discussed until they appear to be the most relevant, without discussion, and are validated by the COPIL.

These parameters must be precisely associated with the objectives and resources that they enable to be monitored. Otherwise, there can be no reflection on the relevance of their choice and use, and on the limits of their validity. We need to be able to trace parameters back to doctrines and regulatory requirements. The simplest way of doing this is to consider these parameters as records linked to critical tasks. In this way, we know how they are considered, how the data is produced, by whom and under what conditions. In this way, the evidence appears as compilations (or aggregations), at the level of the doctrines, of the records of critical tasks.

It should also be noted that:

- Evidence (and the parameters on which it is based) must be open to challenge and may have only temporary validity, justified by changes in operations or advances in scientific or technical knowledge.
- Evidence can be introduced gradually, according to an order of priority to be established. It takes time to involve people and time to discuss choices, to experiment when problems are new, to find resources, and then time to implement them. It is then that the inspector, lawyer, and judge can assess the bona fides of what has been put in place.
- Evidence is produced for the operator before it is produced for the inspector. The operator wants to know whether what he has asked his organization to do is being done properly. This is a good investment rationale, which builds confidence.
- As far as possible, the proof should not represent a new effort for the organization. Ideally, it should be based on existing practices, such as maintenance software. Maintenance data is already reliable. It already exists. Using it costs nothing (or very little!).
- The evidence can:
 - o be widely tested by the profession, or be custom designed,
 - o refers to short cycles of data collection (every second, for example) or long cycles (every ten years).
- Evidence must be adapted to the kinetics of the phenomena and the time required to intervene.

By periodically recalculating the criticality of hazardous phenomena

A risk analysis is an estimate of the probability of occurrence of possible hazardous phenomena in the future, based on current knowledge of past events. Ongoing work on critical tasks enables us to update our knowledge of exclusions, frequencies of triggering events, barriers, the modelling of hazardous phenomena and the sensitivity of the issues at stake, and therefore to periodically redo the calculations. This regular review of analyses provides a solid basis for risk management.

Step 4: Management

Based on risk management demonstration protocols

Nothing is set in stone, because the reality of an industrial plants is constantly evolving: staff turnover, changes to processes or the environment, ageing facilities, change of supplier, etc. The risk management organization is based on realities that are constantly changing. The greater the risks, the greater the need for precision, and the more these changes, however small they may appear, can profoundly alter the level of risk control, and must be considered by the organization.

These changes cannot lead to a revision of the regulatory requirements or of the risk analyses, but only of the protocols for demonstrating risk control, i.e., the ability to carry out the critical tasks, which are responsible for

justifying or verifying the premises, arguments, or conclusions of the risk analyses.

Management must therefore be based on demonstration protocols, to check, on a cyclical basis, that they are still in place and that responses to regulatory requirements are being implemented, in line with the reality on the ground.

With the help of a steering committee

There are no technical choices in terms of processes, then doctrines and risk analyses, then organizational investments, then validation by the steering committee: the choices must be analyzed, taking into account risks, processes and organizational capabilities, and steered by the steering committee.

This requires a committed and well-trained management team, which, without going into the technical details, has an overview of the possible solutions to decide whether or not to invest.

Worth noting:

- The steering committee meets regularly, every six months, and is chaired by the director.
- The steering committee focuses on unresolved problems.
- The steering committee is not the place where problems are discovered, but where solutions are decided. This means that project-based organizations need to be set up before the steering committee meetings, which need to be prepared, typically according to the following cycle:
 - At the beginning of the six-month period, the organizations dedicated to implementing the actions decided at the previous steering committee must be designed.
 - One month before a steering committee meeting, the subjects to be dealt with should be specified, based on the provisional timetable, regulatory changes, difficulties encountered, or results obtained under the actions decided on.
- The steering committee presentations should be designed to help management make decisions:
 - Common topics should be grouped together and, as far as possible, a common thread should be found between the topics.
 - The presentations should be reviewed by the action leaders, at least the day before, to resolve any problems that can be dealt with without a management decision.
 - The Director takes note of and accepts the decisions taken and the action plan, which becomes a guideline for everyone.
- The CR is validated by everyone. Once finalized, it becomes a basic tool for coordination between the steering committees.

By establishing priorities

Depending on the kinetics and criticality of the risk

Not all problems have the same importance, because they do not affect the kinetics and criticality of hazardous phenomena in the same way. It is rational to adjust the allocation of the organization's resources according to these two parameters. This adjustment is based on analyses. The organization designs its specifications on the basis of risk analyses and their updates.

According to the organisation's capabilities

Another prioritization criterion relates to the difficulty for an organization to implement a task. There are several possible scenarios.

Case 1: The solution is known. This is the vast majority of cases. It must be deployed, even if it is difficult to implement, as in the case of:

- Some accident scenarios are so serious that there are still doubts about the means of controlling them, even though they have already been tried and tested, are known, controlled, and implemented by the organization.
- There is a need for standardization, because certain practices are not mastered across an entire site or across all sites.
- Problems that are well known and under control need to be dealt with quickly, as a matter of priority. We need to apply the principle of subsidiarity.

Case 2: the solution has not been fully studied, tested and validated. We need to take the time to explore one or more satisfactory solutions, using an experimental approach, and carry out additional analyses before making a decision, if necessary by the steering committee.

Case 3: the possible solutions involve uncontrolled practices. This is a completely different case. Using an experimental approach, the solutions will have to be classified and analyzed, then their design and implementation will have to be closely monitored, tested, and evaluated. This will result in investment programs to be decided by the steering committee.

According to steering capacity

It is not possible to discuss all the unresolved issues that fall within the remit of a COPIL at the same time. Prioritized issues are dealt with over time. Some problems can be dealt with over the course of several meetings, or even several years. There is therefore an agreed schedule for dealing with problems in the steering committee, and adjustments to this schedule. Everyone is aware of the schedule, which is communicated to the inspectorate and controlled by management. Rushing to deal with problems could lead to even bigger problems.

IT tools

The method involves constructing a demonstration of the control of major risks. This is based on steps involving the manipulation, articulation and re-articulation of knowledge: the data from the risk analysis is restructured around accident scenarios (events and barriers); these scenarios are redesigned so that the players in the field can position their critical tasks within them; the latter are described in terms of resources; the management of these resources is described by support, monitoring and audit processes; the whole process is dynamically controlled on the basis of evidence.

It seems virtually impossible to ensure the fluid management of all this knowledge and, above all, its links within a risk control demonstration without using a computer ontology (Bachimont B., 2007) and therefore a database. This is why the method is computerized (Aneziris O., 2019).

The software solution has been designed to enable several players to work together, each from their own point of view, on the same data and the same model. The solution is therefore not rigid software, with a set of pre-established screens, but an ultra-flexible development platform (Plot, 2022 & 2023), with screens tailored to each player (in a DevOps approach). First, the tool enables us to reach everyone where they are, by adapting to their needs and requirements, to the vision they have of their company, to the specificities linked to their history, their working environment, and so on. Then the tool offers new perspectives and opportunities. It then supports changes in practices, requirements, and visions, while ensuring the overall coherence of the organization. The heuristic is that of trial and error with all the players, around a methodology and a stable, robust digital structure (the only way to ensure overall consistency, manage changes and historical data, and guarantee permanent data control).

The solution offers:

- A common core, a deep methodological and IT layer, dedicated to the consistent management of risk analysis data, critical tasks, and processes,
- A set of resources for developing real-time workflows, data entry forms, data management screens, dashboards, and customized reporting systems, specifically tailored to the needs of each

organization. These developments re-use secure software components that have already been designed and tested, enabling rapid development by focusing solely on the needs of the business and avoiding the risk of bugs.

This IT system has been specifically designed for the implementation and management of risk management systems.

Conclusion

It is important to be wary of simplistic approaches that can be summed up by the following statements we sometimes hear from manufacturers: 'We have taken all environmental requirements into account in our procedures, we apply our procedures 100%, and if there is a problem, we trace it and solve it; so we are good; and moreover, we have never had a notable incident or accident'. The problems with this approach are as follows:

- Procedures are often incomplete, complex, and not always applied.
- Incidents or near-accidents are recurrent on the sites.
- This formulation is tantamount to asking the person who wants to check to redo all the work:
 - o list all the requirements arising from the operating license and risk studies,
 - o check that they have all been identified and considered in the doctrines and tasks that are important for the environment.
 - o check that they have been incorporated into operators' procedures, instructions, or operating methods.
 - o check that these tasks are carried out by competent personnel (trained and assessed)
 - o monitors their effectiveness using appropriate parameters.

This simplistic approach limits the scope for reflection on the real level of risk management within the organization. It means closing our eyes and not giving ourselves the means to check our own mistakes in designing our risk management system.

In contrast, the method presented in this document is specifically designed to organize the conditions for transparency which help to define the priority of actions thanks to a holistic demonstration of the effective level of risk of industrial installations and processes. The aim is to enable criticism, reflexivity, questioning and therefore improvement.

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Risk management in a complex multi risk unregulated environment

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Energy systems are one of the pillars of a civilization and their study for a better safer use is an absolute necessary activity. By Energy Systems we will understand complex systems including energy sources, transmission from one form to another, users, and their feedback to the system as a whole and the environment affected. Energy systems and the knowledge embedded in them were considered in such evaluation as being complex (CES) operating as cybernetic machines and supporting their own transformation from one state to another under clearly defined laws and rules [1]. A similar set of lessons resulted in the project phases with the conclusions from the existence and operation of natural energy system, as it was the case with the natural reactor Oklo [2].

As reported before in a research project on the risks in CES, started two decades ago in various environments and still ongoing [1-3;7-10] CES structure might be complex and diverse (with natural and artificial non intelligent and/or intelligent components). Modelling complex systems was performed as the existing approaches reflected in a large literature and the solutions proposed in [1-3] and were based on basic approaches from it [4-6].

The CES modelled have high uncertainties in their internal and external interactions and they need special approaches to risk definition and evaluation due also to their diverse structure, implying diverse type of challenges, which may induce diverse types of risks as in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Risk zones and types of risks in case of multi sources

Figure 2 illustrates sets of cases of single sources of risk (RS I) and for multiple sources of risk (RM I) which will require complex planning for emergency situations. Existing situation for CES demonstrated the need to move from considering static Emergency Planning (EP) by dynamic decision-making process to Dynamic EP both for single and multiple sources of risks.

Figure 2. Emergency planning development for single and multiple risks sources

A description of potential challenges and their impact to risk status for CES is in Table 1 for natural or man-made (normal and unforeseen cases) indicating the expected type of risk impact. Multiple challenges lead to high and even catastrophic risk situations, requiring complex dynamic planning for emergency situations. In the category of man-made a series of challenges due to diverse structures of CES (which may include artificial hardware, AI, biological ecological environments etc).

Table 1. Challenges to CES and their risk impact expert evaluation for one typical energy system [1]

Challenges L=low M=medium H= High H+ = increased high H++ = catastrophic	Expected singular type of risk impact			Expected multiple type of risk impact		
	SS_Design Basis	SS_Beyond Design Basis	SS_Catastrophic	MS_Design Basis	MS_Beyond Design Basis	MS_Catastrophic
Natural normal	L	M	H	L	M	H
Natural unforeseen	L	M	H	M	H	H+
Man made normal	L	M	H	L	M	H
Man made unforeseen	L	M	H	M	H	H++

For a CES the challenges lead to sets of expected singular/multiple type of risk. Their evaluation is considering their relevance from design point of view. The risks considered in sample calculated cases [9,10] were of the following types: SS / MS_Design Basis, Beyond Design Basis and Catastrophic Natural normal or unforeseen and Man made normal or unforeseen. The risk modelling in those cases uses innovative approaches with pragmatic solutions in high-risk unregulated environments [4,5]. CES in unregulated environments and with changing types of risk sources require description of multi risk types of emergency actions. Sample cases of such modelling from [7,8] were developed for multiple risk cases in [9,10].

In recent phases of the project to evaluate multiple risks for CES systems the goal was to identify specifics for situation when risks arise in CES operating in unregulated environments, as for instance in war type situation [9,10]. The description of the notion of risk for more advanced CES and how to manage it if the system has such a diverse structure and operates in unregulated environments is one of the challenges at the engineering phase of the future energy systems for our planetary and space developments. Risk management for CES of

diverse types (man-made, environmental alive or not, including intelligent beings having AI incorporated), operating as carrying single type of risk (for instance nuclear) or multiple (nuclear, fire, population extinction etc) with the approach mentioned before [1,3,7,8] are already a top issue of real (unfortunately) life in many places and reflected in recent cases [9,10]. For the EP in CES in abnormal environments (unregulated with multiple risks) the Emergency Plans (EP) types are dynamic and create dynamic Emergency Categories (EC), as illustrated in Figure 3 may be defined in four quadrants depending on their relationship with type of risks (single vs multiple – S/M) and if foreseen or unforeseen (F/UF).

During an emergency, the EPs may change and the ECs also. ECs for instance in quadrants I, II, III, IV result for the situations of different EP types (“i” for EP and “j” for EC type (EC i EP j))

Figure 3. EP and EC combinations for CES in multirisk situation

The risk evaluation generates states grouped in four categories (quadrants) in a plane defined by two axes: one of the types of risk sources (S/M) and the second of the type of challenge (F/UF). The results lead to combinations of ECs declared in a developed EPs. The combinations possible are as in Figure 3. The evaluation identified a dynamic change of EC to be declared depending on the variation of the conditions (from single to multiple sources and/or from foreseen to unforeseen challenges).

The results of the EP and EC evaluations, including the dynamic evolution of situation developed the basis for the decision-making process, which finally takes the mitigating actions for a complex, dynamic, and unregulated situation.

A supplementary uncertainty might be induced by the type of risk evaluation method used. For a regulated environment the basic assumption of the evaluations is that the criteria to judge applicability of a certain EP is based on a set of rules, i.e. CES operates in a regulated environment.

Table 3 includes the evaluation of the relevance performed using an approach of benchmarking different methods for risk evaluation, which were reported previously [8]. CES risks in emergency are evaluated for the Decision-Making Process (DMP) by using different methods like [8]:

- Precautionary principle
- Deliberative Principle
- Risk Informed Decision Making
- Aggregate method

The evaluation was performed for a real CES (nuclear power plant in war zone- complex system of diverse

structure with single and multiple challenges and risk sources in an unregulated environment), for a series of possible states in which it may be before EP is declared [9,10]: EP in CES in unregulated environment with multiple risks. The cases considered in the evaluation areas in Table 2.

Table 2. Risk evaluation methods and their use for the decision-making process

Case	Description of case
A	Risk integration rules for single sources of risk RS I and static EP
B	Risk integration rules for multiple sources of risk RM K and static EP
C	Risk integration rules for single sources of risk RS I and dynamic EP
Envelope of ABC	Risk integration rules for multiple sources of risk RM K and dynamic EP

Another level of complexity of such tasks is generated by the a type of evolution not complying with any predictable rules (called jazz type) of the situation in general and in some particular case, i.e. a chaotic, in many cases unregulated development in consistent manner and set to operate in various security challenges environments. The capability to have strategies as the emergency plans proposed in [9,10] for those questions is a key feature of the stable development of protection reached by EP. The risk evaluations for cases in Table 2 were performed by using the methods from Table 3. The detailed description and results on the use of those methods are extensively presented in [8].

Table 3. Risk evaluation methods and their use for the decision-making process

Components of the Decision-Making Process and their impact on the final decision (N= No impact; H=High; M=medium; MH= Medium to High; L=Low; VL=Very Low) as resulted by using different risk evaluation methods	Risk evaluation methods [8]			
	Precautionary principle	Deliberative Principle	Risk Informed Decision Making	Aggregate conclusion
A,B,C = Categories as per	PREC	DELIB	RIDM	AGGREG
Communication	H	H	N	MH
Structure's interface	H	H	H	H
Monitoring	L	L	N	L
Monitoring Coordination	L	VL	N	L
Results	N	M	M	M
Analysis (independent) available	N	MH	MH	MH
Highest overall impact for various cases	A	B	C	ABC

The cases A,B, C, ABC are as per the definition in Table 2.

The results indicate that the decision-making process for CES of[9,10] type has the highest certainty if diverse combined risk evaluation methods are used for any case.

Based on the EP evaluations a set of detailed principles to be included for a particular situation of a CES in unregulated environment, subject to multiple risks are derived and are further detailed on going work [9,10]. The actions to be taken for dynamic ECs are defined and the EPs must consider the CES operation in an unregulated environment.

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List of abbreviations

CES	Complex Energy System
EP	Emergency Planning
EC	Emergency Category
SS_Design Basis	Single Source of Risk due to Design Basis events
SS_Beyond Design Basis	Single Source of Risk due to Beyond Design Basis events
SS_Catastrophic	Single Source of Risk due to Catastrophic events
MS_Design Basis	Multiple Source of Risk due to Design Basis events
MS_Beyond Design Basis	Multiple Source of Risk due to Beyond Design Basis events
MS_Catastrophic	Multiple Source of Risk due to Catastrophic events
EC _i EP _j	“i” type of state evaluated for EP for a “j” type of EC
PREC	Precautionary principle

DELIB	Deliberative Principle
RIDM	Risk Informed Decision Making
AGGREG	Aggregate conclusion
DMP	Decision-Making Process
N	No impact on risk
H	High Risk
M	Medium Risk
MH	Medium to High Risk
L	Low Risk
VL	Very Low Risk
S/M	Single / multiple risk
F/UF	Foreseen or unforeseen risk
I,II,III,IV	Quadrants defining states of combinations for EP and EC combinations for CES in multi risk evaluations represented on the axes F/UF versus S/M

Knowledge creation for resilient cyber-socio-technical systems: framing recent research

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Abstract

The term cyber-socio-technical system (CSTC) has been introduced in recent research to emphasize the increasing pervasiveness of the cyber aspect in modern socio-technical systems, with more intelligence and autonomy. Critical infrastructures such as energy, water and transportation systems, as well as essential services like medical services, are examples of these systems. Digital innovation is creating opportunities to improve their resilience to external and internal stressors but also challenges, such as the increased complexity of the analysis due to various dependencies of system functions and changes in the organization of work. Following knowledge management theories, a novel approach leveraging the SECI model by Nonaka has allowed to identify knowledge flow patterns between various working agents (including cyber artifacts) of a CSTS and their influence in the system performance that may affect its resilience.

In this paper, we present a safety perspective of the SECI model that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC and use this model to classify research advancements on ICT technology to support such activities.

1. Introduction

Accidents prevention and resilience enhancement plans of an organization succeed from making the best use of its own risk/safety collective knowledge. However, building such a knowledge is challenged by the fact that risks are not all quantifiable, given the uncertainty on occurrence and impact of some events, which hinders evidence-based decision making. Qualitative risk assessment may help only to some extent, as it relies on experts' knowledge that is essentially tacit, contextual, experiential and distributed, hence difficult to communicate, combine and generalize [1].

Traditional risk assessment methods, which rely on predefined risk types and historical data, are increasingly insufficient to address the complexity of systems rapidly evolving due to technological advancements and environmental factors. "Cyber-socio-technical system" (CSTC) [2] refers to a socio-technical system in which the integration of cyber components is both significant and desirable, leading to increased intelligence and autonomy. Critical infrastructures, such as energy, water, and transportation systems, as well as essential services like healthcare, exemplify these systems. In these domains, digital innovation plays a crucial role in reducing disruptions, enhancing safety, and adapting to new challenges, such as those related to climate change. For instance, transportation networks are integrating automated systems to monitoring and optimize traffic flow, while mitigating risks of disruptions following extreme weather events. Similarly, energy grids are adopting smart technologies to enhance resilience against climate-induced challenges like heatwaves and storms [3]. These advancements aim to make infrastructures more adaptive and capable of facing current and future events for which they should adapt, for example, through self-reconfiguration mechanisms. This will allow them to withstand extreme events, reduce the need for human intervention in emergency situations, and make human work safer.

Knowledge elicitation and management to the aim of safety design, assessment and resilience improvement, are challenging activities in such settings, as these complex systems are characterized by non-linear interactions of the components, either human or cyber-physical, where even the identification of these dependencies may be a hard problem [4,5]. Indeed, since Industry 4.0, smart objects are capable of learning, adapting and acting in the environment by mimic human decision-making and therefore they also have a role in knowledge-based interactions towards co-creation of the safety culture. Moreover, it is well known that the functions and interdependencies in a system can be influenced by the knowledge of processes and the way this knowledge is utilized by agents who have a role in the work (including cyber agents). Misalignments among work

representations by agents may indicate organizational stress that hinders its resilience, as discussed in [6]. While the difference of work-as-imagine with work-as-done has been the focus of most safety science research, the widespread usage of Large Language Model (LLM) chatbots in all kinds of work environments has led to the definition of work-as-large language model (WALL) to characterize their influence in the process [7].

In the initial study of the above-mentioned research [2], a novel approach leveraging the SECI model by Nonaka has allowed to characterize knowledge flow patterns between the various agents of a CSTS and their influence in the system performance, leading to the conceptual framework Work-as-x (WAX). The support of ICT technology to overcome some of the problems in such flows is also interesting to enhance that analysis. In this paper, we present a safety perspective of the SECI model, i.e., the SECI-S model, that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC, and we use this model to classify recent research advancements on ICT technology to support such activities.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the concept of safety knowledge. Section 3 illustrates the SECI-S (safety-oriented SECI) model, and Section 4 presents and classifies recent research on ICT for safety knowledge.

2. Safety knowledge

As a preliminary step before discussing the SECI-S classification model, it is essential to clarify that the difference of Knowledge and Information is not uniquely understood in general, although these words usually denote different concepts when referring to practical implementations of digital systems. Indeed, knowledge-based systems incorporate artificial intelligence techniques to organize data in formal (logical) structures that enable some automatic reasoning and learning capability. Conventional information systems usually focus on management of numerical and/or textual data.

Following the description in [8], we adopted the following meaning:

- Information is processed data in context. Information is a collection of data and associated textual material describing a particular object, event, or process.
- Knowledge is information that is organized, conceptualized, linked with pre-existing knowledge and synthesized to enhance comprehension, awareness, or understanding to enable decision making also in similar contexts.

This distinction is in line with the Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) pyramid [9, 10] where sensors, including human perception, are data collectors from reality, and intelligence is defined as actionable knowledge of an organization.

Knowledge is built from Information to handle how questions, e.g., “How” is this information relevant? “How” can we apply the information? Thus, safety information (e.g., an accident report), may differentiate from safety knowledge (e.g., risk awareness) as a result of a cognitive process, which allows filtering of data/information/knowledge towards intelligence for specific decision objectives. Furthermore, social networks contribute to transfer it among different users (individuals or communities). Such a process involves insight and analysis, and it is bi-directional as from the specification of (new) decision objectives, the type of intelligence, knowledge, information and/or the data to be acquired should be identified.

3. Knowledge creation for CSTS resilience

Knowledge creation encompasses something previously unknown by an analyst or a manager, or not thought of (e.g., building knowledge on a new type of emergency), and/or enrichment and evolution of descriptions of safety knowledge, e.g., procedures for risk mitigation after an accident. Furthermore, this process is influenced by the communication/sharing between workers at different levels of the same process (i.e. top managers or blunt-end vs operators or sharp-end and machines), as well as between safety authorities/analysts and operators [2]. This is especially true in the new digitalized setting, where organizations rely on proper functioning of autonomous systems also in safety-critical services such as transportation and emergency management. Thus, the communication pattern in Figure 1 describing the knowledge flow in an organization at the highest level of abstraction, with the roles involved in safety analysis processes, should be instantiated with human and/or cyber components.

Figure 1: Knowledge flow pattern among three categories of agents of an organization

It should be noted that these roles do not correspond to the official jobs in an organization but they are used to distinguish among: who decides what should be done by the process or activity but he/she does not take part in it (blunt-end), who directly executes a process activity (sharp-end) and who analyses a process (can be internal or external to the organization and he/she does not work directly on the process objective). These roles apply to individuals who look at the same process from different perspectives and they are not static but relative to the communication pattern under analysis.

3.1. SECI-S model

Risk information communication in an organization may be examined following knowledge management theories, such as the SECI model by Nonaka [1]. The model represents knowledge creation and sharing as iterations of tacit and explicit knowledge conversions within a single or between different individuals of the organization.

Each iteration distinguishes four types of interactions: socialization, externalization, combination and internalization. Socialization represents the transfer of tacit knowledge between individuals through observation and practice. Externalization means translating tacit knowledge into documents and procedures. Combination allows to reconfigure explicit knowledge through combining and/or categorizing, and, lastly, internalization is an individual process to translate explicit into tacit knowledge for acting. This model is depicted in Figure 2, which displays a SECI model instantiation to risk knowledge creation and sharing. The activities may involve one or more types of agents of Figure 1.

Figure 2: SECI model and activities for safety knowledge building (SECI-S)

When referring to safety knowledge in an organization, these activities are described as follows.

- **Socialization.** This refers to tacit knowledge acquisition by a single individual, when observing others, or interacting with them within a task. Examples of the last include emergency crew operations, squadron flights, operating rooms, etc. In modern teams of human and AI agents [11], teammates may achieve better coordination due to the prediction capability. Thus, safety should consider the fundamental shift from traditional human-machine interactions to processes in which humans and machines share tasks both manually and mentally.

Socialization activities refer to both normal (Safety-II by Hollnagel et al. [12]) and emergency cases. In normal situations, socialization encompasses, for example, direct observation of an analyst on execution of procedures in an organization. In the case of emergencies, blunt-end or sharp-end operators may act by adapting and/or taking initiative to the specific situations, which leads to defining new rules and behavior for safety in the future.

- **Externalization.** This refers to knowledge representation into safety information, such as: accident enquiries/reporting based on experience; risk imagination foresight activities [13]; any type of communication/disclosure about safety at all levels, e.g., how safety normative and procedures are understood and/or indirect indicators of risk awareness and adaptive capacity [14]. Furthermore, debriefing after simulated or real events is a powerful tool to externalize the knowledge of sharp end operators [15].

In the digitalized industry, new types of uncertainties are being dealt with. Discussions should involve a variety of stakeholders regarding the opportunities and risks posed by new technologies and innovations [5].

- **Combination.** This refers to integration of the information and models to deliver safety knowledge or to identify risks. In the case of complex socio-technical systems, such integration is not an easy task and might not even be feasible. Perspectives such as technology, software, humans, organizations, safety culture all have a role in accidents prevention studies, and they should not be treated separately [4]. Combining subsystems into a system introduces new paths to hazards that are not apparent when viewing the parts

separately. Intercepting these interactions into analysis models is the challenge of application, by an analyst, of systemic approaches for safety analysis such as STAMP (Systems-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes) defined by Leveson, and FRAM (Functional Resonance Analysis Method) by Hollnagel.

In the modern digital era, three information types are interlinked [16]: Human information (static: role, qualification, experience and dynamic: health, motion, fatigue); Machine information (state information and warnings); Environment information (ambient conditions, resources and workload).

- **Internalization.** These activities refer to introspective cognitive processes for learning (e.g., procedures, from accident reports), adaptation and decision making (e.g., based on acquired information), and identifying opportunities for systems improvement. This is certainly a relevant concern for risk management whose success highly relies on the availability and quality of the information, and of methods for collection and/or automatic interpretation of the information [17].

Multi-perspective knowledge acquisition and combination to the aim of design for safety/resilience or situational awareness is a demanding job and completeness may be unfeasible in a complex system. ICT technology is facilitating in various of the described tasks. The following section presents ICT-based methods and tools usable to lighten obstacles and difficulties to a smooth implementation of the SECI-S model.

3.2. SECI-S model instantiation

A partial account of types of ICT support is provided in Figure 3. A complete state of the art of the methods/tools for the safety knowledge creation process would certainly be of benefit for organizations interested in research/mature technologies that can be used. In this short paper, we limit our analysis to examples retrieved from the recent scientific research literature.

ICT for socialization. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge acquisition, namely, observation/perception, collaboration and experience with others, where these others may be human and/or virtual agents.

Empowering information from field by an agent is one purpose, that refers to how work is organized (blunt-end perspective), how tasks are performed (sharp-end perspective) and who is performing them (human or machine). Intelligent surveillance systems support better monitor safety in the workplace, identify risks and provide feedback to improve safety procedures [18]. On the other hand, process mining [19] can be a tool for indirect observation. This comprises data science methods and software to gain insights on the process from the analysis of traces (i.e., digital representations of observed behavior). A large body of scientific works in this area describe methods and results to support automatic process comprehension (i.e., WAD representations), conformance checking (i.e., WAI vs WAD representation) and predictive monitoring (i.e., predicting a violation or a critical event before it occurs to support organizations in mitigating its effect) [20].

Healthy Operator 4.0 [21] refers to operators using smart wearable solutions (i.e. wearable trackers for health-related metrics) connected with data analytics software to face potential physical risks (psycho-social health) brought by the new context of Industry 4.0 technologies (e.g. autonomous and collaborative robots, augmented reality and virtual reality, artificial intelligence, IoT etc.). Of course, as a drawback, diminished privacy and increased pressure to prioritize performance must be considered [22].

Strengthen/changing collaboration is another purpose. Virtualization of work has increased in the last years allowing work processes to be decentralized by using geographically dispersed workforce, and flexible working organization [23].

SOCIALIZATION	EXTERNALIZATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet of Things (IoT) • (Predictive) automatic monitoring • Augmented/Virtual reality • Autonomous system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serious games • Social networks • Explainable AI • Computational creativity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E-Learning • Simulation and Training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Intelligence (BI) • Risk ontologies/knowledge graphs • Crowdsourcing • Machine Learning (ML) methods • Events database

Figure 3: IT methods and tools to support risk knowledge creation and sharing

Opportunity for safety (e.g., better control) and negative implications of this change (e.g., harm due to increase of temporary jobs; challenges for managing risks in industries with workforce located in countries with different legislations) should be carefully analysed in this new context. Health and safety collaborative apps, virtual and augmented reality are among new opportunities to safety knowledge creation.

ICT for externalization. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge made explicit through communication and reporting.

New communication tools. Social media allow fast exchanging user-generated content as in the face-to-face speech. As for other types of communication tools for safety-related communication, in a production process, obstacles from the sharp-end may include fear and lack of motivation. Digital gamification can be a viable means to engage workers in safety-relevant knowledge acquisition processes [17]. Social media interconnection with the cyber-physical space of the organization (e.g., human and machine chat-bot communication enforced by generative AI) is another proposal [24] to improve the links between the persons working in the production environment, the manufacturing machines, and the knowledge that is created in the process [7].

Support to safety imagination foresight. Risk foresight in accident prevention methods for safety-critical systems is finalized to the identification of new emergency scenarios. Traditional methods for risk assessment are based on risk types and data on past events, while knowledge of unprecedented hazards, but potentially dangerous for systems and people, is partially solved by machine learning solutions. However, these could be limited by the context variability, the lack of training data, and the lack of explainable arguments for the predictions they make. Scenario imagination by safety managers can be cumbersome and requires both knowledge of the processes (WAD) and creativity. Proactive tools for knowledge elicitation can be built following computational creativity methods [25]. According to these methods, which can be automatized, a new scenario can arise by combination and/or analogy with known facts.

ICT for combination. This encompasses technology to support activities finalized to safety knowledge building based on an integrated processing of documents and/or event data related to risk and safety.

Knowledge representation tools. Ontologies and knowledge graphs enable logical representation of knowledge, in the form of graphs with nodes as entities and links as semantic relations (logical propositions) between entities. These tools allow multi-domain/multi-perspective data/information integration under a semantic

structure and enable automatic reasoning to build knowledge-based systems [6]. For example, ontologies to support risk and/or safety data/document harmonization and synthesis are being considered to support systemic studies for resilience of electricity networks [26] given their interdependencies with other infrastructures to manage environmental stressors and cascading effects [27]. A knowledge graph organizing information from large set of safety reports to support safety monitoring and instructing safety interventions is described in [28, 29].

Data analytics/Business intelligence. The potential and effectiveness of modern business intelligence methods is intensely considered in research. These tools are promoted for knowledge democratization of resilience in safety-critical systems [30]. In such areas, the concept of safety intelligence has been introduced referring to the aim to transform raw data and information from incident archives into meaningful information for safety management by means of machine learning methods, which can be visualized in a compact way for decision support [31].

ICT for internalization. This encompasses technology to support cognitive activities in learning/acquisition of skills and competences safety relevant.

Education and training. The benefit of virtual environments for serious gaming supplied through apps and/or virtual and augmented reality to increase safety culture in organizations is described in various scientific papers [32, 33].

Safety assurance of AI. Complex is the problem of training of artificial intelligence agents taking care of data completeness, trust and ethics aspects. This open research problem interlinks (technical) safety assurance methods of automatic systems with resilience engineering techniques and human factors [34].

4. Conclusion

Building and use of risk/safety knowledge for resilience enhancement is a continuous process whose challenges of knowledge reliability, distribution and generalizability could be improved using ICT technology. Various examples of applications and corresponding benefit in each phase of such a process have been provided by the research community.

This article presents a classification of ICT techniques that support the process of safety knowledge creation within an organization. This classification is derived from a state-of-the-art review guided by the SECI-S model, a safety perspective of the SECI model that highlights the activities for safety/risk knowledge creation and sharing in a CSTC. However, the readiness level of the proposed technology, as well as the acceptance and practicability of research approaches in the real world in the short term remain to be clarified. Additionally, the potential changes and new risks introduced by these technologies should be addressed by safety-critical industries and regulators.

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Risk-based Customs' Intrusive Inspection Decision Making: Algorithm & Preliminary Case study

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Abstract

This work is carried on within the frame of the EU Horizon project “BAG-INTEL”. The BAG-INTEL project final target is to develop a Risk-based AI tool to support customs intrusive inspection decision making relative to luggage control in airports. The risk assessment component is the only component of the BAG-INTEL Tool that is presented in the paper. The risk assessment component is one of many other components to be developed in BAG-INTEL Tool. It is powered by an algorithm mixes probabilistic statistics (deductive approach) and Analytic Hierarchic Process (AHP) classification theory (inductive approach). Subsequently, the risk assessment algorithm does not exploit any AI methodology or facility. The exploited data are exclusively numerical figures. Hence, the risk assessment algorithm does neither retrieve nor process any personal or biometric data by its concept.

Two risks are identified and assessed. The first is to miss a bag containing illegal substances (detection failure). The second is to intrusively inspect a clean bag (false detection). We consider three individual risk indicators to estimate the likelihood of illegal substances in a bag: external-intelligence informative risk indicator, sniffer dog risk indicator, and X-scan risk indicator. The list of searched illegal substances of interest is purposely limited to narcotics, tabaco, currency notes, gold, and polymers. The individual risk indicators should be aggregated to determine one global risk indicators by the risk assessment algorithm presented in the paper.

The mathematical models used are briefly presented and applied using academic data simulating the three risk indicators cited above. The paper presents the state of progress in the development of the risk assessment algorithm and the results of its preliminary numerical testing.

The paper is intended to be didactic and accessible to Customs Inspection Decision Making professionals as far as the the probabilistic risk assessment concept and the related algorithm are concerned.

1. Introduction

This work is carried on within the frame of the EU Horizon project “BAG-INTEL”. The BAG-INTEL project’s final target is to develop a Risk-based AI Tool (RBIT) to support customs decision making relative to luggage intrusive inspection in airports. The Risk-Assessment Algorithm (RAA) is developed and is in the pre-testing phase. It is one of the BAG-INTEL Tool’s components. It is not an AI algorithm and does neither exploit nor process any personal or biometric data. It exploits exclusively numerical data and is based on classical probabilistic and statistic risk assessment approaches.

The paper focuses on the algorithm and the implemented mathematical models that process the data concerning the identified risks. The different features of the risk assessment methodology are illustrated and presented through an academic case study. The case study exploits customs inspection experience feedback data and practices. But the individual risk indicators data used are simulated ones as explained later. The simulated data are the external-intelligence informative risk indicator, sniffer dog risk indicator, the X-scan risk indicator, and the bag camera identification and re-identification matching indicator.

The algorithmic concept presented in the paper is based on an upgraded methodology combining applied statistics’ techniques, probability theory, and Analytical Hierarchical Processing method (AHP). The combination of these techniques was not indeed a free choice of the authors. It was rather a practical processing necessity as the used data are of different categories: probabilistic expectations, objective statistical observations, and customs’ inspection cumulated subjective numerical scoring.

The concerned risks in the case study are:

- The risk of “false detection, FD”; when customs’ officers decide to intrusively inspect a bag and find no illegal substances. This action is wasting time and consuming resources with no-profit outcome.
- The risk of a “detection failure, DF”; when customs’ officers decide not to inspect a bag containing illegal substances because nothing is detected. This is a potential tax loss and a breach in crime fighting efforts.

Obviously, one should minimise the above risks exposure in bags inspection practices. This should be carried on using a “risk-based inspection decision making” process as recommended by the World Customs Organisation (WCO) guides and the EU directives and strategic progress monitoring reports regularly addressed to the EU decision makers & parliament.

The method used in the realisation of this task of the BAG-INTEL project is presented in section 2, below.

2. Why and How - The Method

The authors have, first, to identify why the EU and the international “concerned” community emphasis on introducing risk assessment in luggage inspection decision making process. A brief screening of the EU and International context of customs practices is presented in section 3. This is necessary to identify exactly the kind of risks to be included in the risk assessment.

In section 4, the authors specify the risks that should be assessed within the context of the “luggage intrusive inspection” by customs, in airports. Once the risks are fully specified, the authors should look at the identification of the required relevant data issues, their availability and their accessibility.

In section 5, the required data, data sources, their availability and their accessibility are identified. A brief presentation is then given. The identification of the risk assessment inputs and outcomes is also carried on. They are specified in the form of individual risk indicators and a global risk indicator to be determined, respectively. The input data and the outcome of the risk assessment are all numerical data. No meta-data, personal data or biometric data are involved in the risk assessment data processing.

Section 6 treats the “Inspection Experience Feedback” as perceived by the customs partners participating in the BAG-INTEL project. The “Customs’ Inspection Experience feedback” data is formulated by an effectiveness rate of the intrusive inspections and a trustworthiness level that customs allocate to each individual risk indicator. The trustworthiness score goes from 1 to 10, where 10 is the highest trustworthiness level. This dataset allows to weight the relative effectiveness of the individual risk indicators.

Section 7 gives details on the individual risk indicators and their aggregation in a global risk indicator. It treats the relative weighting of each individual risk indicator as their contributions are not equal. The weighting factors are deduced thanks to the “Inspection Experience Feedback” data detailed above in section 6.

Section 8 presents the aggregation algorithm of the weighted individual risk indicators to determine the global risk indicator. This is the main subject of the paper, the algorithm concept, its numerical input data, and its numerical outputs. After the numerical validation of the algorithm, it is supposed to be implemented in the BAG- INTEL Decision-Making Support Tool that is build-up of many other modular algorithms and components. The risk assessment algorithm discussed in the paper is not an AI-algorithm.

An academic case study is detailed in section 9. It should validate the principal of the algorithm that aggregates the individual risk indicators, considering their individual weights based on customs’ inspection experience feedback. The input individual indicators should be provided by other algorithms and components external to the BAG-INTEL Tool. These are: External & Intelligence Risk Indicator, Sniffer Dog Risk Indicator, X-scan Data Risk Indicator, Camera Identification/Re-identification Risk Indicator. The numerical validation of the Risk Assessment Algorithm is then carried on using simulated individual risk indicators. For the purpose the academic case, the risk indicators have been simulated.

Section 10 presents the conclusions of the case study relative to the numerical validation of the Risk Assessment Algorithm.

3. EU and International Context

The WCO recommends that intrusive customs inspections should be limited. A Risk Management Guide has been developed by the WCO, (WCO, 2003). The WCO defines risk management as “the systematic determination of risk management priorities by evaluating and comparing the level of risk against predetermined standards, target risk-levels or other criteria”, as quoted in the WCO (2003b) guide.

In line with WCO recommendations, the European Commission released a Communication on the EU Strategy and Action Plan for customs risk management titled ‘Tackling risks, strengthening supply chain security and facilitating trade, on 21 August 2014 (COM-2014 527 final [2] and COM-2014 527 final-Annexe-1 [3]). In this founding communication, EU defines its strategic targets and the related action plan as following (citing):

- Improve data quality and filing arrangements
- Ensure availability of supply chain data and sharing of risk relevant information among customs authorities
- Implement control and risk mitigation measures where required
- Strengthen capacities
- Promote interagency cooperation and information-sharing between customs and other authorities at the Member State and EU level
- Enhance cooperation with trade
- Tap the potential of international customs co-operation

A detailed EU action plan is given in (COM – 2014 527 final-Annexe1) mentioned above. Three monitoring progress reports on “the Implementation of the EU Strategy and Action Plan for Customs Risk Management” have been published regarding the COM – 2014 527, in 2016 (1st Prog Rep, 2016), 2018 (2nd Prog Rep, 2016), and 2021 (3rd Prog Rep, 2016). The EU Court of Auditors has conducted an interesting special audit and published a report (Special Report, 2021) entitled “Customs controls: insufficient harmonisation hampers EU financial interests” that focused only on the Financial Risk Criteria (FRC). Still, it sheds an intensive light on the fact that both interconnected customs’ missions, financial and law enforcement, should follow risk based decision making process.

4. Risks Identification

As mentioned briefly above, the BAG-INTEL project (HORIZON-RIA, 2023) focuses on the risks that hamper the “Inspection Process Efficiency”, in EU-airports.

The risk inspection process may be hampered, Figure 1, by:

- Either the “detection failure” of illegal substances (DF – detection failure),
- Or the “false detection” of illegal substances (FD – false detection)

Both “detection failure” and “false detections” risks contribute to lowering the performance of the Customs’ Control Process. Both risks should be managed taking advantage of the advanced non-intrusive detection technologies.

Figure 1 presents schematically the four possible scenarios, regarding a bag that went through a detection system:

FC: Free of illegal substances and detection confirms

FD: Free of illegal substances but false detection

occurs DF: Illegal substance exists but detection system fails

DC: Illegal substance exists, and detection system confirms

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of risks

5. Data Identification

Data retrieval relative to illegal trafficking is a complex process that depends on two different types of data retrieval mean: soft and hard ones. Soft data-retrieval covers the use of all relevant data and knowledge assets regarding the concerned illegal activities. Most of these assets are government-owned, private and with no public-access. The hard means cover all relevant remote sensing and scanning engineering technologies. Both require the use of a wide spectrum of data collection, processing, and aggregation advanced technologies.

Within BAG-INTEL project's perspective, the relevant knowledge & data sources are supposed to include:

Potential external sources of risk data

1. Flight data (itinerary, ticket, airline, payment)
2. Pax data (records, personal data, luggage)
3. LEAs data bases (INTERPOL, EUROPOL, SIS II)
4. Risk information forms – RIF (Within the frame of CRMS2)
5. World Customs Organisation (WCO) annual Illicit Trade Intelligence Report

Internal sources of risk data (to store the numerical outputs of the Risk Assessment Algorithm)

6. Customs inspection experience feedback database

Remote sensing equipment and scanning technologies:

7. Sniffer dog
8. X-scan imaging
9. Camera bag-identification (at the entrance of the X-scanner)
10. Camera bag-reidentification (in the customs control zone)

Each of the above ten sources of knowledge & data contributes to the evaluation of the global risk level. Each contribution is determined by an appropriate Individual Risk Indicator (IRI). A Global Risk Indicator (GRI) should be determined by the aggregation of the IRI's, mentioned above.

Knowledge & data sources N°1 to N°5 should be aggregated together to produce only one IRI. It is called external- intelligence risk indicator (I_e). Given the purpose of the case study, the value of the external intelligence risk indicator (I_e) will be simulated. The risk assessment algorithm is not conceived to process the data contents in the databases from N°1 to N°5.

The X-scan risk indicator (I_x), the camera identification indicator (I_{c1}) and the camera reidentification indicators (I_{c2}) are directly determined by the algorithms of the scanning machine and the cameras and supplied to the risk assessment algorithm.

While, The Global Risk Indicator "GRI" (I_G) will be determined by the aggregation of the external intelligence risk indicator (I_e), the sniffer dog (I), the X-scan (I_x), the camera identification indicator (I_{c1}) and the camera reidentification indicators (I_{c2}). The BAG-INTEL data flow diagram is schematically presented in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Schematic presentation of BAG-INTEL Data Flow

source reference: (HORIZON-RIA, 2023)

The unique function of the risk assessment algorithm is the aggregation of all individual risk indicators to determine the Global Risk Indicator (I_G).

Still to specify the “Customs inspection experience feedback knowledge”. Such database does not exist (yet) amongst the LEA’s databases assets or in the relevant literature, as far as the authors can tell. A local “Customs inspection experience feedback knowledge” data base is built up. It exploits the local inspection experience feedback of the BAG-INTEL customs’ partners, as described in the following section.

6. Inspection Experience Feedback

Why is the “Customs inspection experience feedback knowledge” important?

To get a representative overview about the trustworthiness level that customs officers give to the individual risk indicators as function of the searched contraband and vis-versa, a questionnaire has been developed and send to the customs organisation that participate in BAG-INTEL project consortium.

The 1st part of the questionnaire, Table 1, has permitted to estimate the success rate in intercepting contrabands in two configurations: 1) risk assessment-based inspection and 2) random or behaviour-based inspection.

Table 1: Questionnaire – 1st part

Give, roughly, the total number of the inspections you carried on over a defined time-interval* T : ----- * A time-interval that represents roughly your operational experience in luggage inspection activities.			
What is the interval T (in Years) you are considering?			
$0 < T \ll 1$	<input type="checkbox"/>	less than or equal to 1 year	
$1 < T \ll 5$	<input type="checkbox"/>	longer than 1 year but less than or equal to 5 years	
$5 < T \ll 10$	<input type="checkbox"/>	longer than 5 years but less than or equal to 10 years	
$10 < T$	<input type="checkbox"/>	longer than 10 years	
Considering the total number of inspections mentioned above, what are the ratio (%) of:			
The risk-based inspections-----		%	
The behaviour-based inspections (if you have a “Behaviour Detection Programme”)-----		%	
The random-based inspections (if you have a Random Inspection Protocol) -----		%	
Considering the inspection categories mentioned above, give the ratios (%) of full success¹, partial success² and unsuccess³ per each inspection category in Table 1, below:			
Table 1: Ratios (%) of full success ¹ , partial success ² and unsuccess ³ per each inspection category			
Inspections Category	Full Success ¹	Partial Success ²	Unsuccess ³
Considering only the “Risk-Based Inspection”%%%
Considering only the “Behaviour-Based Inspection”%%%
Considering only the “Random-Based Inspections” ⁴%	0%%
¹ The expected contraband is found. ² A contraband is found but not the expected one. ³ No contraband is found. ⁴ In random-based inspection “partial” successes has no sense, as no specific contraband is expected. You have only 2 options: “full success” if “a contraband” is found or “unsuccess” if no contraband is found.			

The 2nd part of the questionnaire, Table 2, has been developed and proposed to all BAG-INTEL customs partners. The customs partners were asked to score twice, from 0 to 10 using Table 1, according to two different point of views.

From point of view – 1, the customs officer scores column-by-column (i.e. per illegal substance) the relative trustworthiness level given per type of risk data source, according to his/her cumulated inspection experience.

From point of view – 2, the customs officer scores line-by-line (i.e. per risk data source) the relative trustworthiness level given per type of illegal substance, according to his/her cumulated inspection experience.

The list of searched illegal substances was purposely limited to narcotics, tabaco, currencies, gold and polymers. The extension of the searched illegal substances is straightforward if a wider spectrum of illegal substances is required. No limitations are imposed by the risk assessment algorithm on the number of the illegal substances.

The metrics used to score the Customs’ trustworthiness level in risk data sources as function of illegal substance varies from 0 to 10. The transfer grid between different scaling systems: discrete figures (0 to 10), and continuous probabilistic figures, is indicated in table 2 below.

Table 2: Questionnaire 2nd part – Trustworthiness level – Risk Data Sources v.s. Detected Illegal substances

Risk Data Sources	Narcotics	Tabacos	Currency	Gold	Polymers
Intelligence & Knowledge Databases					
Dog detection capability					
X-scanning					
Luggage photo identification					
Luggage photo re-identification indicator					

Table 2: Equivalence grid of different scoring scales

	Score ¹	Qualitative scale	Probability scale	
1	0-2	Very Low	0 – 20%	
2	3-4	Low	20 – 40%	
3	5	Medium	40 – 60%	
4	6-7	High	60 – 80%	
5	8-10	Very High	80 – 100%	

¹is used for scoring in the tables when collecting the customs inspection experience feedback

Processing the trustworthiness levels according to the operational inspection experience of the customs officers will provide the relative weighting figures of the individual risk indicators. The relative weighting figures are necessary for a meaningful aggregation of different individual risk indicator to produce the global Risk indicator.

The customs inspection experience feedback local database is still in construction. BAG-INTEL has collected (up to date) some 60 answer sheets cumulating more than 500000 inspection acts. The final statistical processing of all the collected data is expected by July-August 2025.

All the collected data are exclusively numerical. Neither personal nor biometric data are collected.

7. Risk Indicators Weighing Process

The statistical weighting process is a statistical direct application on the trustworthiness scoring of each customs officer. Thanks to the scoring of each customs officer, we could determine mean values representing the trustworthiness of the whole sample of the questioned customs officers. The methodology used here is fully based on the probability theory with a partial use of the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP).

The AHP is a general theory of measurement. It determines relative classification scales using both discrete and continuous paired comparisons. It is widely used in multicriteria decision making and in conflict resolution. It is generally a nonlinear framework for carrying out both deductive and inductive investigations on observable experience feedback to estimate the expectation of new outcomes belonging to the same experience type.

The AHP was developed by T. L. Saaty in 1971- 1975 (Wharton School – University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia), (T.L. Saaty, 1987). Besides, one may recommend other two papers (Pereyra -Rojas, M., 2017), and (L. Hammadi et al., 2016)) written in a didactic manner.

8. Individual Risk Indicators and Aggregation Algorithm

The individual risk indicators are aggregated in two steps.

Firstly, an independent and separate aggregation according to their technical nature to reduce them to 5 indicators: external- intelligence indicator (I_e), sniffer dog indicator (I_d), X-scan indicator (I_x), camera identification (I_c), and the inspection experience feedback indicator (I_o), opposite Figure 3.

Secondly, the final aggregation of the above 5 indicators into one Global Risk Indicator (I_G), carried on by the Risk Assessment Algorithm implemented in the BAG-INTEL Decision Support Tool.

It is worth, at that stage, to note that the inspection experience feedback indicator (I_o) is a set of sub-indicators worked out based exclusively on the growing customs inspection experience feedback. It is the only dynamic indicator in the risk assessment tool. It allows the tool to learn more after each inspection act.

Figure 3: Schematic presentation of risk indicators

8.1. Indicators Aggregation Algorithm

The Risk Assessment Algorithm flowchart is illustrated in the following, Table 4.

Table 4: Risk Assessment Algorithm Procedure

1. Risk Assessment Tool Activation on plan arrival
2. Retrieve External Data (I_e) and Target Risk Threshold (I_s)
3. Determine the relative weights (w_j^e, w_j, w_j^x, w_j^c) of all individual risk indicators (I_j^e, I_j, I_j^x, I_j^c)
4. Retrieve Dog and X-scan risk indicators (I_d, I_x)
5. Retrieve Camera Identification mismatching risk indicators (I_{c1})
6. Retrieve Camera Reidentification mismatching risk indicator (I_{c2}), if $I_{c2} = 1$, report "**Bag Lost**"
7. Determine Camera Identification and Reidentification Risk Indicator $I_c = 1 - w_c(1 - I_{c1}) \times (1 - I_{c2})$
8. Determine Weighted Risk indicators ($w_j^e I_e, w_j I, w_j^x I_x, w_j^c I_c$)
9. Determine the Global Risk Level (I_G) as:

$$I_G = [1 - (1 - w_j^e I_e)(1 - w_j I)](1 - w_j^x I_x)$$
10. Compare I_G and I_s , if $I_G \geq I_s$ recommend "Intrusive Inspection", if not "No recommendation"
11. Transmit comparison results and Cameras mismatching Risk Indicators to the "Customs Central" unit.
12. Check bags flow in, if that was the last bag GOTO #14 STEP, otherwise "Continue"
13. If any update occurred in the Ext Knowledge Risk Indicator, the Inspection Feedback weighting score, or the Threshold Risk Level then GOTO #2 otherwise to initialise all individual risk indicators inputs (I, I_x, I_c), GOTO #4
14. Sleep until next flight.

9. Calculations – Models & Preliminary Results

We recall that the Customs Inspection Feedback Experience database is still under construction. The preliminary results presented in the paper are not exhaustive, yet. Only less than half of the Customs Inspection feedback data (212350 inspections), section 6 (Annexe 1).

9.1. General Statistical Findings

The preliminary statistical assessment shows that the inspection decision making based on risk assessment and on behaviour assessment are almost of the same order, slightly higher in the case of behaviour assessment. That may be interpreted by the tendency of customs officers to classify random inspections under the category of “behaviour-based inspection”, if there is not an official “random inspection protocol” applied in their site, Figure 4(a).

Regarding risk-based inspection cases, Figure 4(b), 44% of the inspections are unsuccessful (no illegal substances are found) and 56% are either fully successful (35%) (the expected illegal substances are found) or partially successful (21%) (illegal substances are found but not the expected ones). It is almost the same data breakout in behaviour-based inspection, Figure 4(c), 43% are unsuccessful inspections, and 57% are either fully (30%) or partially (27%) successful.

It is worth noting that risk-based assessment boosts the full-successful inspections share by 6 points comparing to the partial-successful inspections. That is most likely due to its capacity to provide a better expectation of the illegal substances.

Figure 4: Preliminary statistical assessment of customs inspection experience feedback (212350 inspections)

(RIS: risk-based BEH: behaviour-based RAN: random-based)

Accordingly, we may make this statement “the state-of-the-art in risk-based inspection decision making proves that risk assessment enhances the expectation of illegal substances by 67%, [$\frac{35\%}{21\%} - 1 = 67\%$]. Then, any future progress due to the use of advanced risk-based inspection decision making should show a performance in the expectation of the illegal substances higher than 67%”.

But it is still astonishing that risk-based and behaviour-based inspections give similar unsuccessful inspection ratio. The authors hope that by the end of the full investigations this point could be explained.

9.2. Determination of the Weighting scores

Beside the general statistical remarks above, the second important output of the Customs Inspections Experience Feedback database is to assess the Individual Risk Indicators Weighting factors that will permit the determination of a Global Risk Indicator. The Customs Inspections Experience Feedback data contains two independent data categories.

The 1st category is the feedback of thousands of inspections scoring the trustworthiness level of customs in different data sources regarding separately each type of illegal substance, ex. table 4-1. Then, the relative scoring is done line by line (data source) in each column (illegal substance).

The 2nd category is the feedback of thousands of inspections scoring the trustworthiness level of customs in data concerning each type of illegal substance regarding separately different data sources, ex. table 4-22. Then, the relative scoring is done column by column (illegal substance) in each line (data source).

Tables 4-1 and 4-2, contain the average scores over 212350 inspections. These data are issued by subjective scoring done by customs inspectors. The numerical figures express subjective relative classification by column in Table 4-1 and by row in Table 4-2.

Table 4-1: Mean relative trustworthiness in Individual Risk Indicators (i) per illegal substance (j), (δ_{ij})

Individual Risk Indicators	Narcotics	Tabacos	Currency	Gold	Polymers
Intelligence & Knowledge (I_e)	4.7	6.1	5.2	5.9	6.7
Dog detection capability (I_d)	4.5	5.2	3.8	1.6	2.0
X-scanning (I_x)	2.9	7.7	5.5	5.9	6.7
Luggage photo identification (I_{c1})	1.0				
Luggage photo re-identification (I_{c2})	1.0				

Table 4-2: Mean relative trustworthiness in illegal substance (j) Individual Risk Indicators (i). (ε_{ij})

Individual Risk Indicators	Narcotics	Tabacos	Currency	Gold	Polymers
Intelligence & Knowledge (I_e)	4.8	5.5	5.0	5.3	5.9
Dog detection capability (I_d)	5.5	5.8	4.5	2.6	2.4
X-scanning (I_x)	3.7	7.9	5.3	6.3	6.9
Luggage photo identification (I_{c1})	1.0				
Luggage photo re-identification (I_{c2})	1.0				

9.3. Topology of the Individual Risk Indicators

The Individual Risk Indicators are real-time input data required by the risk assessment tool. Each of the indicators is issued from a different data source. Only, the Camera bag identification and re-identification scores are independent of the kind of the illegal substances. This difference in nature is considered during the numerical modelling and calculations.

However, all indicators have one common characteristic of interest. They all have probabilistic nature. As mentioned above, we are using simulated input data in the validation-in-principle of the risk assessment algorithm. In Table 5, it is shown a simulated input sample of the individual Risk indicators.

Table 5: Simulated risk Indicators input data

Individual Risk Indicators	Narcotics	Tabacos	Currency	Gold	Polymers
Intelligence & Knowledge Databases (I_e)	60%	0%	40%	0%	0%
Dog detection capability (I_d)	45%	30%	15%	0%	0%
X-scanning (I_x)	55%	30%	15%	0%	0%
Camera bag identification (I_{c1})	20%				
Camera bag reidentification (I_{c2})	60%				

The simulated inputs in Table 5 are all probabilistic measures. The risk indicator (I_e) tells that there is a probability of 60% and of 40% that narcotics or currency notes, respectively, are transported on a given flight. The Camera identification (I_{cl}) success probability is about 80% ($I_{cl}=20\%$) and the reidentification success probability is 40% ($I_{c2}=60\%$).

9.4. Aggregation & Global Risk Determination Procedure

Using the simulated Risk input data (the individual risk indicators), the Global Risk Indicator is estimated to be about 78.6%. The Global Risk Indicators (I_G) tells that the probability of having a trafficking case in a bag is 78.6%. In case of the failure of the cameras identification and reidentification capacities, the risky bag will normally be intercepted with a probability of 30% thanks to behavioural and random inspections, Figure 4(c). Adding the cameras identification capacities, the interception expectation of the same illegal trafficking will jump from 30% to 55%. This demonstrates the critical contribution of the Camera identification and reidentification technologies in risk-based inspection decision making.

9.5. Relative Classification of the expected Illegal substances

Once the Global Risk Indicator (I_G) is determined, one's interest switches to the expected illegal substances and their expected classification.

The relative expected classification of the illegal substances is as such: narcotic with a score of 46.7%, Tabaco with a score of 28.1%, and currency with the score of 25.2%.

10. Conclusions

The EU Horizon project "BAG-INTEL" final target is to develop a Risk-based AI-tool to support customs intrusive inspection decision making relative to luggage control in airports. The Risk-based component of the AI-tool is powered by a risk assessment algorithm. The risk assessment algorithm mixes probabilistic statistics (deductive approaches) and Analytic Hierarchic Process (AHP) classification theory (inductive approach). The risk assessment algorithm does not exploit any AI-data processing technology.

The Algorithm and its implemented mathematical models are explained in a didactic manner to guarantee its successful implementation in the BAG-INTEL's tool to support customs intrusive risk-based decision-making processes.

The development of such an algorithm required building up a dedicated evolutive "Customs Inspection Experience Feedback Database" as the functioning of the algorithm requires some weighting factors issued from customs inspection experience feedback. The exploitation of such experience feedback requites equally the use of probabilistic-statistics and of inductive classification methods such as the AHP.

Some numerical experimental runs were carried out and other will still be run to identify the full extension of the informative outputs that can be expected from the algorithm and its mathematical models.

The preliminary results of the experimental runs gave a real insight into many aspects regarding the critical issues in a risk-based decision-making process in the field of customs intrusive inspection of luggage in airports.

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Processing heterogeneous data sources for risk management by knowledge graph databases: the case of BAG-INTEL research project.

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Abstract

Knowledge graphs stand out for their ability to encode and represent knowledge in various fields. With the latest advances in information processing and machine learning, this data structure can increasingly be incorporated more efficiently into reasoning and knowledge acquisition processes. This has made them a valuable and versatile tool capable of answering questions in many domains. In this article, we present these structures, their concepts, and applications and offer an initial approach to their use in airport security within the framework of the BAGINTEL project.

1. Introduction

The BAG-INTEL project is a 3-year Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action powered by a multidisciplinary consortium of 24 partners from 8 European countries, including industrial players, consultancy and advisory firms, universities and research organizations, ministries, customs and tax authorities, and civil authorities. The project aims to develop an AI-based solution to support customs control staff in identifying and locating suspicious luggage for further manual inspection. Risk indicators will be produced and merged once the baggage is scanned by X-ray CT scanners and additional knowledge is extracted from the database. If the customs control staff find these markers concerning, an AI system will use high-resolution cameras to track the suspicious luggage throughout the airport, allowing customs staff to locate it and then proceed with a manual inspection. BAG-INTEL will include a feedback loop where additional and real-time information will be processed to continuously upgrade the risk markers process.

The knowledge from this task will be stored in a graph-based database [9], where we will collect data from the various project partners, trial results, and risk marker information. This type of database has gained popularity since its introduction by Google as a way to manage multiple sources of knowledge with multiple applications [1] (and specifically in the security field [6]). Knowledge graph databases offer numerous advantages in multidisciplinary projects, as they can represent complex relationships, utilize structured and unstructured data sources, absorb information from ontologies (for more realistic knowledge search and representation), and allow a constant evolution in their schema as a fixed table structure does not restrict them. At the same time, incorporating all this information presents a scientific and technical challenge that requires specific design and representation to make the database as functional and practical as possible, particularly in airport security.

This work presents the concept of knowledge graphs in section 1, highlighting why they are an essential tool and their advantages and drawbacks. In section 2, we will introduce the concepts and applications of knowledge graphs. Section 3 outlines our initial proposal for creating a representative knowledge base from which valuable insights can be derived for the project. Finally, we will discuss future directions for this and similar approaches in airport security.

2. Knowledge Graph Databases

In this section, we will present the most important concepts to understand the rest of the article and the relationships between them.

2.1. Graphs, Knowledge Graphs, and Knowledge Databases

Initially, before discussing graph structures or databases, we must introduce the concept of a graph, which is fundamental in mathematics and computer science. A graph is a structure consisting of two main elements: nodes (or vertices) and edges (or links). The nodes represent entities or objects, while the edges represent their relationships or connections. Those edges can also possess a set of different properties, but in the mathematical approach to them, they have only an assigned weight.

The rest of the concepts in this work inherit this basic definition but explore its potential when we establish a bilateral function between these structures and specific concepts. Starting with a knowledge graph, this structure organizes and represents information semantically richly. The nodes correspond to entities or concepts, and the edges correspond to the relationships between these entities, where each relationship can have a label that describes its nature (for example, "is a friend of," "works at," etc.). This allows the information to be much more flexible and enriched, as the relationships between the concepts can be complex and multifaceted.

Although there is still no broad, extended definition of knowledge graph and knowledge graph database, we could establish some specific differences between them. A knowledge graph can be viewed as a graph when considering its graph structure [1]. Formal semantics can be used as a knowledge base for interpreting and making inferences about facts.

From this idea, graph knowledge databases emerge, which store and manage data structured as knowledge graphs. These databases are useful when working with queries involving relationships between entities, as they allow direct and efficient access to these relationships. Unlike relational databases, where tables and foreign keys represent relationships between entities, the relationships are first-class entities in graph databases. This makes it easier to perform complex queries about connections or patterns of relationships, as is common in social network analysis, recommendation systems, or search engines.

Since graph databases are not based on a strict relational model, they are often classified as NoSQL databases. In this context, they are especially useful for working with highly connected data and semantic queries where traditional databases' hierarchical or tabular structure is not optimal.

2.2. Applications

The use of knowledge graphs can be traced back to their relationship with ontologies in the field of computer science, where they have been used to provide expert knowledge in computational processes [1]. Recently, the additional computational capabilities developed through graph-based machine learning have brought these types of data models to the forefront. On the one hand, this is due to their ability to produce usable embeddings that can add the contained information to the system, and on the other hand, thanks to their ability to represent and integrate expert information and semantic structures within computational environments.

For all these reasons, such graphs have surged as a technological approach to solving problems in areas such as question-answering systems and recommendation systems. At the same time, new computer approaches have been developed to improve reasoning over graphs, extract knowledge from graphs, and use network-based methods to obtain novel information from those structures.

Regarding the potential areas of application, knowledge graphs have been widely used in biomedical topics [2], where ontologies have already been established as a powerful describing tool. Especially drug discovery and drug repurposing (discovering which illnesses can be treated with already known drugs) [3], but also in genomic, clinical, and diagnoses, where these graphs enable higher-level reasoning and connections. Besides

that, knowledge graphs are also used in industry, primarily for knowledge fusion [4] but also in security areas. Given the capabilities of reasoning and integration of heterogeneous data, knowledge graphs are used in threat modelling and enhance risk assessment [7]. Specially in cybersecurity [6] and financial [5] environments, for threat and fraud detection [8].

2.3. Computer tools

To conclude this section, it is important to note that, although no standardized query language for graph databases exists that is as widely adopted as MySQL for relational databases, i.e. Cypher (for Neo4j), SPARQL (for RDF graphs), and Gremlin. However, most can read, export, and work with the information represented as triples in the form (S, P, O). In this structure, the subject (S) is the node or entity, the predicate (P) is the relationship represented by an edge, and the object (O) is the related entity. This triple representation is commonly formatted in RDF (Resource Description Framework), a standard model for data interchange on the web.

In our case, the primary tool used for managing the knowledge graph, adding and retrieving information, and extracting knowledge from the graph was Neo4j.

3. Knowledge graphs in airport security

Airport security is one of the top priorities in ensuring the safety of passengers, staff, and facilities. Given the complexity of modern airport operations and the increasing sophistication of illegal activities such as smuggling, an advanced approach is required to manage and analyse the vast amounts of data related to these issues. To address this, we propose a knowledge base that efficiently organizes and connects critical information regarding airport security and smuggling.

The structure of the knowledge base presented is built on a graph model that links key entities such as passengers, luggage, flights, inspections, and suspicious activities. Nodes represent essential concepts like individuals, locations, objects, or incidents, while the edges capture the relationships between them, such as movements, interactions, or known associations.

This model enables the detection of risk patterns and potential threats in real-time and facilitates the historical analysis of smuggling cases, helping to predict high-risk routes or behaviours. Additionally, it integrates information from various sources, such as surveillance cameras, passenger lists, and customs databases, providing a comprehensive view of security operations.

3.1. Bag Intel Proposal

In this section, we will present the proposed knowledge base schema (Figure 1), breaking it down into its key components. Each subsection will explain the role of different entities and relationships within the graph model, detailing how they enhance airport security and prevent smuggling activities. It is also worth noting that this schema is primarily designed to be used at the destination airport as an additional tool to complement smuggling risk assessment. While parts of this work can be understood from a global perspective involving multiple airports, its specific use will be by the arrival airport. Therefore, even though the suitcase may pass through different checkpoints at various airports (as shown in the schema, such as in Figure 3), these are specifically focused on the spaces of the destination airport.

Figure 1: Full Knowledge-base schema

3.1.1. Airport distribution and lines

Our main interest in developing a knowledge base from this project is analysing smuggling information and the flights where it is detected. Establishing a node for each airplane and passenger is logical, allowing us to account for the type of traffic found in the arrival terminal. However, thanks to the potential of graph databases to incorporate heterogeneous data sources, we can enrich this information in various ways. Our proposal involves describing a geographical sector where we have geographic information about airports. Each airport will be linked to different airlines operating various routes. These routes will constitute specific route nodes, which we can use to assess their risk levels based on historical data.

The nodes representing flights will, therefore, be connected to the route nodes. Additionally, we take one step further in concept representation with meta-route nodes. These nodes are designed to highlight, within the database, sets of routes commonly used for smuggling. This feature will allow us to adjust the risk levels of a given flight based on intelligence about intra-city, country, or continent routes provided by security experts. A full schema of this specific part is presented in Figure 2 in detail.

Figure 2: Airport distribution and routes schema, connected to drugs classification.

3.1.2. Bag transportation across the terminal

A particular aspect of our project is the re-identification of luggage. At each phase of our project, additional information may be generated that informs us about how a suitcase has moved through the airport. Therefore, we include a node for each suitcase and establish a set of nodes related to the spaces where the luggage may be located (Figure 3). This set of nodes, when we focus on a specific suitcase, can help us confirm its exact location, as well as identify bottlenecks in the system through the timestamps assigned to the edges marking the entry and exit of each room

Figure 3: Spaces schema for tracking and storing luggage transportation.

3.1.3. Contraband information

The project primarily focuses on gathering information about smuggling routes. This generates a set of additional information that must be incorporated into the knowledge base. To achieve this, our schema includes the relevant ontologies for describing the type of smuggling we are dealing with. Often, a detailed technical or chemical description is not feasible during the detection process, which is why our knowledge base separates possible substances by the type that the scanner can detect. Once the content is confirmed, it is linked to the detected substance based on the ontology proposed by the International Narcotics Control Board for Drugs and Psychotropics.

This approach allows us to connect different substances with specific flight routes or meta-routes while providing specific insights into the methods used to smuggle the substances. Furthermore, these substances are identified based on the machine that scanned them, helping to detect possible malfunctions or improper equipment usage (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Contraband and Passenger information schema.

4. Conclusions

This work presents knowledge bases, their relationship with modern data exploitation techniques, and their typical applications across various fields. Among these, fraud detection and cybersecurity threat identification have been prominent, but to our knowledge, they have not yet been applied to airport security. Within the European project Bag Intel framework, our proposal represents a first step that meets the project's needs and provides a framework and data model that can be expanded to other airports. This model can represent the complexity of airport smuggling situations and enable reasoning techniques through complex semantic relationships to efficiently utilize the data.

Our proposal offers a functional model with the ability to address many uncertainties. In future work, using historical data, we will explore potential applications and the reasoning capabilities of the model to generate insights and enhance the fight against smuggling in commercial flights.

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BAG-INTEL: A Hierarchical Multi-Cloud IoT-Edge-Cloud Architecture for Enhanced Airport Security and Operations

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Abstract

The EU Horizon project BAG-INTEL integrates Internet of Things (IoT) devices with Artificial Intelligence (AI) within a hierarchical multi-cloud architecture to enhance airport security and operations. The design of the BAG-INTEL system is presented in this study. It consists of three layers: common European data environments for non-sensitive information transmission, national governmental cloud clusters for secure interface with federal resources, and edge computing for local data processing. BAG-INTEL tackles latency and data security concerns by utilizing artificial intelligence and a scalable, safe cloud architecture. Its effectiveness and adaptability are demonstrated by deployment scenarios at different airports. Because of its scalability, the architecture can be applied to additional security-sensitive sectors. In the future, it may also be enhanced with global cloud integration and AI-driven predictive analytics. A new benchmark for the integration of cloud, edge, and IoT technologies in airport security is established by BAG-INTEL. The system's architecture, implementation, and possible uses are described in this paper, with a focus on how they may affect cloud computing, airport security, and the Internet of Things.

Keyword: Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Airport Security, Multi-cloud Architecture, Customs, Edge Computing, Cloud Computing

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and Motivation

Airports are complex environments where security, efficiency, and operational effectiveness are paramount. The growing number of passengers and the complexity of potential security threats require modern technology solutions. Conventional systems that depend significantly on human resources and outdated technologies frequently find it challenging to meet the requirements of modern airport operations. The BAG-INTEL project seeks to tackle these difficulties by combining Internet of Things (IoT) devices with Artificial Intelligence and an advanced multi-cloud architecture that improves the security and effectiveness of airport operations.

The project emphasizes the utilization of AI-driven tools for luggage inspection, integrated with a secure and scalable cloud infrastructure, which is fundamental to its innovation.

1.2. Objectives

The primary objective of this paper is to present the architectural design of the BAG-INTEL system, with a focus on its hierarchical, multi-cloud structure. The document will describe the architectural framework and its components.

- Demonstrate how the architecture natively fosters data security and facilitates real-time processing.
- Examine the scalability and application of the architecture across several domains, establishing a paradigm for secure and efficient data processing infrastructures.

2. Related Work

2.1. IoT and Cloud Computing in Airport Security

IoT devices have become increasingly prevalent in airport security, offering critical data from sensors, cameras, and various monitoring systems. Nevertheless, the integration of these devices into a unified system capable of real-time data processing and responsive security threat management continues to be challenging. The current literature underscores the drawbacks of centralized cloud systems, including latency challenges and data security difficulties, which the BAG-INTEL architecture seeks to address.

The study indicates that BAG-INTEL's strategy of integrating edge computing with cloud technology addresses these difficulties by facilitating local data processing at the airport, hence minimizing latency and improving security.

2.2. Multi-Cloud Architectures

Multi-cloud architectures are increasingly adopted in security-sensitive settings as they provide workload distribution among various cloud providers, hence improving resilience and mitigating vendor lock-in. The hierarchical structure of BAG-INTEL's architecture enhances this methodology by incorporating additional layers of security and control, guaranteeing that data is transferred solely when essential and in accordance with strict security rules.

The project demonstrates that BAG-INTEL's multi-cloud architecture, featuring separate layers for on-premises processing, governmental cloud integration, and European data sharing, represents a strong strategy for managing sensitive data across various cloud environments.

3. BAG-INTEL Architecture Overview

3.1. Architecture and IoT Layers

The BAG-INTEL architecture is designed under the IoT-edge-Continuum and split into the following main layers:

- **Cloud Layer:** Performs deeper data analysis, coordination, and long-term storage
- **Fog Layer:** Balances the workload between the edge and the cloud
- **Edge Device Layer:** Responsible for collecting real-time data and processing it locally

And supplementary layers:

- **IoT Sensors Layer:** Contains all the sensors of the system
- **External Data Layer:** Contains all the external data sources and is part of the Edge Device Layer
- **Offline Layer:** Contains all the ML training procedures and is part of the Cloud layer
- **User Interface Layer:** The layer comprising all the visualizations and end-user interfaces

3.1.1. Cloud Layer

At the cloud layer, powerful computer resources are provided together with data storage and management, coupled with high-performance computing (training of AI models). It hosts the offline layer (described below), which includes all the ML training sessions, all the cloud data processing, management and persisting, and the system's digital twin. Furthermore, it addresses the security of data through the interim repository, which is utilized to process externally retrieved data, stored with privacy until they are legally clear to be stored in the system. After data are cleaned, becoming legally and ethically safe, they can be persisted in the External Knowledge Base. The Cloud Layer also hosts the digital twin.

3.1.2. Fog Layer

The fog layer acts as a bridge between the edge and the cloud layers. We opt to host processes here that are located closer to the edge data to improve response times and reduce bandwidth consumption. All the main processes of the system are located here including both the baggage reidentification and luggage risk classification modules. Placing these two main components at the Fog Layer secures direct access to both the edge and cloud layer's data. Fog layer is part of the cloud layer and hence not visible in [Figure 1](#).

3.1.3. Edge Layer

At the edge layer is where the data generation and initial processing happens. Apart from hosting the IoT Sensors Layer (described below), which generates real-time data and the initial processing components for bag triggering, unique ID generation and AI contraband detection, the internal BAG-INTEL Database is also hosted at the Edge Layer. This database will be utilized to persist all the generated and processed system data related to the baggage records. These data are unique for each airport use case and will be persisted for processing by the system and demonstration to the end-users. Finally, the message bus will be hosted at the Edge Layer to ensure real-time asynchronous communications between the system's components. This layer is split into "Outside Airport premises" and "On Airport premises" layers as shown in [Figure 1](#).

3.1.4. Supplementary Layers

As supplementary, we define all layers which are not considered as reference layers in the IoT-Edge-Continuum but are introduced in order to assist the system's architecture:

External Data layer: Includes all the external data sources, independently whether they include sensitive data or not, which will be utilized by the cloud layer of the system to populate, through the Interim Repository, the external knowledge base. This data will be utilized mainly from the Luggage Risk Classification module. This layer can be officially considered as part of the Cloud Layer.

Offline layer: Hosts all the training of the ML models and can run asynchronously and before the system's online operation. This layer can be officially considered as part of the Cloud Layer.

IoT Sensors Layer: Comprises all the sensors setup at the airport (cameras, dog, label scanner, X-ray scanner) and generates real-time data which the system further processes. This layer can be officially considered as part of the Edge Device layer.

User Interface Layer: The user interface layer comprises all the visualizations that are essential to provide input and output to the end-user. Without them, the end-user would not be able to receive the results of the system or introduce input and parameterizations.

3.2. The Hierarchical model of the Multi-Cloud, IoT-Edge-Cloud Continuum Architecture

The BAG-INTEL architecture enables the orchestration of the intelligent analysis performed at different checkpoints along the moving conveyor belt and until the luggage exits the airport through the customs area. The architecture has been designed based on the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum paradigm, enabling real-time responsiveness, by pushing complex, time-critical computation at the edge and even on the IoT while ensuring security and privacy.

A number of state-of-the-art equipment is used including X-ray scanners and cameras for image acquisition. These devices are modeled in the architecture within the IoT layer (Figure 1). An IoT orchestrator enables the integration of the devices, the unification of the data in the platform of the Airport Cloud and their further analysis by AI/NN components.

Figure 1: The Hierarchical model of the Multi-Cloud, IoT-Edge-Cloud Continuum Architecture

The data generated or used during the airport operations are mission-critical, and for this reason we need to avoid their transmission to the public cloud. Nevertheless, the benefits of elasticity, high-availability, resilience and scalability a Cloud environment offers, cannot be overlooked. For this reason, we have designed the development of a secure, airport-located (on-premises) cloud (BAG-INTEL Airport Cloud at the Edge) which provides these desired properties.

The architecture has a hierarchical structure, allowing the connectivity of the BAG-INTEL Cloud at the Edge - forming a core layer (Layer 0) - with other clouds following a multi-cloud paradigm in a layered manner (Figure 1)

The middle layer of the multi-cloud consists of other secure governmental (country specific) clusters which the BAG-INTEL Cloud can extend in an integrated manner (Layer 1, Figure 1). Information received from governmental sources are extremely important as they are processed by AI BAG-INTEL subsystems (External Knowledge subsystems) to generate risk signals.

The top layer of the multi-cloud (Layer 2, Figure 1) allows the sharing of non-sensitive information with Common European Data Spaces and the hosting of non-sensitive information (such as environmental data related to airports and traveling) on European Federated Cloud Infrastructures.

The overall design develops a novel, hierarchical, multi-layered, multi-cloud architecture for the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum. While our proposed architecture has been designed for the BAG-INTEL system and airport operations, it can be used as a general framework for other domains.

The BAG-INTEL system and processes aim to become an integral part of existing airport operations and systems; thus, we have defined its architecture to follow Secure-by-Design principles, establishing security measures that will be implemented early in the development of the BAG-INTEL system. Security measures are integrated with the overall architecture thus avoiding security-related modifications in the future. While the design of the architecture has as epicenter the BAG-INTEL Cloud at the Edge on Airport premises -- protected by the airport security processes and directives, data flows crossing the different cloud layers in the multi-cloud hierarchy, need special attention and specialized architectural designs to enforce security.

Another parameter affecting the overall security of the system, is the need for edge computation residing outside the airport, on technology suppliers' (direct peering sites) infrastructures. "Outside the airport" computational infrastructure, as a separate layer (Edge Layer-Outside Airport Premises, [Figure 1](#)), enables Continuous Integration Continuous Development (CI/CD) and has many benefits allowing development and operations teams to collaborate to deliver services to the BAG-INTEL Cloud at the Edge. Nevertheless, this layer creates serious security vulnerabilities that need to be appropriately addressed by security architecture designs, due to the direct access of the Cloud at the Edge on Airport premises, which is furthermore integrated with the overall airport IT infrastructure. The layers in the hierarchical multi-cloud structure are outlined in the following paragraphs:

- **Layer 0: BAG-INTEL Cloud at the edge**

This layer consists of the Edge Layer-On Airport premises and the Edge Layer-Outside Airport premises.

- **Layer 0.a: Edge Layer-On Airport premises**

The Edge Layer-On Airport premises is implemented within the airport, ensuring that sensitive data from IoT devices, such as cameras and X-ray machines, is processed locally. This layer leverages the low latency of edge computing, essential for time-sensitive tasks such as security screening. This layer has a critical security role, as it keeps data generated by the BAG-INTEL system (e.g. video streams from the cameras subsystem, AI analyses results, external information trusted to the layer) confidential and within the secure airport infrastructure.

- **Layer 0.b: Edge Layer-Outside Airport premises**

The Edge Layer-Outside Airport premises, consists of the infrastructure of multiple vendors' development and operations teams, collaborating outside the airport to deliver services to the Edge Layer-On Airport premises. Such an infrastructure is necessary as it allows development agility and enables the improvement of the overall BAG-INTEL system through machine learning and regular training of the AI models of its subsystems. Nevertheless, strict security measures are required for this layer as it accesses the security critical operations at the Edge Layer-On Airport.

- **Layer 1: Secure Country-Specific Governmental Cloud Clusters**

Country-Specific governmental data are important for the effectiveness of the BAG-INTEL system, as they are processed by the AI components of the External Knowledge subsystem to generate risk signals. BAG-INTEL interfaces with the secure federal cloud clusters, enabling the connection with national security databases and additional governmental resources, thereby enhancing the overall security response. The Security-by-Design architecture, ensures that data shared with governmental systems is protected by stringent security measures, complying with national regulations and standards.

To strengthen the protection of sensitive data received from governmental data sources, an Interim Repository, which is a data repository covered by a legal and ethical umbrella has been included in the architecture as shown in [Figure 1](#). The interim repository temporarily stores sensitive data received from Layer 1 in Layer 0, for privacy protection measures to be applied on them (e.g. anonymization), before these data are diffused within the overall Layer 0 infrastructure. The novel concept of the Interim Repository was first introduced in a white paper of the project PolicyCLOUD and StandICT.eu 2023 [8].

- **Layer 2: Private Cloud (Non-Sensitive Data)**

The outer layer of the BAG-INTEL architecture promotes the dissemination of non-sensitive

information among European federated cloud infrastructures. This layer is intended to oversee data that, although significant, does not pose the same security threats as the data handled at the lower layers. Such data are environmental data (e.g. CO2 emissions and statistics on the number of passengers, luggage flowing through the airports per season/country).

3.3. Data Flow Management and Security Protocols

The BAG-INTEL system is designed to oversee data flows across its layers securely and efficiently. Data flows are regulated by strict rules that guarantee the sharing of only crucial data between layers and external entities. Our approach enforces the implementation of sophisticated encryption methods, access restrictions, and auditing processes in order to protect data during its entire lifecycle within the BAG-INTEL system.

4. Implementation and Operational Scenarios

4.1. System Deployment in Airports

The BAG-INTEL system intends to be deployed in airport environments as a comprehensive solution for enhancing security and operational efficiency. The system plans to integrate seamlessly with existing airport infrastructure, allowing for the real-time processing of data from various sources, including security cameras, baggage scanners, and bag-tag readers. The on-premises cloud (Layer 0.a) handles critical tasks like threat detection and passenger flow management, ensuring rapid response times and reducing the workload on human operators.

4.2. Case Studies

The customs control of checked-in baggage from commercial passenger flights arriving at interior border airports is the main use case for the BAG-INTEL system. When a plane lands, its luggage is moved from the baggage conveyor belt to the carousel area, where travelers retrieve their possessions. Passengers are only allowed entry to the carousel area and are required to exit through a specific customs inspection point thanks to BAG-INTEL. To protect privacy and security, the carousel area is visually isolated from the pre-arrival procedures and baggage belt.

The luggage scanner and the end-to-end re-identification system are the two main parts of BAG-INTEL in this scenario. The scanner uses cutting-edge AI-driven approaches to identify suspicious things in order to discover and identify contraband hidden in the suitcase. From the time of arrival until it clears customs, the re-identification system guarantees continuous tracking of any baggage marked for examination. When suspect luggage is carried into the customs examination area, real-time alarms are sent to the customs officers. When customs consider scanning unnecessary in low-risk circumstances, the system can be turned off to maximize resource utilization.

The purpose of BAG-INTEL is to improve the efficiency of customs inspections by offering high-precision tracking and scanning that easily integrates with the current airport infrastructure. The following are actual instances of how the technology will be put into use and evaluated at different airports:

Use Case 1: Billund Airport, Denmark (Small International Airport)

In Denmark, the entire BAG-INTEL system will be installed at Billund Airport. The ultimate users will be the airport operator and Danish Customs. In this case, cameras will be installed for luggage recognition and registration, and Smiths Detection (SDE) will supply an X-ray/CT scanner.

Prior to installation, a controlled environment will be used to teach the AI system and scanner to detect specific forms of contraband, such drugs. In addition, a dataset of photos of luggage gathered at the beginning of the project will be used to train the camera and AI. This guarantees that luggage travelling through the airport may be successfully recognised and reidentified by the system. The re-identification system and the AI's capacity to identify contraband will be put to the test by customs inspectors, who will also make sure that any suspect luggage is appropriately identified and examined before it leaves the airport.

Use Case 2: Thessaloniki Airport, Greece (Medium-Sized International Airport)

The entire BAG-INTEL system will be installed in this use case at the airport in Thessaloniki, Greece. The principal end users will be Greek customs, border guards (Hellenic Police), and airport operator Fraport Greece. For this configuration, an X-ray/CT scanner will be provided by Smiths Detection (SDE), and the airport will supply handheld devices for scanning bag tag labels prior to the luggage entering the X-ray/CT scanner. Important details like the departure airport that are provided by these labels will be entered into the BAG-INTEL knowledge base for risk assessments.

While the camera/AI will be trained on a dataset of suitcase photographs gathered earlier in the project, the scanner/AI will be trained in a controlled environment, much like the Billund scenario. In this use case, the effectiveness of BAG-INTEL will be assessed using key performance indicators (KPIs), and the system's compatibility with the current customs, airport, and law enforcement systems will be tested. This guarantees that the BAG-INTEL system improves airport security agency collaboration.

Use Case 3: Adolfo Suárez Madrid–Barajas Airport, Spain (Large International Airport)

A high-risk setting will be used to test the BAG-INTEL system at Madrid-Barajas Airport, one of the busiest airports in Europe. The testing will involve border police (Guardia Civil), Spanish customs (AEAT), and other relevant parties. Because Madrid-Barajas is home to many foreign flights with a high risk of contraband, it offers a rare chance to stress-test the system in difficult circumstances.

Here, the degree of screening for arriving flights is already decided by the customs and border police using a predetermined risk assessment scale. All baggage on flights classified as "Very High Risk" or "High Risk" is subject to X-ray screening utilising mobile scanning trucks on the apron, which is outside the terminal building. Dogs that detect things are also used in this situation. The BAG-INTEL system faces a special problem because of this operation's mobility character, especially regarding the positioning and functionality of AI cameras, which could not be in fixed positions.

The BAG-INTEL system will be put to the test in a high-stakes, real-world setting in this large-scale use case to make sure it can handle the challenges of a sizable airport with a variety of operational requirements. In this context, the integration of AI tracking and mobile scanning will demonstrate the system's scalability and versatility.

5. Scalability and Applicability

5.1. Adaptation to Other Domains

The architecture of BAG-INTEL is engineered for scalability, enabling adaptation for many applications requiring robust and secure data processing. The identical hierarchical methodology might be utilized in border control, where the necessity for real-time data processing and secure transmission is equally critical. The document indicates that the system's design is sufficiently adaptable to accommodate the varied requirements of other industries, rendering it a desirable framework for other security-sensitive contexts.

5.2. Future Developments

The BAG-INTEL system suggests several possibilities for future enhancement, including the use of AI-driven predictive analytics to foresee security threats prior to their development. A potential advancement may include the expansion of the system's multi-cloud architecture to include worldwide cloud infrastructures, thereby augmenting its scalability and resilience.

6. Conclusion

The BAG-INTEL system represents a significant advancement in the integration of IoT, edge computing, and cloud technologies for airport security and operations. BAG-INTEL provides a scalable and secure solution for the various challenges of airport environments through the implementation of a hierarchical, multi-cloud architecture. The system's capacity to locally process crucial data while utilizing the advantages of cloud computing establishes a new benchmark for the successful management of sensitive operational data. The paper establishes the architecture and potential uses of the BAG-INTEL system, emphasizing its contributions to the domains of IoT, cloud computing, and airport security.

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Quantitative Assessment of Landslide Risk to Residents on the Slope of a Hazardous Area in Malaysia.

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Abstract

This paper presents a Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA) method for the impact of a landslide using a case study in Malaysia. The probability of the slope experiencing a landslide event is computed. Subsequently, the runout of the landslide in the case study is forecasted using the previously developed empirical model for Malaysia. The risk for elements at risk along the landslide's runout path is estimated. The overall risk to society is then portrayed using an F-N diagram, demonstrating the practical application of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion. In addition, the results of this analysis will serve as a foundation for conducting a cost-benefit analysis, designing risk reduction measures aligned with the established risk acceptance criteria, and informing future land use planning processes.

1. Introduction

A specific case study was selected for numerical simulations aimed at providing an understanding of the risks associated with rainfall-triggered landslides. These simulations function as an initial warning system, particularly in areas prone to severe landslides that can result in extensive devastation and potential loss of lives. To mitigate these risks to both lives and property, it becomes imperative to conduct thorough stability analyses and risk assessments of slopes within specific regions.

This paper focuses on evaluating the direct risk to life within a residential area in Malaysia. A developed empirical landslide run-out model is employed to quantify the risk of landslide run-out for elements situated downhill from the areas where landslides initiate. From the analysis, one shall see that the slope was already within the unacceptable risk region of the Malaysian risk criterion, leading to the occurrence of slope failure resulting in high casualties. In addition, the results of this analysis will serve as a foundation for conducting a cost-benefit analysis, designing risk reduction measures aligned with the established risk acceptance criteria, and informing future land use planning.

Using PLAXIS LE, the numerical model was conducted as follows: (i) Examining the transient seepage into soil slopes during an extreme rainfall scenario with a 10-year Annual Recurrence Interval (ARI); (ii) Evaluating the probabilistic slope stability associated with transient seepage induced by extreme rainfall infiltration. Through this analysis, the probability of an event of a specific magnitude was ascertained. The consequence of an event of a particular size was assessed in relation to the vulnerability of the residents by taking into account the runout distance, enabling the estimation of the annual probability of a fatality resulting from a landslide in the study area.

2. Extreme Rainfall Analysis

Rainfall records spanning the past 48 years were acquired from the Department of Irrigation and Drainage. Employing the Gumbel extrapolation technique [1], [2], the maximum rainfall anticipated within those specific days was computed for a return period of 10 years. The choice of a 10-year return period aligns with recommendations stipulated in the Geotechnical Manual for Slope in Hong Kong [3] and stands as a prevailing design standard for Malaysian slopes, as cited in studies by [2], [4].

Figure 1 displays the computed maximum potential rainfall and rainfall intensity expected over durations of 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 14, and 30 days for a 10-year return period, derived through Gumbel's extrapolation method. The data illustrates that the pattern of rainfall across various days does not follow a linear progression due to the

non- uniform nature of precipitation over extended durations. The difference of rainfall intensity between day 1 and day 2 is seen to be drastic while day 2 onwards the difference is seen to be more gradual. As the total volume of rainfall accumulates over a given timeframe, the intensity tends to diminish.

Figure 1 Intensity of Rainfall occurring at different days for return period of 10 years.

3. Numerical modelling

In this study, an unsaturated/saturated transient seepage analysis was conducted using the Groundwater component within the PLAXIS LE computer program. The simulation spanned a 30-day period, simulating of extreme rainfall condition. The analysis commences by defining the initial state as the position of the initial groundwater table, accompanied by a designated maximum negative pore water pressure head. This approach enables a more realistic execution of the analysis.

Preceding the seepage analysis, the definition of material or soil properties and the establishment of boundary conditions were necessary prerequisites. The characterization of soil properties relied on volumetric water content (VWC) functions, soil water characteristic curves (SWCC), and Hydraulic Conductivity Functions (HCF), considering both unsaturated and saturated material models. Among the numerous of available functions integrated into PLAXIS LE i.e. VWC data point function, Van Genuchten function Gardner Fit, and Fredlund-Xing function etc., this study employed the data point function for defining volumetric water content. A general SWCC specific to silty residual soil from Malaysia, as outlined in [5], was implemented in the simulation. [Figure 2](#) (a) & illustrate the SWCC and hydraulic conductivity function utilized in the simulation, respectively. The impermeable underlying rock layer was replicated within the simulation by allocating an extremely low hydraulic conductivity value, specifically set at $1E-17$ m/s.

Figure 3 shows the slope model simulated in PLAXIS LE. The geometric configuration of the slope was subject to the following boundary conditions:

- 3.1 Rainfall intensity was modeled as a flux boundary condition on the slope's surface.
- 3.2 Below the groundwater table, total head boundary conditions were applied along the sides of the slope.
- 3.3 Above the groundwater table, a nodal flux of $Q = 0$ m³/s was enforced along the slope's sides, symbolizing a no-flow boundary condition.

The results derived from the seepage analysis, which portray the distribution of pore water pressure (PWP), serve as input data within the Slope Stability module of the PLAXIS LE computer program [29]. The unsaturated shear strength is computed by employing the Mohr–Coulomb failure model within the PLAXIS LE program, Details regarding soil properties can be found in [Table 1](#).

The Alternative Point Estimated Method (APEM), is employed for probabilistic analysis [6]–[8], reduces the necessary number of analyses when employing the Monte Carlo method. APEM significantly cuts down the computational time essential for statistical analysis [7], [9]. With $2N + 1$ model runs, where N represents the quantity of model input variables, this method can compute probabilities efficiently. It particularly appeals in

scenarios with numerous input variables exhibiting variance. The parameter Cohesion is assigned as a log-normal probability density function [9] while friction angle and unit weight are assigned to follow a normal distribution [1], [9]. The outcomes will be presented in terms of the probability of failure, *pf*. Moreover, APEM allows the depiction of results via a tornado diagram, indicating the relative impact of each input variable [8]. Consequently, it becomes feasible to ascertain both the overall probability of failure and the input variable exerting the most substantial influence on the factor of safety.

Figure 2 (a) Soil–water characteristic curve (SWCC), (b) hydraulic conductivity function

Figure 3 General profile of the slope at the case study area

Table 1 Soil properties of the slope of study

Soil Layer	Soil Type	Depth (m)	Effective Cohesion, c' (kPa)	Effective Friction Angle, ϕ (°)	Soil Unit Weight γ' (kPa)
Layer 1	Silt	0–13.5	3	26	17.5
Layer 2	Sandy gravel	13.5–17	8	32	18
Layer 3	Granite	17 onwards	10	38	18.5

3.1 Pore-water pressure results

Transient pore-water pressure variations at the middle of the slope (Section A–A') are shown in **Figure 4**. Similar PWP trend and results is seen in the documented study by [10]. It should be noted that PWP at the soil surface at the middle section became near zero after a period of 3 days of continuous rainfall for the entire period the extreme rainfall. Again, similar results were obtained by [10] where the PWP at soil surface saturates at an early phase under extreme rainfall conditions. The early saturation occurs due to the swift decline in matric suction and reduced cohesion among soil particles [10]. It's important to highlight that no positive pore-water pressure was observed at the surface during the entire simulation duration which is similar to the results in the model by [5], [11]. The PWP (Pore water pressure) at 2 meters below the surface at section A-A' (**Figure 3**) never reaches zero, suggesting that the water table does not rise to that extent during the entire 30 days of continuous extreme rainfall.

Figure 4 PWP profiles for the slope at section A- A' during the simulation

3.2 Probabilistic slope stability analysis results

The changes of the Factor of Safety (FOS) with time in the simulation is shown in **Figure 5**. The findings from the analysis of slope stability showed a pattern akin to PWP, demonstrating a decline in Factor of Safety (FOS) from

1.18 at the initial stage, reaching near critical value of 1.04 at the end of the 30th day of extreme rainfall. Similar results were seen in documented studies related to the same slope [5], [11], [12]. As the PWP at the slope built up, the safety factor decreases. The drastic drop in FOS at the beginning can be explained by the high rainfall intensity at the beginning of the simulation as seen in Figure 1. Due to the substantial increase in water load during early stages of extreme rainfall, there is a rise in pore water pressure and a simultaneous decrease in matrix suction. Consequently, this causes a decline in the slope's safety factor. The slow and marginal decrease in FOS safety after the initial drastic drop is due to the lower value of saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil. Overall, the observed decrease in Factor of Safety (FOS) was attributed to prolonged extreme rainfall and the subsequent redistribution of the infiltrated rainwater [5].

Figure 7 displays the most vulnerable slip surface with the minimal FOS. Following 30 days of extreme rainfall, the critical safety factor reaches 1.04 when employing the GLE solution technique. Analysis using this method indicates that the calculated safety factor just after the 30-day rainfall period hovers close to the brink of failure. In real life scenario, the same slope experienced the failure resulting in deaths due to prolonged antecedent rainfall when its FOS approach and drop slightly below the critical safety factor of 1.0 [5], [12]. This indicates that this slope will be likely to fail if subjected to 30days continuous rainfall of 10 years-ARI. It should be noted

that in real life, failure occurred at the top layer of the soil which greatly aligned with the simulation results presented in [Figure 7](#) [5], [11].

The tornado diagram in [Figure 8](#) shows the relative influence of the material parameters to the factor of safety value. The analysis indicates that the FOS for this slope is primarily affected by the friction angle of silt, the soil at the top layer. Following this, the cohesion of top silt layer does exert some influence on the factor of safety. However, the cohesion of the second layer, comprised of sandy gravel, alongside the materials' unit weight, has a relatively uniform and minimal impact on the slope's safety factor which is not surprising as the critical slip circle occurs only on the top soil layer of the slope. Similar results are obtained in published studies where friction angle exert the highest influence on FOS followed by cohesion of the materials [1], [9], [13].

The probability of failure, pf throughout the simulation is presented in [Figure 6](#). The pf during the initial condition is computed at 0.0786 through the APEM analysis in PLAXIS LE. According to the expected levels of performance in terms of probability of failure by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as seen in [9], the computed pf at initial stage is *unsatisfactory*. The unsatisfactory performance of the slope is not surprising at all, numerous slope failure incidents have been reported in the area [5], [12], [14]–[16]. There is a drastic rise in pf at the early stages which aligns with the drastic drop in FOS due to the high extreme rainfall intensity at that time. Increased rainfall intensity elevates the likelihood of failure as it swiftly generates positive porewater pressure, thereby diminishing shear strength parameters [1]. Conversely, lower rainfall intensity decreases the probability of failure due to the absence of these effects. It should be noted that the standards by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers considers that a slope with pf of 0.16 and above as *hazardous*. The slope of this case study reached the hazardous stage at day 16 of continuous rainfall and reaches a final pf of 0.355 after 30 days. Thus, the expected level of performance of the slope after 30 days extreme rainfall at 10 year-ARI is *hazardous*. It should be noted that the hazardous performance is in good agreement with numerous documented studies found in [5], [12], [14]–[16]. Furthermore, in real life scenario, fatal landslide has occurred in this slope before that result in deaths due to prolonged antecedent rainfall [5], [17]–[19]. The findings derived from PLAXIS LE models indicate the potential criticality of the slope in the event of a 30-day rainfall of a 10-year return period. Previous studies have demonstrated that landslides triggered by rainfall occurred in slopes within Hulu Kelang, particularly in areas with soils of moderate permeability, primarily due to extended antecedent rainfall [5], [12], [14]–[16]. Hence, the outcomes of this investigation align with documented studies, further supporting their validity.

4. Risk estimation and quantification results

From [Figure 7](#), the retrogression distance, rL was calculated to be 150m. Sim et al. [20] formulated a relationship between retrogression distance, rL of a landslide and its subsequent runout, Lu which is, $Lu = 3.6322rL^{0.8475}$. Using the established empirical model, the runout is subsequently calculated at 254m which is a little higher than the actual runout that occurred (210m). The total travel distance from the crest to the toe of the slide will thus be approximately 404m. These estimates are a little more on the conservative side (real life total travel distance 330m). The model was made to give runout parameters on the conservative side and to provide a safety margin for emergency situations, avoiding underestimation of risk and hazard. As stated by [21], a conservative prediction could be highly suitable for initial evaluations of landslide susceptibility and hazard. In addition, although the prediction was conservative, it is not unrealistic as the model was developed on the basis of real life landslide cases [21]. With a ten year return period rainfall, (probability of occurrence of 0.1 (1 in 10)) and a resulting probability of slope failure of 35.5% or 0.355, the probability where a landslide would occur that would result in a total runout distance of 404m is thus computed to be at 0.0355. The estimated landslide affected zone is plotted in [Figure 10](#) taking into account the total travel distance of 404m. The residential area comprises mainly of houses and its occupants were treated as elements of risk. The loss of human lives is the main focus for risk estimation. There are around 21 houses located in the affected area as seen in [Figure 10](#).

The risk analysis approach was primarily built upon the framework outlined by Lee and Jones [22] and was adjusted and broadened according to the specific scenarios being examined. Consequently, a definition for risk analysis was formulated as follows:

$$\text{Risk} = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit}|\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Damage}|\text{Hit}) \times C$$

The equation Risk equals the product of P(Event) multiplied by the conditional probabilities of P(Hit|Event) and P(Damage|Hit), all multiplied by the consequences (C) resulting from the landslide event. Here, P(Event) represents the anticipated likelihood of a landslide event occurring annually, P(Hit|Event) signifies the yearly probability of an element being impacted given a landslide event, considering both spatial and temporal probabilities of affecting elements at risk, P(Damage|Hit) denotes the yearly probability of damage occurring given that an element is impacted, measured on a scale between 0 and 1, and C signifies the consequences stemming from the landslide event.

In the context of this study, 'Damage' was interpreted to denote the occurrence of one or more deaths among the residents, effectively encapsulating the combined notions of 'Damage' and 'Consequences.' As a result, the equation is transformed into:

$$\text{Risk} = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit}|\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Death}|\text{Hit}) \times C$$

Risk equals the product of P(Event) multiplied by the conditional probabilities of P(Hit|Event) and P(Death|Hit).

Figure 5 changes in FOS with time

Figure 6 Changes in probability of failure with time

Figure 7 Critical slip surface with lowest factor of safety after 30 days of extreme rainfall at 10-year ARI with GLE method

Figure 8 Relative influence of material parameters to FOS

Figure 9 Aerial views of the case study slope. Source: [12]

Figure 10 predicted runout of the potential landslide

2.1 P(Event)

According to Winter [23], landslide hazard, referred to as P(Event), is defined as the yearly probability of occurrence derived from historical data. This explicitly adopts a uniformitarian perspective, assuming that the past serves as a reference for future events. There remains a debate on the suitability of relying solely on historical natural process patterns as a predictor of future occurrences. For example, uncertainties arise regarding the projected qualitative rise in landslide frequency due to climate change [10], [24]. Furthermore, this method requires a complete landslide inventory which unfortunately is not ideal hence it will lead to complications in directly evaluating landslide hazard [25]–[27]. On the other hand, P(Event) can also be determined through the computation of the probability of failure of a slope [26], [28]. Hence, after conducting comprehensive probabilistic slope stability analyses, the likelihood of an annual occurrence (or frequency) of a landslide covering a total travel distance of 404 meters, capable of potentially damaging 21 houses situated on the slope in the case study, has been calculated to be $P(\text{Event}) = 0.035$.

2.2 P(Hit | Event)

When a landslide occurs on the slopes adjacent to the residential area within the study zone, the individuals residing in the houses are considered the potential vulnerable elements. This risk factor comprises two

contributing aspects, specifically denoted as $P(\text{Wrong Place})$ and $P(\text{Wrong Time})$ [22]. The duration for which an asset or an individual remains susceptible to the hazard—being in the 'wrong place' at the 'wrong time'—can vary significantly. For instance, there exists a disparity in exposure between a person walking underneath an overhanging rock and someone occupying a stationary beach hut. [22]. The probability of being in the wrong place at the wrong time contributes to $P(\text{Hit}|\text{Event})$, which quantifies the probability of an occurrence described as a 'hit' connected with a landslide event.

In the context of individuals residing in the buildings, the determination of 'wrong place, wrong time' relied on the assessment of the amount of time these individuals spend inside the building throughout a year [26]. The frequency of occupancy by individuals is contingent upon the building's purpose. For individuals who occupy a residence almost constantly (such as elderly individuals or homemakers), probability for 'wrong place, wrong time' was considered as 1. However, for individuals in workplaces like offices, and students in schools, it was computed based on an average of 8 hours per day and 5 days per week, resulting in a value of 0.23. Regarding individuals present in the building during the night for 12 hours, the value will be taken as 0.5.

For the present study, the wrong place, wrong time will be taken as the probability where the residents are in the house when the landslide occurs. For simplification purposes, residents within this study are assumed to be at their residences from 7 pm to 7 am on Mondays to Fridays, totalling 12 hours. On weekends, it is presumed that they are absent from home for 8 hours, considering weekend activities like shopping, recreation, dining out, etc. Consequently, this assumption leads to a $P(\text{Hit}|\text{Event})$ of around 0.55. Accordingly, the probability where the house will be hit by the landslide when the resident is residing in the house will be computed as follows referencing documented workflows [22], [23]:

$$P(\text{Individual House Hit}) = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit}|\text{Event}) = 0.035 \times 0.55 = 1.9\text{E-}2$$

2.3 P(Death | Hit)

$P(\text{Death}|\text{Hit})$, denoting human vulnerability (i.e., the likelihood of death upon the convergence of a house and landslide), was established as a quantitative representation of the probability of death resulting from an encounter with a landslide event affecting the house. It signifies the probability of fatality within the hazardous zones of the landslide (i.e., the 'Wrong Place' in either scenario).

Several determining factors influencing human vulnerability in the context of landslides are as follows [29], [30]:

- Whether the landslide covers the individual(s).
- Whether the individual(s) are outdoors or sheltered inside a vehicle or building.
- Whether the building collapses upon impact by debris.
- The nature of collapse in case of building collapse

A vulnerability rating of 1 signifies certain death, while a rating below 0.5 suggests a significantly higher chance of survival. Jaiswal et al. [26] recommends a value of 0.2 to 1.0 for people in reinforced concrete buildings where as the value of 1 (certain death) is recommended for residents residing in tin-shed buildings and 0.6 to 1.0 for residents of houses made of brick in mud without column structures. The likelihood of survival increases comparatively when an individual is inside a reinforced concrete building due to its greater structural strength. Several other documented studies also recommend the value of 0.2 for people inside a building inundated by landslides [31], [32]. According to previous reports, there was a landslide event that struck the same area in 1999 that results in 0 death [33]. In addition, there have been several other landslide that results in the destruction of bungalows with zero fatalities i.e. 2014 and 2022 Ampang landslide which is not far from the site of case study; 2016 Cameron Highlands landslide [34]–[36]. Harahap & Hazirah [37] proposes a vulnerability rate of 0.48 for the residents affected by landslides in the studied area; however, considering the preceding information, this latter figure appears notably high and somewhat conservative. The evidence provided above strongly indicates a notably reduced figure, and a value of 0.2 for $P(\text{Fatality}|\text{Hit})$ appears fitting within the context of the case study.

2.4 Societal Risk

The societal risk posed by landslide along the case study area is addressed using the F-N diagram, focusing on societal risk. The calculation for the societal risk associated with fatalities of inhabitants of the case study area was derived using the following equation [22]:

$$\text{Societal Risk} = \text{Individual Risk} \times \text{Exposed Population}$$

The specific group exposed to the landslide hazards are all the inhabitants of the houses in the study area, and their population size was determined based on reasonable assumption in accordance to the past reports [5], [38], [39]. In this study, house occupancies ranging from 1 to 8 per home has been taken as an estimate of for the at the site. Assuming equal exposure to landslide risks within the study area, the research categorized eight consequence classes based on house occupancy. This classification involved grouping houses into these classes, and subsequently, determining the quantity of houses within each class. The calculation of the probable fatalities

(N) for each consequence class involved multiplying the house occupancy by the probability of fatality given a hit (P(Death|Hit)). The calculation for the F-N curve is tabulated in [Table 2](#).

Various methods exist for generating data for the F-N diagram, outlined by Wong et al. [40], and Lee and Jones[22], none holding a superior claim to the other. In this study, Wong et al.'s [40] approach will be used as it has been proven to yield data better suited for plotting on the F-N diagram, resulting in a clearer representation [23], [41]. In comparison to the F-N curve of the case study site to other regions as shown in Sim et al. [19], [42], the F-N curve sits in between that of Nepal and Italy. The landslide risk of the site is also seen to be lower than that of Nilgiri Hills, India which is not surprising as the houses over there comprise various types including those made of tin-shed buildings, brick and mud without columns, as well as non-reinforced concrete houses [26]

From the F-N curve in [Figure 11](#), it's evident that the value of F for N of 4 to 5 deaths falls between 10 years to 100 years. In reality, it didn't take more than 100 years after the construction of Bukit Antarabangsa for landslides to cause fatalities. The 4-5 deaths occurred in 2008, which is over 10 years after the development of Bukit Antarabangsa began around the time of the Highland Tower incident in 1993 [5], [43]. This aligns well with actual reports of the landslide tragedy at the site. Furthermore, the F-N curve falls in the Unacceptable region when benchmarked against the risk criterion of Malaysia [19]. This also means that falls into the unacceptable category of yearly fatalities established by Hong Kong [42], [44]. This precariousness explains the landslide tragedy that occurred in real life at the site and also is of the utmost priority concerning slope mitigation or countermeasure strategies.

Table 2 Calculation for plotting F-N curves for residents at the site using. The consequence class simply refers to the different levels of house occupancy.

House Occupancy {2}/ Consequence Class	P(Death Hit) {3}	Number of Houses {4}	Frequency of Occurrence of N Deaths {5} = {1} x {3} x {4}	Cumulative Frequency of occurrence of N or more Deaths (F) {6}
1	0.169642857	1	3.25E-03	6.83E-02
2	0.169642857	2	6.50E-03	6.50E-02
3	0.169642857	3	9.75E-03	5.85E-02
4	0.169642857	5	1.63E-02	4.88E-02
5	0.169642857	4	1.30E-02	3.25E-02
6	0.169642857	3	9.75E-03	1.95E-02
7	0.169642857	2	6.50E-03	9.75E-03
8	0.169642857	1	3.25E-03	3.25E-03
{1} P(Individual House Hit)		1.92E-02		

Figure 11 F-N curve of the site benchmarked against the interim Malaysian Risk [19]

5. Limitation and future works

Uncertainties arose during the computation of population risk, primarily stemming from the challenge of estimating the likelihood of being in the 'wrong place at the wrong time'; the probability of death when a building is impacted by a landslide. Approaches for evaluating landslide risk should consistently account for these uncertainties and be applicable for implementation across extensive areas without excessive data demands. It is crucial to integrate these uncertainties into the analysis, presenting results as a spectrum of risk values, as demonstrated in this study where we assessed the range of expected losses from the affected zone owing to the landslide runout from the crest to the toe. Given the uncertainties associated with diverse input data in the risk analysis, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive risk assessment on a large scale to inform the planning of risk reduction strategies. Furthermore, these uncertainties can be modelled through various scenarios based on value ranges, employing simulation methods such as Monte Carlo simulation—a potential avenue for exploration in subsequent studies. In other words, incorporating uncertainty quantification methodologies to assess the confidence intervals of estimations would greatly enhance the robustness and reliability of the results. This will also further improve the applicability of the novel Malaysian risk criterion.

6. Summary and Conclusion

This paper illustrates how one can apply the proposed F-N risk criterion through Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA). QRA emerges as a proficient method for comprehending, forecasting, and expressing the levels of risk associated with landslides at a specific location. In this section, QRA for the impact of a landslide on residents (potential fatalities) was reported for a hazardous site in Malaysia through a selected case study. Subsequently, runout of the landslide of the case study was predicted using the developed empirical model. Risk levels were estimated for elements at risk located along the run-out paths of the landslide and the overall risk to society was expressed using an F-N diagram, showcasing the practical implementation of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion.

The methodology takes into account the probability of a slope experiencing a landslide event, predicting both the runout distance and the potentially affected zone. It also factors in the conditional probabilities associated with a house being affected, given an event, and the likelihood of damage or death occurring when a house is affected. The analysis encompasses scenario involving a house being struck by a landslide.

Probabilistic slope stability analysis has shown that the site considered in this study is already in the *unsatisfactory* level of performance at initial stage by the standards of U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as seen in

[9]. After 30 days of extreme rainfall, the performance further plummeted to *hazardous* level. The overall travel distance from the crest to the toe of the landslide was predicted to be around 404 m. These estimates are a little more on the conservative side as the real-life total travel distance was 330 m. The model was made to give runout parameters on the high side and to provide a safety margin for emergency situations, avoiding underestimation of risk and hazard. A conservative approach could be highly suitable for initial evaluations of landslide susceptibility and hazard [21]. The societal risk was conveyed through the F-N diagram, indicating that the annual risk falls within the unacceptable zone of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion [19].

Furthermore, the societal risk level well described the landslide disaster that occurred in real life at that site. This also shows that the vulnerability value of $P(\text{Death}/\text{Hit}) = 0.2$ used in this study seems fitting to context of the study. This is not surprising as previous reports regarding the landslide incident on the same slope brought about the destruction of 14 bungalows resulting in 4 to 5 deaths with 14 individuals sustained injuries and 93 people escaped unharmed [5], [38], [39]. The analyses function as an initial warning system for areas prone to significant landslides, capable of causing extensive damage. Conducting a thorough stability analysis of the slopes in specific regions is crucial to determine the risks and vulnerability of the population and to implement mitigation measures to minimize the potential risks to both lives and property. The assessment approach demonstrated in this paper can be applied to future hillside developments in Malaysia, especially when human lives are concerned.

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Risk Assessment of Liquid Hydrogen in Marine Transportation

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Extended Abstract

This paper presents the major steps of the risk assessment methodology for liquid hydrogen bunkering and a preliminary assessment of safety distances. European and international shipping regulations are becoming increasingly strict to contribute to a neutral climate where Sulfur and Nitrogen Oxides, Carbon Dioxide, and greenhouse gas emissions will be considerably reduced (European Commission, 2019; IMO, 2008). New technologies to adopt alternative low-flashpoint fuels have been already considered to reduce such hazardous emissions from ships, including low-carbon fuels such as Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG), Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) and methanol. However, the use of such fuels can benefit in the mid-term applying the existing technologies and infrastructure. One long-term solution, among others, that would enable a zero-carbon shipping industry in the future is hydrogen. IMO, through the IGF code, allows the application of hydrogen as an alternative fuel for ships (IMO, 2015) and the vessels that use hydrogen as a fuel shall be designed with the specific requirements contained in the SOLAS alternative ship design regulation (IMO, 2009). In addition, some guides have already been developed by classification societies encouraging the use of LH2 (DNV, 2021a; IMO, 2021; ABS, 2021). In parallel, recommendations for ships carrying hydrogen as a cargo have been developed (IMO, 2016; ClassNK, 2017). Infrastructure for transport, storage and bunkering still needs to be built and new safety regulations should be developed and implemented for the use of hydrogen as a marine fuel.

Hydrogen is a pure substance that is produced by steam reforming of methane or water electrolysis. It is an almost zero-carbon alternative, since its combustion merely produces hydrogen or water depending on the production method. To store and transport hydrogen in large quantities, it needs to be liquefied at -253°C . Its high energy density requires storage tanks 5 times larger in volume compared to petroleum-based fuels and therefore liquid hydrogen (LH2) would be practical only for small ships that travel short distances. Nevertheless, regardless of the environmental sustainability, the use of LH2 can pose a significant risk to human life and infrastructure. Primarily, human exposure to extreme temperatures poses a significant cryogenic risk. In addition, it is a flammable substance, especially when mixed with pure oxygen, that requires major measures to be taken to prevent large-scale accidents. Indeed, when LH2 is released into the open air, a flammable gas mixture is formed that produces invisible flames posing a serious fire hazard (ABS, 2021). The result is either a jet fire or an explosive gas cloud and may lead to detonation.

The current study utilizes the methodology already presented by Papazoglou et al. (1992) to quantify the risk associated with LH2 handling in port areas, and particularly it is performed a risk assessment considering truck to ship (TTS) and ship to ship (STS) bunkering. The adopted methodology consists of the next three major phases:

a) assessment of damage states and their frequency of occurrence, b) assessment of consequences of flammable or toxic substances release, and c) risk integration. In the first phase of the risk assessment methodology, master logic diagrams (MLDs) are constructed to determine the initial events that are likely to occur during TTS or STS bunkering. MLDs initiate with the top event "Loss of Containment" which is decomposed into simpler events. Inadequate purging or ventilation, external heat owing to external fire, tank rupture owing to corrosion, embrittlement or weld failures, and overfilling are identified initial events in case of LH2 leakage during bunkering (Ringland, 1994; NASA, 2005). As soon as the initial events are identified, the safety functions and systems for preventing release, and the damage states are identified. Herein, it is examined merely the case of the LH2 release owing to hose rupture during bunkering. The frequency of the occurrence of hose rupture can be calculated by the Event Tree and/or Fault Tree methodology, or by using accident frequency data from the literature. At the current study, the data incorporated in HYRAM+ (Ehrhart and Hecht, 2022) and DNV (2021c) was used.

The second major step involves the assessment of the consequences owing to the LH2 release. As a matter of fact, in case of hose rupture there are two possibilities: a) an immediate ignition will occur at the time of the release thus a jet fire will take place, and b) in case an immediate ignition does not occur, LH2 will evaporate, spread and eventually form a vapor cloud dispersing into the atmosphere that may result in vapor cloud explosion, if ignited. The consequences are directly related to the bunkering rate that differs among the various

bunkering modes. Assuming TTS, low and high bunkering rates can be considered to be 14 m³/h to 56 m³/h respectively (DNV, 2021b), while in STS the respective low and high bunkering rates are 400 m³/h and 1000 m³/h (DNV, 2021c).

Finally, the third major step involves the integration of the results of all previous phases to estimate the total individual risk. Assuming LH2 release and the associated physical phenomena, heat radiation and the maximum impulse are calculated by using the HYRAM+ software. Table 1 shows the damage states as well as the distances where individual risk equals to 10⁻⁶ for the considered LH2 installation assuming a full rupture of a hose and pressure at 10 bar. It is also assumed that after the full bore hose rupture either a jet fire will occur, or a vapour cloud explosion each with 50% probability. Two sets of calculations have been performed. In the first one the frequency of the full bore rupture was equal to 6.0 10⁻⁵/yr, according to HYRAM+ data and in the second one it was equal to 2.64 10⁻²/y for small releases and 2.64 10⁻³ for larger ones, according to (DNV, 2021c). The most serious accident is an hydrogen vapour cloud explosion during STS bunkering at high flow rate.

Table 1. Distances where individual risk is equal to 1.0 10⁻⁶. (HYRAM+ and DNV frequencies)

Damage State - LH2 hose full rupture	Bunkering Rate	Hose Inner Diameter	Frequency of occurrence (HYRAM)	Distance	Frequency of occurrence (DNV)	Distance
	(m ³ /h)	(mm)	(frequency /year)	(m)	(frequency /year)	(m)
TTS and jetfire or explosion	14	10	3.10 10 ⁻⁵	3.5	1.32 10 ⁻²	7
	56	18	3.10 10 ⁻⁵	18	1.32 10 ⁻²	45
STS and jetfire or explosion	400	50	3.10 10 ⁻⁵	63	1.32 10 ⁻³	134
	1000	80	3.10 10 ⁻⁵	101	1.32 10 ⁻³	215

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Introducing a new framework as a response to the existing challenges on road tunnel fire risk assessment.

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Fire accidents constitute the biggest threats for road tunnels during their operation phase. Therefore, these types of accidents are of primary concern for both policy makers and road operators since tunnels are considered as critical infrastructure systems of the road networks. The main focus of each safety strategy adopted is on reaching an acceptable level of safety of the tunnel for the public. Despite the efforts that established a common framework for the risk analysis of fires involving vehicles carrying dangerous goods, issued with the QRAM software (INERIS, 2021), this is not the case with the risk analysis of fires without the involvement of these type of goods. However, this aspect causes a serious gap on the goal of securing the level of safety of tunnel systems since past accidents indicate that this type of fires can evolve in serious disasters (Kirytopoulos, Mourelatos, Chatzistelios, Ntzeremes and Konstantinidou, 2024).

This presentation elaborates on the development of a new risk assessment framework, named “SIREN” in order to address the shortcomings of existing risk-based approaches concerning fire accidents in road tunnels without the involvement of vehicles carrying dangerous goods (Ntzeremes and Kirytopoulos, 2018). The analysis focuses on three axes. Initially, the definition of risk in the field of road tunnels is discussed, since the risk terminology used can affect the subsequent analysis. Subsequently, the structure of the “SIREN” framework is analysed in order to indicate how the shortcomings of existing risk-based approaches are addressed. Last but not least, the approach adopted by the framework for the evaluation of the level of safety of such systems and for this type of accidents is discussed in order to provide policy makers and practitioners with solutions that can enhance the transparency of risk assessment on road tunnel systems.

The proposed framework aims at developing a quantitative instrument in order to assess fire safety of road tunnels. To do so, it adopts an event-oriented definition of risk while it is designed following a scenario-based approach. Contrary to existing quantitative risk assessment methods that all work on a deterministic approach, the “SIREN” operates on a stochastic-based approach. By doing so, the uncertainty of important parameters of the tunnel system is taken into account highlighting its role during the risk assessment process, assisting thus the safety analyst by providing a more realistic depiction of the effect (benefit) of potential safety measures on tunnel system’s parameters.

In brief, the SIREN’s framework consists of four main layers following a top to bottom decision sequence (Ntzeremes, 2019). The framework begins with the stochastic analysis of the system, through which the parameters of the system that should be treated stochastically are identified. Subsequently, the criticality level of each of the above identified parameters is estimated in the second layer. Based on these results, the selection of the critical parameters that risk analysis should be focused on as well as the additional measures required in order to enhance the tunnel’s level of safety is performed. Having applied the additional measures, the third layer of the framework that deals with the re-evaluation of the system is followed in order to estimate the effectiveness of the measures introduced. In last layer of the framework, layer 4, the decision process on the selected additional measures based on the comparison of the estimated cumulative diagrams for the different set of measures introduced in each case, one of which is the diagram that result from the use of the Best Available Technology approach.

Figure 1 depicts the results of an indicative case that the “SIREN” framework is applied. In this Figure, four cases are illustrated associated with its cumulative diagram. The blue line depicts the Number of scenarios (Frequencies) / Number of losses for the current situation of the tunnel. The orange line depicts the result in case the current situation fulfils the minimum requirements imposed by the European legislation. The grey line depicts the results in case current situation not only fulfils the minimum requirements but also designs its mechanical ventilation system in quicker response. Finally, the yellow line depicts the results in case the best available technology on mechanical ventilation is adopted. It should be noted that dots on the figure illustrate the deterministic results in case current approaches implemented for estimating rod tunnel’s risk.

Fig. 1. Cumulative diagrams

The presented framework fulfils the following objectives: (1) incorporates a plausible definition of risk, which allows a more comprehensive understanding of risk from the perspective of all the stakeholders of the system involved in the risk assessment process, (2) develops a framework that can be applied in different tunnel systems, also providing the flexibility to each country to incorporate its provisions and interests, (3) designs a method in order to handle uncertainty, and finally (4) addresses the problem of risk evaluation in the absence of absolute thresholds by the national provisions for these type of accidents by incorporating the Best Available Technology approach.

To sum up, risk analysis definitely supports policy makers and road operators to reach better informed decisions on the level of safety of a tunnel system in order to minimize potential unacceptable fire risks. Therefore, policy makers have imposed the use of risk analysis on a regular basis for securing tunnels' safety. However, the application of any risk assessment method cannot resolve all problems. This presentation will contribute to this issue by providing a risk assessment framework capable of addressing the deficiencies of current approaches while also providing the benefit of being applied to all tunnel types, while conforming to each county's regulative provisions.

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What roles for risk imagination in risk assessment?

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Abstract

This paper presents the findings of an investigation that was carried out following a railway accident: the derailment of a freight wagon. The derailment occurred because the excess of the chains used to secure the equipment loaded on the wagon, fell through holes in the wagon floor and became tangled with a part of the track that was not properly installed. The accident was thus caused by a combination of factors for which the railway undertaking (the company operating the wagon) was responsible and factors for which the infrastructure manager (which builds and maintains the track infrastructure) was responsible.

In the course of the investigation, some inconsistencies were found in the risk analyses carried out by the infrastructure manager and the railway undertaking, which did not identify the possibility of the danger of the surplus of an anchorage tie snagging parts of the line.

The investigating committee concluded that the risk assessment committees would have needed "imagination" to identify these hazards. We discuss the concept of risk imagination, as proposed by N. Pidgeon and M. O'Leary, its usefulness in creating foresight concerning safety, and organizational features that could enhance the ability to identify novel accident scenarios in the railway sector.

Keywords: accident, risk assessment, imagination

1. Introduction

On **17th March 2023**, at about **20:30** o'clock, in the running of freight train no.66358, on track II, between the railway stations Beia and Cața, before entering the bridge from km.262+858, both bogies of the second-last wagon of the train derailed.

The train consisted of 11 wagons, of which 10 were platform wagons loaded with military equipment and another one (coupled first after the locomotive) was a car transporting guard staff. The train was hauled with a diesel electric locomotive.

Figure no.1

The accident site is in the railway county Braşov, track section Braşov – Sighişoara (electrified double-track line), managed by Romanian national infrastructure manager - CNCF „CFR” SA.

The train, the wagons, the hauling locomotive and its crew belong to the Romanian national freight railway undertaking SNTFM „CFR Marfă” SA. Following the accident, there were neither victims nor environmental damage. The derailed wagon and the track superstructure suffered damage.

2. How did it happen?

The wagons of the train were loaded at the Dumbrăveni railway station by personnel belonging to the Ministry of National Defense.

After loading, before the departure of the train from the station, the train was taken over by staff belonging to the transport operator, the train was subjected to a technical composition check and a full brake test, without any irregularities being found.

The wagons were loaded with military equipment on wheels, which was secured by direct anchorage using steel chains and tensioners - *photo no.1*.

Photo no.1

The portions of the chains that were no longer used for anchorage were left on the wagon platform, without being secured against shifting - *photo vo.2*.

Photo no.2

While the train was running on a stretch of track on a curve with a right-hand deviation in the direction of travel, the loose ends of the chains (in the form of a loop) anchoring/fastening the military material, of the second last wagon in the train fell through the gaps in the area where the horizontally movable stakes were placed on the floor of the wagon - *photo no.3*, and the one on the right, in the direction of travel, landed on the track embankment - *photo no.4*.

Photo no.3

Photo no.4

In front of the bridge at km 262+858, there were two interior metal components installed to prevent derailed wheels of rail vehicles from rolling away and to avoid further damage. They must be fitted as shown in Figure no.2.

interior metal components

Figure no.2

But these metal components were not properly installed, as they did not have their left/right ends glued (close together) and were not bent vertically far enough to be inserted into the ballast below the level of the embankment sleeper. Nor were they clamped into each sleeper - *photo no.5*.

Photo no.5

When the loop of chain touching the track bed reached the area of the metal components, which were not properly fitted, it caught the right-hand end of the train, which it lifted.

The raised end of the stock struck the first axle in the direction of travel of the next wagon, causing the climb of the left wheel outside of the curve.

The movement of the wagon with the first derailed bogie led to the derailment of the second bogie inside the track to the right.

After the first axle in the direction of travel fell out, the wagon ran in a derailed state for a distance of about 123 m until the pneumatic connection between the penultimate and last wagon in the train was released. At that moment, the train was braked in an emergency.

3. What the legislation says about loading wagons

Loading and securing of wagon loads is regulated by International Union of Railways (UIC) through "Guides for loading". According to the statements from UIC site (<https://uic.org/freight/load-safety/article/loading-guidelines>), from 2022, European Union Agency for Railways ERA, considers these standards as being "Acceptable means of conformity" that guarantee that the freight loaded on the wagon is correctly secured along the journey to the client. These are updated and completed from time to time (before the accident, the last update was made on April 1, 2022).

In accordance with these guidelines, two types of anchorages/fixings are provided: direct anchoring and indirect anchoring. Wheeled vehicles - as in the case under investigation - must be secured by direct anchorage.

For the realization of direct anchoring, several requirements are laid down, which were complied with in the investigated case. But in this chapter, no mention is made of the issue of securing the surplus steel chain used for anchoring.

The Committee of Inquiry found that this provision is very difficult to find in the Guide. Thus, the committee identified that in the sub-chapter for wheeled vehicles and machinery, there is a paragraph for "further guidance". One of the indications refers to "indirect fastenings" with a hint to a footnote stating: "The minimum breaking strength (straight pull) corresponds to twice the permissible tensile strength (LC); this refers only to synthetic webbing, fabric webbing and load securing webbing as well as steel lashing ropes and lashing chains".

The indication for "indirect anchoring" is continued with the information: see fact sheet 0.7. Information sheet 0.7 introduced in the Guide on 01.04.2022 contains an item entitled "Execution". In this point, it states: "*The free ends of the bindings must be secured and must not hang loose.*".

From the drawings in the guide, it does not appear clear that chains can be used for indirect anchoring.

"If using indirect fastenings, no metallic bindings should be applied to the sheets".

In the light of the above, the investigation commission concluded that for the realization of direct anchoring, the regulations were not clear enough with regard to the surplus of steel chain used.

4. Why did it happen?

Given the conditions in which the accident occurred, the investigation commission checked the activities carried out by each rail player involved in order to prevent the occurrence of the situations observed.

Rail Infrastructure Manager

The responsibility for the installation and condition of the metal components lies with the District Line Manager according to the job description.

According to the regulations, for these staff, the training programs in the railway sector in order to maintain and develop the professional competences specific to the function, consist of continuous professional self-instruction.

In the course of the investigation, it was found that the staff knew how to install the metal components, but justified the fact that they were not properly installed by the fact that this was the way they were installed in 1974 and by the lack of materials and personnel needed to fix them. It was also found that up to the time of the accident, no written requests had been made by the above-mentioned personnel to the higher management to remedy the situation.

During the monitoring activities carried out in the last two years before the accident, there were no findings of improper fitting of the metal components by the staff in control.

During the checks carried out, it was concluded that the level of technical and professional knowledge of the staff responsible for traffic safety was "satisfactory", without giving examples or explaining how this professional knowledge was acquired or assessed.

The investigation commission considered that, given that the staff responsible for the condition of the metal components are self-trained, monitoring the way in which the metal components was managed was the only way to ascertain and remedy the incorrect fitting.

With regard to the risk identification action, in view of the role of a metal component on the bridge, the investigation commission found that the danger of these pieces not being fitted properly had not been identified.

No hazard has been identified that the improper fitting of these could lead to increased consequences in the event of a derailment of rail vehicles before entering the bridge or to its being caught by rail vehicle components that could accidentally hang on the ground, as in the case investigated.

Prior to this accident, there had been no accidents involving an improperly mounted metal component. But after this accident, in the course of 1 year, within the radius of activity of Braşov county, there have been 2 accidents in which the damage was high and was caused by improper installation of this component.

Rail transport operator

The wagon on which the military equipment was loaded had no technical problems. The spaces created in its floor were due to the vertical spikes used for the transportation of other materials, which in our case were positioned horizontally as required by the regulations. It is true that another type of wagon, with a solid compact floor (with no gaps), was usually used, but the legislation does not prohibit the use of a wagon of the type involved in the accident.

The military equipment was properly secured, except that the excess steel chain used was left loose on the floor, unsecured.

The staff who took over the wagons after they had been loaded were not made aware of the provision introduced in April 2022 in the Loading Guidelines regarding the need for surplus chain to be secured.

During the investigation it was found that since the beginning of the transportation contract in 2022 and up to the date of the accident, there were no control - monitoring actions of the personnel with such duties at the stations where trains loaded with military equipment were being loaded.

With regard to the risk identification work, no hazards have been identified in relation to the cargo in the wagons (least of all the possibility of the surplus cargo lashing/ securing chain remaining unsecured and falling through gaps in the wagon floor).

Some hazards have been identified which may create the risk of a rail accident/incident. The preventive measure proposed was "retraining staff and stepping up hierarchical control actions".

But, as shown above, there was no monitoring activity for such shipments.

5. Conclusions

In accordance with the European legislation in force, infrastructure managers and rail transport operators must identify and analyse all operational, organizational and technical risks that are relevant to the type, scale and scope of the operations carried out by the organization. These risks include those generated by human and organizational factors, such as workload, work organization, fatigue or adequacy of procedures, and the activities of other stakeholders. The assessment of these risks shall be done by applying appropriate risk assessment methods (EU Regulation 762/2018).

In using these methods, assessment teams generally use the databases of the rail actor to which they belong.

The assessment teams are made up of the railway actor's own staff - from different specialties of the railway system - locomotives, wagons, traffic, track, etc. In some cases - as in the investigated case - the staff is also trained in risk management principles.

In our case, both rail actors have used their own as well as the rail system's database of rail accidents occurring before 2023 in their risk identification action. As there were no accidents that occurred under similar

conditions, the assessment teams did not take into account such a situation as the one that produced the accident under investigation. All the hazards identified, were related to accidents or incidents that have happened before or to situations which are quite common in the work of front-line staff.

Although the activities mentioned above are regulated by national and European legislation specific to the rail system, the investigation commission concluded that in order to identify the risk of a derailment as it occurred (taking into account the existing regulations), the risk assessment team - in particular the one belonging to the transport operator - needed imagination, which we can call "risk imagination".

The rail operator's risk identification procedure foresees the possibility for front-line staff to issue risk alerts if they identify new risks in their own work. The investigation commission found that these staff did not recognize the possibility of excess chains falling through holes in the wagon floor and therefore did not issue risk alerts.

Michael Lewis believes that risk management involves an imagination effort. And human imagination is a very weak tool in the risk evaluation. People are very good at preventing and responding to crises that have happened before, because they imagine, naturally, that what happened once is very likely to happen again, and organizations put in place rules and regulations to prevent situations that have been shown to be likely to cause accidents. But they are less clever to imagine a crisis *before* it happens and to establish actions to prevent it in a proactive manner (Lewis, 2018).

It could also be argued that, in addition to a lack of imagination, the review boards' analysis was fixed on a prescribed pattern of thinking, contrary to the idea of *safety imagination* (Pidgeon, O'Leary, 1994).

The idea of safety imagination is based upon the principle that our understanding and analysis of events should not become overly fixed within prescribed patterns of thinking particularly when faced with an ill-structured incubation period (Pidgeon, O'Leary, 2000).

In the case under investigation, the thinking of the assessment teams occurred against the background of such an incubation period, with the metal components having been improperly fitted since 1974, without the personnel responsible for its condition and monitoring having noticed this throughout this period. We can say that we witnessed a chain of hidden errors and other partially understood events that accumulated in a way that was at odds with existing beliefs and norms about hazards – the disaster incubation period (Turner 1978). According to Turner, this period led to an increase in the vulnerability of the underlying system, which it did.

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Vulnerabilities and disruption risks for the supply chains of Critical Materials necessary for the clean energy transition

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Extended abstract

Faced with the challenge of reducing EU dependence on fossil fuels, especially those imported from Russia, on top of the longstanding climate crisis, the EU has adopted ambitious targets towards accelerating the decarbonisation of its economy and towards net zero emissions by 2050. But, the clean energy transition is a materials transition: Focus is shifting away from the fuels and moving towards the materials which are necessary for manufacturing the clean energy technologies, such as wind turbines, photovoltaic panels, batteries and hydrogen electrolyzers.

In order to meet the EU's energy and climate targets, we need to build the right technologies, in the right quantities, at the right speed. A failure to fulfil these conditions could jeopardise the clean energy transition, delay the decarbonisation of our economy and finally derail EU's efforts to meet its climate targets. However, many of these clean technologies require materials that are imported from just a handful of countries. Most important are the *Critical Raw Materials* (CRM), which are those materials that have significant economic importance and are exposed to a high supply risk, often because of a high concentration of supply from a few third countries. Demand for these precious resources is expected to increase exponentially in the coming years, as not only the EU but also the rest of the world will increasingly rely on renewable energy sources. This combination of import reliance on a small number of third countries on one hand, and the exponential increase of the materials demand on the other, makes the EU *vulnerable to supply disruptions* and elevates the *resilience of the relevant supply chains* to an issue of paramount importance: It is an issue of *Open Strategic Autonomy*.

To secure the undisrupted supply of critical raw materials necessary for the energy and digital transitions and the space and defence agenda, the European Union adopted on 11 April 2024 the [Critical Raw Materials Act](#) (Reg. (2024)1252). The European Commission's Joint Research Centre has studied extensively the materials supply chains of the key strategic technologies, [analysed dependencies](#), bottlenecks and demand projections, and summarised the findings in the report "[Supply chain analysis and material demand forecast in strategic technologies and sectors – a foresight study](#)", which formed a pivotal body of evidence for the development of the Regulation. That study presents a systematic and detailed analysis of the complete supply chains, from raw and processed materials to components, assemblies, super-assemblies and systems, for 15 key technologies across the five strategic sectors of renewables, electro-mobility, decarbonisation of energy intensive industries, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and space and defence.

The study shows a rapid, multi-fold increase in the demand for the critical raw materials, which are key to the EU's green, digital and security goals. For example, compared to 2020, lithium demand for batteries in the EU is expected to grow 12 times as large in 2030 and 21 times as large in 2050. Similarly, the demand for graphite (natural and synthetic), which is used for components of solar and wind industries and batteries, is projected to increase 14 times by 2030 and 26 times by 2050, always compared to 2020 values. And for the rare earth metals (REE) necessary for permanent magnets for wind turbines (NdFeB magnets) a fivefold increase by 2030 is projected.

However, the EU relies heavily on imports for these materials. In fact, for raw materials supply, the EU share in global production is never higher than 7%. For example, while the EU is a global leader in wind turbine production, it is fully dependent on China for the permanent magnets and the rare earth elements used in them. This concentration of supply poses geopolitical risks that needs to be monitored and mitigated. These are among the main objectives of the Regulation.

One important measures for mitigation of risk is through innovation and substitution with advanced material. At the JRC, we are looking closely at the gap between demand and innovation, with a particular focus on high-impact areas and supply chain resilience. We find that [advanced materials can be good for innovation and substitution in many clean energy technologies](#), but they often face barriers to widespread adoption. We need to ensure that more efficient, sustainable alternatives reach the market faster.

In this presentation, we provide insights on the vulnerabilities of selected strategic supply chains, the dependencies and disruption risks on which the EU is exposed, and we discuss how these risks can be assessed, monitored and mitigated, notably through the EU legislative framework of the Critical Raw Materials Act.

Safe and sustainable-by-design: The case of nanomaterials

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2.1 Introduction to SSbD

Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) principles have emerged as a critical component of the European strategy for safe and sustainable chemicals and materials (ECSS, 2020), to safeguard health and the environment within a Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) (Shandilya et al., 2021). SSbD and SIA encourage the exploration of alternative advanced materials and production processes, within a proactive framework that places an emphasis on incorporating safety and sustainability considerations into the early stages of innovation. Early assessment of risks is key to these approaches, so that developers can identify opportunities to reduce adverse impacts on human health and the environment throughout the entire life cycle of chemicals and materials (Florin, 2023). SSbD can integrate green chemistry principles to promote the development of safe, biodegradable or recyclable chemicals (Furxhi et al., 2023), go beyond the traditional goals of circular economy for reduce, reuse, recycle (Apel et al., 2023), and consider societal and economic aspects (Cassee et al., 2024).

The effort to propose a standardised procedure for SSbD innovation that the industry would adopt voluntarily is still ongoing. Alternatively, the adoption of SSbD could be promoted through regulatory pressures and/or consumer demand for sustainable practices (Tarraco et al., 2021) as part of eco / green innovation approaches. The new eco-design regulation aims to establish updated standards for green products, enhancing their circularity, energy efficiency and other aspects of environmental sustainability in the EU market. This applies to the assessment of existing chemicals as well as the criteria for developing new SSbD products according to the ECSS (EcoR, 2024).

To assist the implementation of SSbD for Chemicals and Materials, the JRC has recently proposed an Implementation Framework and reviewed available tools for sustainable management, including LCA tools for environmental impact or social-LCA (Caldeira, 2022). Recently, Apel et al. (2024) outlined a roadmap for application of SSbD in industrial operations, and highlighted stakeholder needs in the key areas of research, skills and education, and knowledge sharing, emphasizing the need for early, pragmatic SSbD implementation.

2.2 The case of nanomaterials

Nanotechnologies and nanomaterials are key enabling technologies for European industry, offering significant potential to tackle societal challenges in the 21st century. Ensuring their sustainable production and use requires understanding and effectively managing potential risks along the industrial innovation value chain. Assessing the risks of nanomaterials, including nanoforms, is challenging and requires specific provisions (Schwirn et al., 2020) due to their unique features. These include the diversity in the nanomaterial physical and chemical composition, their surface functionalization and structural properties, as well as the variety of their alternative configurations (Blekos et al., 2023).

Over the past decades, significant European funding has been allocated to studying the safety of materials at nano-scale and developing validated frameworks for the assessment, management and governance of risks and specific to nanomaterials and nano-enabled products. The European NanoSafety Cluster (NSC) was established to enhance collaboration between European projects focused on the safety of nano-enabled materials and technologies, addressing toxicology, ecotoxicology, exposure assessment, interaction mechanisms, risk assessment, and standardization efforts (Savolainen et al., 2013). The current volume of research has provided data, protocols, models etc. to aid the risk assessment of new nanomaterials. Efforts are still needed to advance our understanding of the diverse adverse effects caused by nanomaterial exposure (Marcoulaki et al., 2021; Mancardi et al., 2023) and particularly the long-term environmental and health impacts until end-of-life stages (Nizam et al., 2021).

Practical operationalization of SSbD requires clear definitions, terminology and criteria, targeted training,
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strategic plans for collaboration and protection of intellectual property across industries, academia and regulators (Apel et al., 2024). Standards are essential to support public policies and guide the industry toward adopting sustainable practices and environmentally friendly innovations, and provide a framework that ensures green innovations are effectively implemented and aligned with long-term sustainability goals (Scapolo et al., 2015). Recent advancements on nanomaterial-related standards, include the development of Test Guidelines by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2022), guidance and policy reports by the Joint Research Centre, and documentary standards from ISO/TC 229 Nanotechnologies¹ and CEN/TC 352 Nanotechnologies² (Rauscher et al., 2023). Currently, CEN/TC 352 is also developing a standard for the SSbD concept dedicated for nano-scale materials and nano-containing products (Cassee et al., 2024).

Responding to the need for global collaboration, the International Network Initiative on Safe and Sustainable Nanotechnologies (INISS-nano) brings together leading researchers across nano-safety research fields, aiming to improve the understanding and regulation of nanomaterials' impacts on health and the environment (Pogany et al., 2024). On the side of specialized training, there is need for vocational training dedicated to SSbD. At the moment, there are postgraduate courses in Europe focusing on nanomaterials and SSbD principles as part of their curriculum. Additionally, projects like SbD4Nano³ provide e-learning modules and resources aimed at operationalizing SSbD in nanotechnology supply chains.

2.3 Conclusions

SSbD is integrated into the European strategy for chemical safety and sustainability, and aims to serve as a catalyst for innovation, pushing the boundaries of traditional chemical design to include environmentally benign alternatives and improved manufacturing processes (ECSS, 2020). By addressing safety and environmental concerns proactively and embracing a life cycle approach, SSbD not only enhances the marketability of products but also supports the broader goals of environmental sustainability and public health. As research continues to advance in this area, the potential for SSbD to reshape industries for the better remains substantial.

Efforts to implement the SSbD strategy to innovative nanomaterials and nano-enabled products include the development of guidelines, standards and regulations at EU and international level. These are supported by long and ongoing research to enhance understanding of nano-specific hazards, and develop regulatory-relevant assessment tools for risk assessment and management. Knowledge gaps remain in long-term environmental and health impacts of nanomaterials, demanding further interdisciplinary research. However, all the outcomes discussed here provide the framework and drive for adoption of the SSbD approach in nanomaterial innovation, and act as a paradigm for implementation and operationalization of SSbD to other advanced materials.

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Enhancing Cross-Border Risk Assessment for Critical Infrastructure: Challenges, Tools and Recommendations

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Extended Abstract

The Directive on Resilience of Critical Entities (Directive (EU) 2022/2557) outlines that each Member State (MS) should carry out, within a harmonised framework, an assessment of the relevant natural and man-made risks, as well as those of a cross-sectoral or cross-border nature, that could affect the provision of essential services. The risk assessment by MSs should integrate a wide range of hazards, from accidents, natural disasters and public health emergencies to hybrid threats or other antagonistic threats, including terrorist offences, criminal infiltration and sabotage (Art. 5).

Moreover, the actions of MSs to identify and help ensure the resilience of critical entities should follow a risk-based approach that focuses on the entities most relevant for the performance of vital societal functions or economic activities. When conducting their risk assessments, MSs should consider the extent to which sectors depend on one another, including sectors in other MSs and third countries.

The outcome of the MS risk assessments should be used for the purposes of identifying critical entities (Art. 6) and assisting those entities in meeting their resilience requirements (Art. 13).

To facilitate the development of a cohesive framework across the EU, this analysis explores the complexities and challenges of conducting cross-border risk assessments for critical infrastructure (CI) and associated critical entities, from a conceptual perspective.

The study begins by examining the current state of National Risk Assessments (NRAs), highlighting discrepancies, heterogeneity of competences as well as the lack of a harmonised framework and coherent terminology across MSs. NRAs frequently overlook future changes and neglect cross-border risks, focusing on individual hazards and failing to account for compound events and systemic impacts.

This JRC work underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach to assess risks to CI that may have low likelihood but potentially high impact, as well as an all-hazards perspective that includes spill-over effects and interconnected risks. Such approach is essential for fully grasping the systemic vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure, which may be exacerbated by dependencies on sectors in other MSs and third countries.

The study also explores the drivers of cross-border risk assessment, emphasising the need to address fast and slow onset phenomena and the dynamic linkages to climate change, environmental degradation, and urbanisation, which can rapidly transform the risk landscape. Additionally, the analysis highlights the impact causes, orders and categories of cross-border dependencies for CI, providing examples of impacts resulting from neighbouring countries and affecting multiple nations simultaneously.

Furthermore, the study introduces methods and tools for CI risk assessment, considering data inventory, spatial mapping, measuring metrics, and analytical products. It highlights the challenges of cross-border risk assessment, such as fragmentation, communication barriers, comparability, ownership, prioritization, and offers recommendations to address them.

In conclusion, the proposed approach underscores the importance of integrating impact and likelihood in MS risk assessments, understanding the type and magnitude of events, and recognising the potential hindrances to emergency response capabilities due to a CI disruption. It advocates for service-oriented approaches, harmonised information sharing, effective governance frameworks, and multi-stakeholder engagement as

essential components of a robust cross-border risk assessment strategy to address the intricate interplay between risks and the knowledge associated to CI. These elements are vital not only for the management and reduction of risks but also for ensuring the resilience of critical entities across the EU.

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List of abbreviations

CI	Critical Infrastructure
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MS	Member State
NRA	National Risk Assessment

Critical Gas-Fired Power Plants in Integrated Natural Gas and Electricity Systems

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Abstract

The interdependence between gas and electricity plays an important role in ensuring energy security in many regions in the world. In the European Union, there are regulatory frameworks that recognize this interdependency and the concept of critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs) is introduced. Specifically, the Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 on security of gas supply states that critical GFPPs may be given priority over certain categories of gas customers during gas supply crises when curtailment of gas is unavoidable. However, despite the significance of this issue, the Regulation does not set up clear rules about the designation of critical GFPPs. Within this context, we propose an optimisation problem for finding critical GFPPs in interconnected gas and electricity systems. The optimisation problem accounts for the gas and power system flow representation as well as links between both systems. We then analyse the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs such as the electricity network topology, the impact of the natural gas network, and the effect of fuel switching capabilities in GFPPs. In addition, the proposed model allows for a ranking of critical GFPPs provided that they should be prioritised over special categories of gas customers such as protected customers. The proposed methodology is applied to the IEEE Three-Area Reliability Test System (RTS).

Keywords: Critical gas-fired power plants; Gas-electricity interaction; Security of supply; Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938.

1 Introduction

The increasing gas-electricity interdependency has triggered some regulatory changes in the European Union (EU). Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 concerning measures to safeguard the security of gas supply (hereinafter referred to as the Regulation) acknowledges such linkage and introduces the concept of critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs), which can be designated by EU Member States (MSs). According to the Regulation, critical GFPPs could be prioritised over certain categories of gas customers (e.g. protected customers) during gas supply crises when curtailment of gas is unavoidable. Hence, it is necessary to consider both natural gas and electricity networks when it comes to identifying such critical GFPPs. However, the Regulation does not set up clear rules about the designation of such plants, e.g. the time of designation is ambiguous or the methodology guidelines for identifying them are unknown.

The preventive action plans of only seven EU MSs, namely Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, Ireland, Malta, and, to a lesser degree, Poland and Spain, address to some extent the gas-electricity interaction. However, the matter of critical GFPPs is discussed explicitly in three of them: Germany, the Netherlands, and Poland. Germany has regulated the concept of “systemically relevant” GFPPs in Section 13f of its Energy Industry Act¹. Unlike the definition of critical GFPPs in the Regulation, this does not imply by itself that the respective GFPPs should be prioritised over protected customers. The Netherlands lists four criteria to determine if a power plant is considered critical². Finally, Poland is the only country providing a list of critical GFPPs without explicitly mentioning the identification methodology.

The research about the gas-electricity nexus has been growing in the last decade [1, 2]. The recent literature related to the identification of critical assets in coupled gas and electricity systems can be categorised into three groups: (i) graph-theory-based methods [3–7], (ii) hierarchical methods [8–10], and (iii) model-based quantitative assessments [11–14].

Graph theory, which is used in [7], is deemed a promising tool to assess the vulnerability of interdependent gas and electricity systems under cascading failures. The works relying on hierarchical optimisation [8–10] to address

⁽¹⁾ The German transmission system operators for electricity can designate GFPPs with a nominal capacity above 50 MW as systemically relevant.

⁽²⁾ The criteria are: (i) share in total generation capacity, (ii) their use to balance the electricity grid, (iii) their black start function, and (iv) their criticality for continued operation of vital infrastructures.

the vulnerability of interconnected systems are characterised by two drawbacks: (i) scalability issues in real-world and large-sized transmission networks due to computation tractability, and (ii) reliance on linear steady-state models. This work falls within the last category, i.e. model-based quantitative assessments [11–14]. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, none of the works has focused explicitly on the identification of critical GFPPs in line with the Regulation.

The main contributions of this work are twofold:

- We propose a mathematical model to identify and rank critical GFPPs in interconnected gas and electricity systems to comply with the Regulation. We model the electricity system by using a unit commitment formulation whereas the natural gas system is formulated by means of a mass-flow steady-state model. Unlike the closely related scientific literature, we explicitly address the issue of critical GFPPs.
- We analyse the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs such as the network topology and the effect of fuel switching capabilities.

The paper is outlined as follows: Section 2 presents the proposed model to identify critical GFPPs. Section 3 briefly describes the case study and scenarios, while Section 4 analyses the results for a range of scenarios. Section 5 duly draws some concluding remarks.

2 Proposed modelling approach

2.1 Standard joint power and gas dispatch

We adopt a day-ahead optimisation approach with hourly time steps for modelling a coupled gas and electricity system. The proposed mathematical model follows the standard electricity and gas optimal dispatch with power plant unit commitment restrictions. It can be expressed as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g, \mathbf{v}} f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v}) + f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g) \quad (1a)$$

subject to:

$$\mathbf{h}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v}) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1b)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^g(\mathbf{x}^g) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1c)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^{e-g}(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g) \leq \mathbf{0}, \quad (1d)$$

wherein \mathbf{x}^e and \mathbf{x}^g are vectors of continuous dispatching variables associated with the electricity and natural gas systems, respectively; \mathbf{v} is a vector of binary scheduling variables; $f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$ and $f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$ are the respective cost functions of the electricity and natural gas systems, which include the cost associated with the electricity not-served (ENS) and gas not-served (GNS); $\mathbf{h}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$ and $\mathbf{h}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$ are constrained functions associated with the electricity and natural gas systems; and $\mathbf{h}^{e-g}(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{x}^g)$ is a constrained function representing the coupling between the electricity and natural gas networks [15].

The *electricity system* is modelled as a unit commitment problem driven by the minimization of operation cost $f_{cost}^e(\mathbf{x}^e, \mathbf{v})$, while respecting the load-generation nodal balance and generation operational limits. Thus, the set of equations pertaining to the electricity system captures the operational, technical, and economic constraints as represented by (1b). We adopt a DC load flow model for modelling the electricity grid flows and also account for transmission line capacity limits. The generation scheduling constraints model ramp rates, minimum up and down times, start-ups, production limits, and binary scheduling decisions, as in [16].

The *natural gas system* is characterised by a mass-flow steady-state model, driven by the minimization of operation cost $f_{cost}^g(\mathbf{x}^g)$, while respecting operational and technical constraints, as represented by (1c). These constraints include the gas volume nodal balance, pipeline transport, maximum production limits, and other constraints such as gas storage chronological constraints. The interested reader is referred to [15] for an example of a gas system formulation.

The *gas-electricity coupling* is primarily defined by the dependency of the power system on gas. This relationship links the gas offtake for electricity production to the corresponding GFPP and is represented by constraints (1d).

Next, we extend the standard gas-electricity coupling, specifically gas consumption for electricity, by including a new set of equations. These equations capture the fuel-switching capabilities for some GFPPs and the gas-electricity linkage concerning household consumption, alongside the modelling of critical GFPPs.

2.2 Extended formulation for critical GFPP identification

For the identification of critical GFPP, it is important to have a complete representation of the main coupling links between gas and electricity systems. Apart from the gas-for-electricity (1d) connection between both systems, there are another two important linkages that are typically overlooked, or not addressed deeply, in the literature: fuel switching and gas-electricity for critical residential customers.

2.2.1 Fuel switching

A gas-fired generator may be equipped with fuel-switching capabilities and may use the backup fuel in an emergency situation. If the power plant located at bus i has access to backup fuel, the set of equations (2) represents its fuel-switching capabilities. Although fuel switching has no direct coupling with electricity system variables, the gas or alternative fuel availability impact directly to the final way of producing electricity.

$$0 \leq q_{it}^g \leq \bar{q}_{it}^g(1 - w_{it}), \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (2a)$$

$$q_{it}^b w_{it} \leq q_{it}^b \leq \bar{q}_{it}^b w_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (2b)$$

$$0 \leq \sum_{t \in T} q_{it}^b \leq \bar{Q}_i^b, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}. \quad (2c)$$

For modelling fuel-switching (FS) capabilities, we define a binary variable w_{it} in the domain of GFPP that has fuel-switching capabilities, I^{FS} . The variable $w_{it} = 0$ if the GFPP i is using gas in period t , and $w_{it} = 1$ if it is using backup fuel. Thus, the constraint (2a) states that the natural gas offtake of GFPP i , q_{it}^g , is zero if $w_{it} = 1$. However, if $w_{it} = 0$ the GFPP can use any value of volume of gas³ between 0 and \bar{q}_{it}^g . Similarly to constraint (2a), the equation (2b) forces the backup fuel offtake of GFPP i , q_{it}^b to be zero if $w_{it} = 0$. However, if $w_{it} = 1$, the backup fuel offtake is forced to be between a lower and upper limit. Finally, constraint (2c) models the limits of the total available backup fuel for the whole period of study. The backup fuel is typically limited because there are stocks on-site for emergency situations. We also need to modify accordingly gas cost function $f_{cost}^g(x^g)$ to include the binary nature of GFPP with fuel-switching capabilities using the binary variable w_{it} .

2.2.2 Gas-electricity for residential customers

We include constraints for modelling the reliance of the gas residential consumers on electricity. A certain share of households may not be able to use the natural gas in case of a blackout because their gas meters require electricity. To model it, we can include the following constraint linking the electricity and gas residential demand in a specific region:

$$\frac{GNS_{rt}^{resid}}{GD_{rt}^{resid}} \geq \gamma \frac{ENS_{rt}^{resid}}{ED_{rt}^{resid}}, \quad \forall r \in R, \forall t \in T, \quad (3)$$

where R is the set of regions; T is the set of time periods; GNS_{rt}^{resid} and ENS_{rt}^{resid} are the residential GNS and ENS in region r and time period t , respectively; GD_{rt}^{resid} and ED_{rt}^{resid} are the residential gas and electricity demand, respectively; and γ is the factor coupling non-served residential gas and electricity.

Equation (3) imposes a lower bound on the residential gas demand not served, when the electric load shedding is greater than 0, thus linking the gas and electricity demand of residential consumers.

2.2.3 Ranking critical GFPPs

We define the k critical GFPPs as the ones leading to the smallest economic consequences [17]. In other words, the gas and electricity dispatch cost as well as the cost related with the GNS and ENS is minimized while only the k critical GFPPs are supplied. We can model it by solving (1)-(3) and adding specific constraints to select the k -best GFPP (4).

$$\sum_{i \in I} u_{it} \leq k, \quad \forall t \in T \quad (4a)$$

$$v_{it} \leq u_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{NFS}, \forall t \in T \quad (4b)$$

$$v_{it} \leq u_{it} + w_{it}, \quad \forall i \in I^{FS}, \forall t \in T \quad (4c)$$

$$0 \leq u_{it} \leq 1, \quad \forall i \in I, \forall t \in T. \quad (4d)$$

(³) The upper bound limit represent a big-M and not an actual technical limit. It is in general, a value larger than the intake gas capacity that the GFPP i can have from the main gas network.

A continuous auxiliary variable⁴ per GFPP i and period t is introduced, u_{it} , (4d). When $u_{it} = 1$, the GFPP i is considered to be critical, otherwise $u_{it} = 0$.

Equation (4a) sets that the total number of GFPPs that can be identified as critical at each time period are at the maximum k , which is a user-defined value. For example, if interested in the single most critical plant, k must be set to 1. Equation (4b) enforces GFPP i to be offline, i.e. $v_{it} = 0$, when the auxiliary variable u_{it} is 0. This equation is defined for the set of GFPP that has no fuel-switching (NFS) capabilities. For the rest of GFPP with switching capabilities, we add (4d) that additionally accounts if the GFPP i is running on natural gas, i.e. $w_{it} = 0$, or backup fuel, i.e. $w_{it} = 1$.

3 Case study

3.1 Data and simulation setup

We apply the proposed model to the updated IEEE Three-Area RTS (hereinafter referred to as RTS-GMLC system) [18]. We have created a stylized gas system comprising only three gas nodes to showcase the proposed methodology. Even though the gas topology is rather small, the main drivers for the identification of critical GFPPs can be adequately discussed.

The electricity network for the RTS-GMLC system is made up of 73 buses and 121 branches in total. The system consists of three regions which are connected by five AC cross-border interconnectors and one DC link. In turn, each region is divided into two zones (e.g. region 3 has zones 31 and 32). The zones 11, 21, and 31 are predominantly consumption areas (lower voltage) whereas most of the production facilities are located in zones 12, 22, and 32 (higher voltage).

There are 10 gas-fired combined cycle (CC) generators with an installed capacity of 355 MW each, and 27 natural gas-fired combustion turbines (CT) generators with an individual installed capacity of 55 MW, which are located among 19 buses. The total capacity amounts to 1095 MW, 1560 MW, 2380 MW, for regions 1, 2, and 3, respectively. The highest installed capacity can be found at bus 323 in region 3⁵.

Finally, we have selected the simulation period 24-30 August of a representative year because the electricity peak demand hour occurs on 26 August at 3 pm. The total electricity demand for that week is 926.8 GWh: 308.8 GWh in region 1, 321.9 GWh in region 2, and 296.2 GWh in region 3. The electricity system is further described in [19].

For the sake of simplicity, we have adopted a three-node gas network⁶ which is made up of three gas nodes, three gas pipelines, and two gas production facilities located at gas nodes 2 and 3, as can be seen in **Figure 1**. In each gas node, there is a “conventional” gas demand that can be itemised by industrial, commercial, and residential consumption. Moreover, the demand for electricity production is linked to the GFPPs of the corresponding region. We also assume that there are neither underground gas storage nor liquefied natural gas facilities.

The production cost of the gas production facilities at nodes 2 and 3 is assumed to be 34.1 and 17.1 \$/MWh, respectively, whereas their maximum production per hour is set to 2.9 and 4.4 GWh. We assume that the available gas volume in the production facilities is unlimited.

There are three pipelines connecting the gas nodes, labelled 2-1, 3-1, and 3-2. The gas flow direction is endogenously defined in the notation, e.g. the gas in pipeline 2-1 flows from gas node 2 to gas node 1. Bidirectional flows are neglected in this illustrative example. We also assume that the maximum amount of gas that can be stored (linepack) in pipelines 3-1 and 3-2 is 1.5 GWh whereas for pipeline 2-1 it is limited to 0.3 GWh. We set the maximum flow to 1.5 GWh/h. In this gas system, node 3 cannot use any gas from other gas nodes in case of need, which may cause bottlenecks in some cases.

(⁴) Note that the equations (4a)-(4c) has integer coefficients and the variables, other than u_{it} , are binary. Thus, u_{it} can take only 0 or 1 values without the need to define it as binary.

(⁵) The technical characteristics of conventional generators (heat rate curve, start and shutdown costs, minimum stable level, and minimum up and down times can be found in <https://github.com/GridMod/RTS-GMLC>.

(⁶) The purpose of the data shown in this example is to showcase the proposed methodology and, under any circumstance, these data should be taken as reference values for real-world gas networks.

Figure 1. Joint electricity and natural gas network for the RTS-GMLC system.

Source: JRC, 2024.

The simulation period spans from 24 August until 30 August. The conventional gas demand in that period amounts to 174.1 GWh, of which 20% correspond to commercial consumption, 20% to industrial consumption, and 60% to households.

The supply of gas for electricity production and households is prioritised over commercial and industrial customers. Moreover, supply of gas to commercial customers is prioritised over industrial ones.

3.2 Scenarios

We analyse the following scenarios:

- Scenario 0 (SC 0): This scenario represents the results for a reference (SC 0.a) and a congested case (SC 0.b) when the gas network is neglected. In the congested case, cross-border line capacities among the three regions are reduced to half of the original values and the capacity of inter-zonal lines are reduced to 100 MW. The model is made of constraints (1a)–(1b) and (4a)–(4b), (4d).
- Scenarios 1-2 (SC 1–SC 2): These scenarios discuss the results for a reference (SC 1) and a congested case (SC 2), as described in SC 0. These scenarios account for the operation of the natural gas network. We assume a 70% reduction of gas production capacity. In other words, we set the maximum production levels of gas production facilities at gas nodes 2 and 3 to 0.88 and 1.32 GWh, in that order. The core model is (1), (4a)–(4b), (4d). In turn, we consider the following variants:
 - Case 1.a: Reference case and $k = 0$, i.e. there is no gas available for electricity production. Gas is only consumed by conventional consumers.
 - Case 1.b: Reference case and $k = 1$, i.e. only the most critical GFPP is identified each period.
 - Case 1.c: Reference case without including the constraints (4a)–(4b), (4d).
 - Case 2.a: Congested case and $k = 0$.
 - Case 2.b: Congested case and $k = 1$.
 - Case 2.c: Congested case without including the constraints (4a)–(4b), (4d).
- Scenarios 3-4 (SC 3–SC 4): Scenarios 1 and 2 account only for the dependence of the electricity system on the natural gas system, so the electricity system does not have any effect on the gas network. For instance, the model in SC 1–SC 2 ignores the fact that some households could not even use the natural gas in the case

of an electricity blackout. Therefore, SC 3–SC 4 extend the model in SC 1–SC 2 to include constraints (3), modelling the dependence of gas consumption of households on electricity for both the reference and the congested cases, in that order. To do that, we assume that all electric loads in zones 11, 21, and 31 belong to households. As similarly done in SC 1–SC 2, we assume a 70% reduction of gas production.

- Scenario 5 (SC 5): This scenario analyses the effect of fuel-switching capabilities in the identification of critical GFPPs. We impose fuel-switching capabilities to the GFPPs located at bus 213. In this scenario, the model is (1)–(4). We assume that the backup fuel is light oil, its price is 30.5 \$/MWh, and the maximum backup fuel offtake per hour is set to 1.5 GWh. This maximum limit does not impose any constraint in the formulation since the fuel offtake for the GFPPs located at bus 213 when working at full capacity is equal to 1.1 GWh per hour. Four different cases are then analysed:
 - Case 5.a: Reference case, $k = 1$, and 73.3 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.b: Reference case, $k = 1$, and 146.5 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.c: Congested case, $k = 1$, and 73.3 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.
 - Case 5.d: Congested case, $k = 1$, and 146.5 GWh of maximum backup fuel offtake per week.

4 Results and discussion

We build the coupled gas and electricity model in Plexos 8.1. We run a day-ahead optimisation for the week 24–30 August by considering hourly time steps and a 4-hour look-ahead window. The resulting model is run with the solver Xpress-MP 34.01.03 by using an optimality gap equal to 0.1%.

4.1 Scenarios 0-2: Impact of the natural gas network

We analyse two cases: reference (SC 1) and congested (SC 2). Without any gas shortage, the reference case can fulfil both electricity and gas demand. However, the congested case leads to an ENS equal to 11.6 GWh (around 1.3% of the total electricity demand) and dumped energy equal to 0.2% of the total electricity generation due to the constraints imposed by the natural gas network. More specifically, the ENS in zones 11, 21, and 31 is equal to 1.5, 8.2, and 1.8 GWh, respectively.

Table 1 shows the critical GFPPs identified in cases 1.b and 2.b, i.e. when at most one critical GFPP can be identified per time period ($k = 1$). We rank the critical GFPPs based on the number of operating hours that GFPPs have been scheduled on during the optimisation horizon. Note that cases 1.a and 2.a represent the worst-case events in which no GFPP would be operational, thus no identification of critical GFPPs takes place for these cases. Cases 1.c and 2.c are less stringent than cases 1.b and 2.b because the set of constraints (4a)–(4b), (4d) to identify critical GFPPs are no longer imposed. In these cases, any GFPP can be used at any time with the goal of minimising the electricity and gas not served while respecting the technical and operational constraints. Hence, these cases would provide per se an optimal ranking and dispatch of critical GFPPs.

Table 1 also includes the results for cases 0.a and 0.b, which correspond to the reference and congested cases when the gas network is neglected. We first compare the results for the reference case (case 0.a versus case 1.b). We can observe that the critical GFPPs shift from the ones at bus 323 to the ones at bus 213. The reason of this change relies on the underlying assumption made in SC 0, in which we assume that the critical GFPPs could make use of the gas without any restriction. In scenarios 1–4, the available gas is constrained by the operational limitations of the gas production facilities. Another reason for such a shift are the technical constraints of the generating units located at those buses. Two 355 MW GFPPs are located at bus 323 with a minimum stable level of 170 MW and a minimum up time of 8 h. In bus 213, there are two 55 MW GFPPs with a minimum stable level of 22 MW and a minimum up time of 2 h, and one 355 MW GFPP with a minimum stable level of 170 MW and a minimum up time equal to 8 h. Clearly, some GFPP units at node 213 are more flexible than those at node 323. Therefore, prioritising the GFPPs at bus 213 would decrease the gas used for electricity production and more gas could be devoted to satisfying the conventional gas demand. In fact, the natural gas offtake for electricity production is 212.6 GWh for the whole week in case 0.a (98% of the gas is consumed by the GFPPs at bus 323), whereas the gas offtake for electricity production decreases to 146.6 GWh in case 1.b (only 18% is consumed by the GFPPs located at bus 323). This comes at expense of increasing the ENS by 23%. In the congested case (case 0.b versus case 2.b), the top four critical GFPPs are identical in both cases and there are only slight differences in their commitment.

Table 1. Critical GFPPs identified in scenarios 0-4 for both reference and congested cases when $k = 1$.

Case 0.a		Case 0.b		Case 1.b		Case 2.b		Case 3.b		Case 4.b	
Reference		Congested		Reference		Congested		Reference		Congested	
ENS = 75.4 GWh		ENS = 129.7 GWh		ENS = 92.9 GWh GNS = 1.8 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 131.5 GWh GNS = 1.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 93.0 GWh GNS = 2.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 146.0 GWh GNS = 12.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 12.5 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
323	156	107	84	213	126	107	72	213	113	107	65
213	8	213	39	323	24	213	51	323	46	213	56
		323	31			323	23			313	47
		313	14			313	14				
						321	8				

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Figure 2. Electricity and gas not served - Reference (SC 1) and congested (SC 2) cases.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Figure 2 (left plot) shows the ENS in each zone of the electricity system for all cases. In this figure, the pink-coloured bars correspond to the distribution zones wherein we have assumed that all residential consumers are located. **Figure 2** (right plot) shows the GNS for all conventional gas consumers. First, we can observe that the total ENS decreases when k increases, i.e. when moving from cases a to c , whereas the GNS for industrial and commercial consumers increases because the gas devoted to electricity production is prioritised. Scenarios 1 and 2 always lead to ENS in zones 11, 21, and 31 where the households are located, whose gas consumption is supplied first. However, this may not be realistic because some households need electricity to operate their appliances, despite the fact that **Figure 2** shows no GNS for those consumers in scenarios 1 and 2.

4.2 Scenarios 3-4: Impact of the reliance of residential gas consumers on electricity

Scenarios 3 and 4 illustrate the impact of including constraints (3) into the problem formulation, i.e. some households cannot consume gas without electricity. **Table 1** reports the critical GFPPs for these scenarios when $k = 1$, whereas **Figure 3** shows the ENS and GNS for scenarios 3 and 4. In the reference case (SC 3), the total ENS and GNS are essentially the same as the ones resulting from scenario 1. Interestingly, there is no residential ENS (neither electricity nor gas) in cases 3.a-3.c. The constraints (3) enforce a new dispatch and commitment

solution thanks to the spare transmission capacity in the electricity network. Regarding critical GFPPs, the identified power plants in case 3.b are the same as in case 1.b, as can be seen in **Table 1**.

On the other hand, in the congested case (SC 4), the transmission congestion causes an unavoidable load shedding in the electricity system. In the three cases (4.a-4.c) of **Figure 3**, we can also observe gas shortage in households due to the linkage between the electricity and gas consumers modelled by the constraints (3). As expected, the residential ENS (i.e. the loads located in zones 11, 21, and 31) decreases by 43%, 49% and 57% in cases 4.a-4.c with respect to cases 2.a-2.c, respectively. However, the total ENS increases by 6%, 11%, and 6% in cases 4.a-4.c, respectively. Finally, the critical GFPPs in case 4.b are included in the set of critical GFPPs identified in case 2.b. In order to satisfy the ENS at the zones where residential consumers are located, the GFPPs at buses 321 and 323 are no longer critical in case 4.b, thus increasing the number of operating hours for the other GFPPs.

Figure 3. Electricity and gas not served - Reference (SC 3) and congested (SC 4) cases.

Source: JRC, 2024.

4.3 Scenario 5: Impact of fuel-switching capabilities

The results from cases 5.a-5.b are compared with those obtained in case 3.b in order to analyse the impact of the fuel-switching capabilities in the GFPPs located at bus 213 in the reference case. **Table 2** shows the ENS, GNS, and the residential GNS for each of the cases, along with the ranking of critical GFPPs. In case 3.b, the critical GFPPs are the ones at bus 213 followed by the ones at bus 323. The gas offtake for electricity production amounts to 153.2 GWh and 71.8% of the total gas offtake is supplied to region 2. This solution leads to an ENS equal to 93 GWh and a gas shortage of 2 GWh.

When the GFPPs at bus 213 are equipped with fuel-switching capabilities, the results are substantially different in terms of ENS and criticality. In case 5.a, we can observe that the GFPPs at bus 213 are no longer critical. Note that the formulation may still choose the GFPPs as critical provided that their fuel-switching capabilities are deemed insufficient. Instead, the GFPPs at bus 323 are identified as critical followed by the ones located at buses 221 and 313, in that order. The backup fuel offtake is equal to 73.3 GWh, i.e. GFPPs at bus 213 use their full inventory with the goal of minimising the ENS while satisfying the technical and economic constraints. In this case, the natural gas offtake for electricity production decreases by 10.7% compared to case 3.b (i.e. to 136.9 GWh). In addition, the ENS decreases by 32.3%, but the GNS increases from 2.0 to 12.8 GWh. The reason for this increase in the GNS relies essentially on the change of the critical GFPP which causes 95% of the gas offtake for electricity production being supplied to region 3 (in case 3.b most of the gas goes to region 2). The gas of the production facility at the gas node 3 is mainly used to satisfy the residential gas demand and the demand for electricity production. Since the gas cannot flow from gas nodes 1 and 2 towards gas node 3, the industrial and commercial gas demands are curtailed, thus increasing the gas shortage. From the results, we can infer that

having fuel-switching capabilities in the GFPPs at bus 213 may not be the best strategy to minimise the total energy not served of the integrated system because of the increase in the GNS.

Table 2. Critical GFPPs identified in cases 3.b (without fuel-switching capabilities), 5.a and 5.b (both with GFPPs at bus 213 with fuel-switching capabilities) for the reference case.

Case 3.b		Case 5.a		Case 5.b	
ENS = 93.0 GWh GNS = 2.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 63.0 GWh GNS = 12.8 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh		ENS = 59.5 GWh GNS = 10.1 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 0 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
213	113	323	137	323	122
323	46	221	10	107	14
		318	8	221	10
				207	3

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

Expectedly, the increase of backup fuel inventory in case 5.b allows for a further reduction of the ENS and GNS. Similar to case 5.a, the critical GFPPs are located at bus 323 for most of the analysed period. The backup fuel offtake increases to 125.7 GWh and the gas offtake for electricity production decreases to 121.7 GWh. Although 88% of the total gas offtake is still supplied to region 3, the absolute gas offtake is lower than the one in case 5.a. Hence, the gas shortage decreases by 21.4% compared to case 5.a and the ENS by 5.6%.

Table 3 compares the results from case 5.c-5.d with those of case 4.b, i.e. without fuel-switching capabilities. In the congested case without any backup fuel, the critical GFPP is located in the first region (at bus 107) followed by the GFPPs at bus 213. The natural gas offtake for electricity production amounts to 105.2 GWh and now the gas offtake is not predominant in any of the three regions. As can be seen, the ENS is 146.0 GWh and the GNS (residential only) is equal to 12.5 GWh.

Table 3. Critical GFPPs identified in cases 4.b (without fuel-switching capabilities), 5.c and 5.d (both with GFPPs at bus 213 with fuel-switching capabilities) for the congested case.

Case 4.b		Case 5.c		Case 5.d	
ENS = 146.0 GWh GNS = 12.5 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 12.5 GWh		ENS = 119.0 GWh GNS = 10.7 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 10.7 GWh		ENS = 108.7 GWh GNS = 11.0 GWh GNS ^{resid} = 11.0 GWh	
Ranking	# hours ⁽¹⁾	Ranking	# hours	Ranking	# hours
107	65	107	111	107	105
213	56	313	45	313	42
313	47	207	8	207	12
		307	3	113, 213, 307	3

⁽¹⁾ The number of hours refers to the hourly time periods that the gas-fired power plant is scheduled on for the simulation period.

Source: JRC, 2024.

The critical GFPP is still the one at bus 107 in cases 5.c and 5.d. However, since the GFPPs at bus 213 switch to backup fuel, more GFPPs come into play for a few hours in cases 5.c and 5.d. Although the critical GFPP remains unchanged, fuel-switching capabilities may help reduce the energy not served in the integrated system. Note that the ENS decreases by 19-26% while the residential GNS reduces also by 12-14% in both cases, unlike the situation observed in the reference case.

5 Conclusion

This paper proposes an optimisation model for an integrated natural gas and electricity system to identify and rank critical gas-fired power plants (GFPPs) in order to comply with Regulation (EU) No 2017/1938 on security of gas supply. The electricity system is modelled as a unit commitment and economic dispatch problem whereas the gas system is represented by a mass-flow steady-state model. Additional constraints allow to consider modelling aspects such as the reliance of gas consumers on electricity and fuel-switching capabilities of certain GFPPs.

Several conclusions can be drawn from the case study:

- Congestion in the electricity network plays a crucial role because the power plants identified as critical are not necessarily the ones with the highest installed capacity.
- The consideration of an integrated system may change the degree of criticality of the GFPPs since the gas network may impose additional constraints.
- The reliance of residential gas consumers (households) on electricity does not affect the identification of the main critical GFPPs in this case study, but the ranking of critical GFPPs may be different to help reduce the gas shortage of residential gas customers.
- Adding fuel-switching capabilities to critical GFPPs changes the designation of the critical GFPP and decreases the electricity not served of the power system. However, this may lead to an increase in the gas shortage of the natural gas system. Therefore, it is essential to carefully determine which GFPPs should be equipped with fuel-switching capabilities while accounting for an integrated natural gas and electricity system.

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Disclaimer

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Enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures through innovative pathways – The FIRELOGUE and STRATEGY projects approaches in emergency management

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Abstract

In cases of incidents impacting critical infrastructures, early notification and proper information sharing are vital for effective response and recovery. The EU 2557/2022 CER Directive outlines pathways to resilience, emphasizing the importance of coordinated efforts among Member States. The newly released CEN Workshop Agreement CWA 18024:2023 Emergency Management – Incident Situational Reporting for Critical Infrastructures provides a standardized approach for reporting incidents to national authorities, ensuring consistency and clarity in communication. Developed under the STRATEGY project, this CWA was rigorously tested in table-top and full-scale exercises with the participation of researchers, critical infrastructures operators and emergency responders. A pilot coordination center dedicated to critical infrastructures, utilizing a GIS-based platform from the Center for Security Studies (KEMEA) in Greece, facilitates seamless collaboration between critical entities and emergency responders during incidents that threaten the normal operation of these infrastructures. The (pre-) standardisation framework developed in STRATEGY was specifically designed to address the needs of emergency responders, ensuring that the CWA was tested across various scenarios to gain acceptance from a wide range of stakeholders. Moreover, in order to enhance situational awareness and to create a real-time common operational picture, an online incident reporting form, built on the CWA 18024:2023, has been integrated within the pilot coordination center. Undoubtedly, and during the tests, incident management was greatly improved leading to enhanced resilience of critical infrastructures. The FIRELOGUE workshops in 2023 (Solsona, Spain) and 2024 (Nea Makri, Greece) highlighted the critical role of technology in managing wildfires and their impact on infrastructures. Applications offering early warnings, fire ignition probabilities, and burnt area calculations are crucial for infrastructure operators and emergency responders. By combining data from various sources into a single, cohesive platform enhances the information's utility and management, allowing for more informed decision-making. Moreover, adherence to legislation and regulations is crucial for resilient infrastructures. The implementation of EU Directives not only strengthens resilience but also fosters a culture of preparedness and proactive risk management. In conclusion, effective incident management and collaboration are essential for the resilience of critical infrastructures. The integration of standardised reporting systems and technological advancements play a pivotal role in enhancing preparedness and response capabilities, ultimately safeguarding public safety and ensuring the continuity of essential services.

1. Introduction

Critical entities and their infrastructures are one of the key pillars of modern societies providing a broad spectrum of services to the population, from basic necessities such as access to clean water, electricity, telecommunication and heat to every household up to more sophisticated offerings like financial services, extremely fast internet services, cybersecurity, health services and other.

The European Union in an effort to enhance the resilience of infrastructures and make sure to provide a safe environment for their citizens, published out and put into act the Critical Entities Resilience Directive [1] and the NIS 2 Directive [2]. The Council CER Directive [1] broadens the concept of infrastructure by introducing the term “entity”, and by including more types of infrastructures (i.e., banking, financial services, health services, drinking water and water related services, digital infrastructures, production and distribution of food), besides the energy and transport sectors, compared to the previous Directive 114/2008 [3]. More precisely, it mandates a series of actions from the Member States to be implemented, such as, conducting risk assessment, continuous monitoring of the infrastructures, in real-time if possible, incident reporting, continuous

collaboration and communication between infrastructures and state authorities. This will be achieved by each Member State by enlisting all their infrastructures that are compatible with the CER Directive [1] and by appointing a national contact point. The national contact point will be responsible to identify the national critical entities and will consist of the national authority that will perform all the functions and activities foreseen by the Directive in collaboration with all the necessary state authorities and other entities. As a follow up from this, STRATEGY project focused on addressing the requirements of critical entities and the authorities and developed the CWA 18024:2023 – Emergency management – Incident situational report [4].

Thus, a new era has begun in the critical infrastructure domain, which requires a continuous and close collaboration between all stakeholders and exchange of improved data in order to provide safe and secure services to the citizens. Unexpected events and/or incidents may be often inevitable, however the aim is to try to mitigate their impacts and limit the disruption of the service offered. Climate change can currently lead to extreme weather events and extreme and more frequent wildfires which may cause significant impact to the infrastructures. Other disruptive event, for which anticipation is necessary, is floods, which is a major threat for Europe, or the case of large earthquakes which occurrence is unavoidable.

In recent years, a significant attention has been given on wildfires, which is a typical threat for Southern Europe (Mediterranean countries) and emerging as a new concern for Central and Northern Europe. Moreover, extreme fire events, despite the reduction in the number of fires, occur more and more frequently in Southern Europe, with larger burnt areas, fast spread rates, high intensities, and megafires (e.g., [5]). EU under the Green Deal initiative has funded four Innovation Actions aimed to tackle wildfire challenges promoting an integrated approach and already the first results come up (e.g., [6], [7]).

Critical infrastructures play a crucial role in wildfire risk management, as they can act either as a triggering or ignition factor or as a suppression mechanism. The FIRELOGUE project and specifically the Infrastructure Working Group [8], which is a fundamental part of the project, is dealing with this issue.

2. Needs and challenges related to critical infrastructures and entities resilience

2.1 Enhancing crisis management in critical infrastructures through standardization - Insights from the STRATEGY project

A standard is a “document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context” [9]. The development of a standard consists of an open and ongoing procedure that incorporates the views, scientific and practical experience of subject matter experts. Critical infrastructures at national, even European and international level, benefit greatly of available standards, being part or not of the legal framework, due to their interconnected nature and services offered. In particular, crisis management within an infrastructure or disaster management at wider level when critical entities are involved, require the implementation of standardized actions and tools that facilitate cross-border and cross-organizational collaboration.

STRATEGY project developed a comprehensive, cross-European framework for pre-standardization activities related to systems, solutions, and procedures. This framework addresses crisis management and has been validated through the use of sustainable testing and evaluation frameworks. The overarching objective of the project, through the development and implementation of the pre-standardization activities, is to enhance the resilience of the EU in the face of a multitude of natural and man-made disasters through the assurance of first responder (FR) safety and the fortification of their operational capacity. In response to the identified needs of previous EU initiatives and the findings of the desktop research on EU priorities, the project addresses eight streams within the domain of crisis management. The following areas have been identified as requiring further attention: Search and Rescue, Critical Infrastructure Protection, Response Planning, Command and Control, Early Warning Systems and Rapid Damage Assessment, CBRN-E, Training and Terminology.

The STRATEGY project following a desk research analysis on existing needs, challenges and gaps of emergency responders and practitioners, in the eight thematic topics stated previously, identified approximately 100

standardisation gaps on the field of crisis, and more specifically, on disaster management, among them being the protection of critical infrastructures ([10], [11]). The identified gaps in standardization related to critical infrastructures are the following:

- Definition of basic specifications and requirements for coordination centers of critical entities
- Specifications and requirements for equipment and space in coordination centres of CIs
- Standard DSS format of CI coordination centres.
- Standardised procedures for registration, authentication and authorisation of users in DSS and coordination centres systems.
- Post crisis needs assessment tools integrated to existing DSS.
- Interoperability between UAVs and DSS. Standardised data collection and mapping of UAVs, and transfer in the daily operations.
- Standardised intervention plans of first responders specifically for the CIP domain
- Processes and methods for dynamic risk evolution embedded in new and existing DSS (e.g., earthquake shaking, fire propagation, extreme weather forecasting). Requirements for standardized risk assessment modelling with an all-hazards approach, including climate change-related hazards.
- Standardised threat detection systems linked to DSS and coordination centres
- Cross-organisation interoperability with standardised data exchange formats, protocols and common SOPs, including security plans for interconnected CIs to enhance efficient information sharing and datasharing.

The analysis and discussions between practitioners, emergency responders and research partners of the project led to the development of two pre-standardisation items, two CEN Workshop Agreements:

- CWA 18024:2023 – Emergency management – Incident situational reporting for critical infrastructures [4].
- CWA 18028:2023 – Semantic layer definition and suitability of OASIS EDXL-CAP and OASIS EDXL-SitRep standards for crisis management in critical infrastructures [12].

These pre-standardisation items have been developed in collaboration with a broad spectrum of stakeholders and tested in one table-top (TTX) and one full-scale exercise (FSX) gathering feedback directly from the end users, i.e. the emergency responders the critical infrastructure operators, security liaison officers and all engaged stakeholders. The first one is discussed in more detail on chapter 3, as it consists of a new pre-standardisation item dedicated to support Member States in the implementation of the new EU CER Directive [1].

2.2 Enhancing Resilience: Integrated wildfire risk management and critical infrastructures protection

Wildfires, with increasing frequency and intensity, have become an event of major concern for policy makers and study focus of the scientific community. Recent disasters affecting critical infrastructures have provided evidence on the interdependencies between infrastructures, societal function and resilience in different dimensions (e.g. power outages in areas affected by wildfires and transport disruptions) [13]. Moreover, malfunctions in infrastructures can be a driving factor for wildfires, especially in the Wildland-Urban Interface (WUI) (e.g. powerlines causing wildfires). As a matter of fact, there is a mutual cause-effect relationship between wildfires and infrastructures, the understanding of which can lead to the adoption of efficient risk reduction measures and impactful actions:

- **Infrastructure as a driving factor in fire regime.** Infrastructure's malfunction, failure or misuse may lead to wildfire ignition. Prevention measures for the assets upgrade and/or vegetation management of the surrounding areas are deemed necessary. Additionally, the positive involvement of different infrastructures in wildfire management should be further exploited (e.g. role of road network as fire break).
- **Impact of wildfires to infrastructure.** Wildfires can adversely affect the operation of infrastructure assets and networks exposed due to their geographic location, causing disruption of the service provided. This tendency has increased due to the expansion of human settlements and industrial activity into the wildland.
- **Cross-cutting topics** are also evident, such as (i) the nature-based solutions infrastructures may adopt for their protection against wildfires; (ii) the necessary societal awareness and preparedness in case of an emergency caused by service disruption; (iii) the insurance claims in case of an infrastructure-ignited fire and vice versa; (iv) the role of civil protection agencies in ensuring resilience planning and emergency training on behalf of critical infrastructure operators, (v) climate change projections and EU climate change adaptation policies regarding infrastructures and WFRM.

In this respect, the working group Infrastructure of FIRELOGUE project generated insights and recommendations on the abovementioned topics, lying under the overarching theme of the interaction of infrastructure with its surrounding natural environment and their exposure to wildfires. The FIRELOGUE project is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) granted under the Horizon 2020 Green Deal programme (H2020-LC-GD-1-1) on preventing and managing extreme wildfire events through the integration and demonstration of innovative tools and means [8]. The objective of the project is to facilitate a discourse and empower the Wildfire Risk Management (WFRM) community to address both current and future wildfire challenges. FIRELOGUE brings together various types of stakeholders in order to discuss and improve WFRM. It is structured into five working groups focused on: i) the environment, ii) society, iii) infrastructures, iv) insurance and v) civil protection, which allow discussions across four thematic strands: socio-economic, climate change mitigation, technology and earth observation, in order to promote policies that support wildfire risk management.

FIRELOGUE examines the co-existence of wildfires and critical infrastructures in a participatory method and a dialogue between the various engaged stakeholders. Following a series of extended experts discussions, it has been pointed out there is a need to follow a more integrated approach with a stronger collaboration between involved stakeholders and improved data exchange. A lack in risk assessment is evident as in the use of modern technologies, while a prioritization towards research is necessary. Strengthening of infrastructures against wildfires is also necessary [14].

The preliminary recommendations findings [14] of the dialogue that Firelogue are focused on the collaboration and coordination among the governmental agencies, private sector and communities; enhancing the collaboration among infrastructures, improved data sharing, support training, invest more in research and technology, conduct risk assessment following the mandates of the CER directive, move towards real-time estimations, implement risk management at various levels, considering the landscape, enhance standardisation and implement a cultural change towards prevention, mitigation and preparedness, engaging the community.

It has to be noted that these recommendations do not simply represent wildfire risk management issues related to critical infrastructures. Instead, some of these must be considered as recommendations to improve the emergency management system which accounts for various risk types (natural and man-made) and not only wildfire prevention, response and recovery.

3. Enhancing incident situational reporting: A pre-standard for critical infrastructures supporting the implementation of the CER Directive

3.1 The CWA 18024:2023 – Brief overview

The CER Directive [1] through its 15th article mandates all Member States to ensure that all critical entities notify on time, without undue delay, and the latest, no later than 24 hours, the competent authority of incidents that disrupt significantly the provision of essential services. Moreover, CER Directive [1] asks for a detailed report, submitted no later than one month after the incident. In addition, the minimum incident notification should include information about the number and proportion of users affected, the duration of the disruption, and the geographical area affected. Finally, the CER directive [1] asks for the notification of the Commission in case the incident has an impact on six or more Member States.

CWA 18024:2023 [4] is a CEN Workshop Agreement document that provides a common set of information, terms and datatypes as requirements and recommendations that should be made available to a national, local or European coordination centre, control room, contact point or any competent authority, by any affected critical infrastructure in case of an incident. It consists of a set of information that mainly targets the higher command levels, at strategic and operational level [15] but not aimed at the tactical forces on the scene. This set of requirements and recommendations can fully support Member States in the implementation of the EU CER Directive, being compatible with the “Article 15 – Incident notification”.

The information that is requested to be filled in by the user is categorised in four main pillars:

- the identification of the user and the incident,
- the description of the incident, in simple words structured description of what happened,
- the characterization of the impacts and the risk in a structured way,
- additional information about the actions in place and resources needed to face the incident and restore the service.

Practically, the pre-standard is structured in a way that provides to coordination centres all the necessary information to estimate the current situation, provide the future evolution of the incident and help them to understand what resources may be needed. This is done in a sequence, and it is assumed that at least four types of reports exist: the initial report, an update, a final report and a cancellation report, indicating the closing of the emergency. The CWA has been built in such a way to take into account technological systems, meaning that its implementation facilitates the use of technological system, and it can be used in a typical paper format or a modern technological system.

All the information requested by the CER directive has been covered, as the user preparing the report, i.e., the critical infrastructure operator, can provide information about themselves, the incident, the geographical area, in the form of geographical coordinates with a polygon, access to the area, details on the incident, the impacts, the restoration time objective, the number of people expected to be affected, what actions have been made or will be made and what potential resources may be needed. The end user has the freedom to fill in any information and update it at any time it is necessary to do so, and they are instructed always to provide the best possible estimation. Nevertheless, at the final report, the recommendation is to provide the real numbers and not estimations.

Thus, the proposed standardized incident reporting form facilitates the collaboration between critical entities and emergency response services, it provides an enhanced situational awareness and common operational picture, and a common language to the involved stakeholders in an easy-to-understand and -to-use format. Moreover, it can be employed by competent authorities to create statistics, as it can be used for any type of incident, of higher or lower severity, natural or man-made, for any type of infrastructure including infrastructure in the food and feed sector and help on future improvements. Finally, it is compatible with other similar standards used outside Europe such as the [16] in UK, the [17] and the [18].

3.2 Collaborative validation at operational level using modern technological applications

The CWA 18024:2023 [4] was developed in collaboration with the end-users, emergency responders and critical infrastructure operators, with their active participation, not only for the development of the document, but also during table-top and full-scale exercises. The latter activities, i.e. the exercises were the main validation tool of the under-development standards in the framework of STRATEGY project. An innovative, end-user driven pre-standardization framework that facilitated the development of new standards in crisis management domain, or the improvement of existing ones was developed in STRATEGY.

It was tested in one TTX that was organized at the premises of Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), in Athens, Greece in June 2022 and a FSX and demonstration, as part of a larger scenario, that took place in the area of Gualdo-Tadino and Valfabbrica in Italy (March 2023). These exercises were not used for training of the involved personnel, although they facilitate such purpose, but to test the standards, to evaluate and validate whether the standards can fit to existing operational procedures and meet the needs of FRs. In these two exercises, the CWA [4] was tested in different scenarios with the use of modern technological systems. The implementation of the exercises was based upon the eExercise Guidance Method - XGM framework [19] developed in the STRATEGY project. XGM is a reference framework on conducting exercises for standards and it is based on the Trial Guidance Methodology-TGM [20]. Thus, for each exercise, at least one person was assigned for each of the following roles: the exercise manager, the problem owner, the research leader, the host and the technical support leader.

In the first case, the TTX, both natural and man-made independent events were selected without an escalation difficulty as this was the first real test with the end users. The tests included three different incidents affecting critical infrastructures, one large earthquake affecting a metropolitan area with the focus given on the damage of a main natural gas pipeline, the second event included a man-made incident, an emergency landing of an airplane that ended to be a hijack and the third episode was related to an overturn of a truck carrying hazardous chemical materials along a main highway.

The FSX was based on two different scenarios, the first one was related to an earthquake and the collapse of a nearby dam (scenario A), and the second one was related to a wildland urban interface fire (scenario B), testing in total 14 standardization items (CEN Workshop Agreements and Technical Specifications). CWA 18024:2023 [4] was tested with the first scenario. A large earthquake occurred in the location area hitting a water reservoir. The reservoir even though was designed to withstand a large earthquake, a new section being under test load was affected, leading to its partial collapse, generating a water wave that escaped the overflow channel and poured into the riverbed. The nearby highway was flooded as well as a stadium full of people. During the exercise, in the command centre, the end users (emergency responders and civil protection authorities) were receiving the various relevant information, through the incident form which was filled in by the local infrastructure operators.

The infrastructure operators with the use of an online form built in ArcGIS Survey 123, which is an online representation of the [4], reported the incident to the command centre and the national competent authority (Figure 1). The report is being translated into a web-GIS environment and the same picture is shared among all involved stakeholders.

Figure 1. Left: online form for incident reporting according to CWA 18024:2023 [4]. Right: Indicative screenshot for the

KEMEA risk application and incident report built for the full-scale exercise that was carried out in Italy.

Source: Left: <https://survey123.arcgis.com/share/35a360a8d90249a998ea59997867e0db>. Right: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

The use of modern Geographic Information Systems (GIS) allows all the necessary information to be translated into a map view, thus making it easier to communicate and understand the information. Moreover, during both exercises, besides the testing of the pre-standardisation items, the integration and interoperability of various systems was also examined and tested. In Figure 2, the technical setup and the integration of the various technological systems is also presented, from the end user online form and front end to the KEMEA's ArcGIS sever and to STRATEGY's project testbed. Finally, in Figure 3, an example of the printed output of the incident report based on the recommendations of the CWA 18024:2023 [4] is presented as being presented in the FSX. These recommendations, provided in CWA 18024:2023 [4] have taken into account various options in order to suggest a template that will provide to the reader the most important information, such as the severity of the incident and its impacts with a catch of the naked eye without devoting significant time for reading it.

Figure 2. Integration schema used both in the TTX and FSX.

Source: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

Figure 3. Indicative example of a recommended printed format (CWA 18024:2023, [4]) from an incident as presented in the FSX.

INCIDENT REPORT (CWA – Emergency Management – Incident situational Reporting) FSX - 30 March 2023					
User and Incident Identifier					
Incident Report type	Incident ID		Linked incident	Linked incident ID	CI Business name
Report	201		0	0	Vallabrice Dam
Incident Creation Date/Time (Local)	Report recipients	CI Sector	Person or group reporting		Person authorized
3/29/2023 13:10	Fire_Service,Medical_emergency_services,Civil_protection,Police_authorities,other	Water - reservoir	Dam security team		Dam security officer
Contact email	Contact tel		+00	Country (code)	IT
valdam@vallabrice-dam.it					
Incident basic information description					
Incident type			Incident certainty		
True incident			HighlyConfident		
Incident Occurrence Date/Time (Local)	Area	Latitude (WGS84)	Longitude (WGS84)	Elevation (m)	Radius
3/30/23 7:05 AM	Vallabrice area				
Incident description	Due to the earthquake a leak from the dam was observed which led to a dam partial collapse. The integrity of the dam has been seriously affected. Areas to the downstream of the dam are expected to be flooded.				
Accessibility status	Not yet known. Main roads may be flooded. Suggestion to use alternative access of higher altitudes.				
Incident hazard and impacts					
Hazard type		Incident severity a)	Incident urgency a)	Incident priority a)	
Da collapse due to earthquake		Extreme	Immediate	Extremely critical priority / 4	
Impact description			Scale of impacts		
The dam has collapsed partially and its stability has been affected. Collapse may be expanded. Waters run already downstream with the risk to flood the areas below the dam (Vallabrice, stadium and houses).			Unknown / 0		
CI Service affected	Human losses	Expected external impacts (to other CIs)	Other CI sector affected		Restoration time

INCIDENT REPORT (CWA – Emergency Management – Incident situational Reporting) FSX - 30 March 2023					
Water supply stopped.	Unknown	Unknown. Maybe the road has been flooded.	Water supply stopped.	Unknown.	
Actions					
Actions in place					
Alternative infrastructure for service provision			Not applicable		
Description of the actions	0				
Resources					
Resources used by the CI					
0					

Source: Ruiz and Sakkas [21].

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Critical entities, their protection and resilience are crucial in modern societies. Any incident, man-made or natural, that may affect a specific critical infrastructure can have significant impact to the society and may trigger cascading effects to other critical infrastructures or entities. The stability and well-being of the society rely on uninterrupted essential services. The European Commission with the publishing of the two new Directives [1] and [2] clearly aims to a more holistic approach that will support the enhancement of the resilience of the critical entities towards a safer European Union for its citizens.

The findings from the STRATEGY project in the CIP domain point out a clear need for improved collaboration among involved stakeholders. Faster diffusion of standardised exchange of data and information, a common operational picture and situation awareness, standardised risk assessment and processes, as well as dynamic riskevolution are crucial. Use of modern technological systems such as command and control centres, UAVs, and DSS are vital with a focus on standardisation and interoperability between the systems being a key factor.

The recent findings of FIRELOGUE project also support the work of STRATEGY project in the CIP domain, focusing on wildfire risk management. Current needs in wildfire risk management relevant to infrastructures point out the lack of collaboration among stakeholders in wildfire management, global support for decision-makers, and enforcement of legal frameworks at Member State level, contribution to insufficient data sharing and cooperation. Advanced monitoring technologies are limited, and training programs are inadequate. Real-time risk assessment capabilities are lacking, and continuous training for first responders is also insufficient. There is also a lack of standardized data-sharing protocols and little knowledge available about fire prevention technologies, socio-economic impacts, and further operational elaboration on the findings of integrated fire risk modeling. The importance of understanding exposure analysis, building resilience in structures, addressing gaps in current codes, implementing strategies to mitigate risks, leveraging agroforestry systems, using standardized data schemas, accurately defining exposure, and focusing on hazard identification and mitigation. Overall, enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures is essential in mitigating societal impacts. Collaborative efforts and technological advancements are key in building a safer environment for all citizens.

The main scope of this document is aimed at improving the resilience of critical infrastructures and mitigating risks following a holistic approach, considering the interconnectivity of various critical infrastructures. Enhanced resilience requires standardized procedures, widely accepted by all the types of stakeholders. Codes, norms and legislation are an important guide for this path. Technology offers innovative tools to make things simpler, faster and interoperable. Modern technological tools offer significant advantages in continuous monitoring, early warning and detection. Technological advancements also offer important tools that can support the response phase of an incident, especially providing real-time situation awareness and common operational picture to all involved stakeholders. Last but not least, technology can support the use of standards as well as can promote new materials and services compatible with standardized procedures.

The combination of a standard with a technological tool in a simulation environment (table-top) and field exercise in the STRATEGY project clearly showcased a positive outcome of using technology in the daily work of emergency response services and infrastructures, and it was positively accepted by end-users. However, successful implementation requires system readiness and political will to embrace these changes. The participatory process in the STRATEGY project and FIRELOGUE project clearly highlights that responders and infrastructures are ready and available to use new technologies following standardized protocols in order to facilitate their work and guarantee a safer society. This proactive approach reflects an understanding of the need for innovation in response to evolving challenges.

A recent, good example of modern technology to combat wildfires in action is observed in Greece, particularly following the devastating wildfires of 2023. The current deployment of permanent patrolling UAVs has revolutionized early detection and warning systems, enabling rapid response to wildfires. While these technologies do not guarantee complete success in fire suppression, they represent a crucial step toward addressing incidents in their early stages. The political will to integrate such technological tools signifies an acknowledgment of current professional needs and priorities. The use of various sensors and new technological tools (UAVs, satellites, local sensors, weather sensors) is starting to become a prerequisite in order to gather data and acquire more information on the incident [22, 23], potentially affecting a critical infrastructure. Nevertheless, this does not mean that one size fits all solutions, but it is certainly a step towards improved resilience.

Another good example of the use of technology in the critical infrastructure domain is the study of [24] who conducted a computer assisted exercise (CAX) in Greece, which aimed to bring together operators of critical infrastructures and emergency responders. This exercise successfully identified possible civil protection system inconsistencies and provided practical recommendations for strengthening information exchange and cooperation among infrastructure operators, eventually enhancing infrastructure and societal resilience. Player evaluated positively the technological tools used during the drill, emphasizing the benefits of direct information exchange and standardized reporting, both during training and real-life operations.

Another example of political will to incorporate new technologies in disaster risk management and specifically on wildfires is the recent peer review assessment of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism on wildfires [25]. This evaluation emphasizes the importance of utilizing state-of-the-art technologies to safeguard lives,

environment, and properties. It also promotes environmentally friendly, sustainable civil protection activities as part of a comprehensive resilience approach. Italy, for example, stands out as a model, having implemented technological enhancements following the 2021 wildfires, focusing on prevention, prediction, and swift action.

The combination of research and innovation, along with standardization, regulations, and political determination, establishes a strong foundation for developing resilient critical entities and infrastructure. By prioritizing these factors, societies can create secure pathways toward improved preparedness and response capabilities in the face of evolving threats.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

CAX	Computer Assisted Exercise
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
DSS	Decision Support System
FR(s)	First responder(s)
FSX	Full Scale Exercise
TGM	Trial Guidance Methodology
TTX	Table-top Exercise
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
WFRM	Wildfire Risk Management
WUI	Wildland Urban Interface
XGM	eXercise Guidance Method

Lessons Learned from Coherent Resilience Tabletop Exercises in the Baltic Region

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Extended abstract

Current geopolitical environment in the Baltic Sea region requires continuous actions to build and enhance resilience of energy infrastructure. Tabletop Exercise proved to be an important tool that can bring together all the stakeholders and foster resilience through cooperation, sharing and networking of neighbouring states or regions. A Tabletop Exercise is a facilitated discussion-based exercise conducted in a stress free environment. The NATO Energy Security Centre of Excellence (NATO ENSEC COE) and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) have jointly organised three tabletop exercises in the Baltic region addressing resilience and energy security. The exercises were conducted every two years in 2019, 2021 and 2023. All three exercises were evaluated by a team from Naval Postgraduate School (NPS). This paper presents three tabletop exercises and their major outcomes.

A tabletop exercise (TTX) is an informal, discussion-based exercise in which a team discusses their roles and responses during an emergency or crisis, considering several examples of potentially risky situations. The atmosphere is collegial and exploratory, and is not meant to put participants in the mindset they'd have during a real crisis event. Tabletop exercises are used to prepare for crises, with primary aim to identify gaps in legislation and share best practices among the participants [1].

A TTX is in particular useful tool to discuss and prepare for crisis events that might affect several countries having different legal, governance and emergency response systems that need to interact and work together in case of real event. TTX not only serves as a perfect networking event, it could also serve to spark and set up intergovernmental agreements for common crisis response.

Coherent Resilience (CORE) is a series of national and regional level tabletop exercises (TTXs) aimed at enhancing resilience of energy systems in an era of hybrid threats. CORE TTXs have been conducted in Ukraine as well as national and regional programs in the Baltic States and other countries.

The main objective of this study is to provide an overview of the three exercises completed in the Baltic Sea region in the period of 2019-2023 and evaluate their importance and effect in increasing resilience and energy security in the region. As the main focus of the exercises is to improve resilience of energy systems, resilience is understood as system's ability to withstand external shocks and continue to provide services as long as possible, see more details in [2].

Coherent Resilience 2019 (CORE 19) was a Tabletop Exercise on the Baltic States and hybrid threats related to regional natural gas supplies and critical energy infrastructure protection. The TTX took place 14-16 May 2019 in Vilnius, Lithuania. The goal of the exercise was to support the national authorities and natural gas transmission system operators (TSO) of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of gas to consumers and mitigating the disruption over the Baltic region. This three-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event was divided into three phases including an academic seminar, a two-day TTX, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. The event brought together 108 participants from 14 NATO and European Union countries, who came from 35 different organisations representing gas supply and energy security stakeholders.

The goal of the exercise was to support national authorities and gas transmission system operators of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of gas to consumers and mitigating the disruption over the Baltic region through the execution of a tabletop exercise, where national emergency response plans and regional cooperation were exercised. Particular attention was given to the topic solidarity agreements that are required by the EU Regulation 2017/1938.

The following are examples of key conclusions that were identified by the participants:

Tabletop Exercise as a Tool. Participants noted the value of the tabletop exercise as a forum to share best practices, discuss challenges, and review national and regional plans. Having a community of interest to focus on energy security challenges can lead to improvements in resilience of supply and systems through cooperation and communications. CORE 19 participants could see a continuous cycle of annual exercises, where this event is followed organisation, interagency, national, and again a regional-level exercise.

Future Infrastructure as a Positive Change. Planned future additions to regional energy infrastructure - as identified in the scenario 2020+ – was identified as having a significant positive effect on regional and state energy security. It was very clear to the participants that additional infrastructure would significantly lower chances for solidarity request situations. Such solidarity needs are rather low even with today's infrastructure as it became evident during the exercise. Nonetheless, it was also clear that additional work is required in all areas as it is imperative to further improve resilience.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [3].

Coherent Resilience 2021 – Baltic (CORE 21-B) was a Tabletop Exercise on the Baltic States and hybrid threats to the regional electric grid with a focus on critical energy infrastructure protection. The TTX took place 20-24 September 2021 in Vilnius, Lithuania. The aim of the exercise was to support the national authorities and electricity system operators of the Baltic States in ensuring supply of electricity to civilian and military consumers and mitigating the possible disruption in the light of hybrid threats over the Baltic region due to vulnerabilities caused by close proximity of unsafe Belarusian Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) and the process of synchronization of the Baltic States power grid with the Continental Europe grid. CORE 21-B was a five-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event that was executed with an academic seminar, a three-day TTX, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. The event brought together over 100 participants from 12 NATO and European Union countries or partner nations, who came from 35 different organizations representing electricity supply and energy security stakeholders.

A few example key takeaways and recommendations are those identified by the broader syndicate teams that consisted of facilitators, participants, and evaluators:

There is a need for increased baseload reserve generation. There is a need in the Baltic States to increase baseload generation capacity and not to rely on interconnections only. This need is particularly evident when the Baltic States operate in isolation mode creating situations with load shedding as the only available option. **Recommendation:** Analyze the feasibility of building new baseload generation capacity in the region. Feasibility is dependent on need, cost of power, and public opinion. The type of fuel can be as diverse as practically reasonable, be it nuclear, gas, hydrogen or others. Due to ongoing climate protection regulations, low or zero green house gas (GHG) emission technologies should be analyzed for feasibility.

Early Multinational Cooperation during Hybrid Scenarios would improve resilience. During crisis events, the national emergency response centers combine various stakeholders from the TSO(s), cyber agencies, intelligence agencies, and others to facilitate a coordinated national and/or multinational response. But regulations have not been updated regarding the notification and declaration of incidents for all hybrid attacks. And when events and indicators did not clearly trigger declaration of a crisis event, the lines of communication to share information across states and agencies were inconsistent and would likely lead to information gaps at decision-making levels. When thresholds were not clearly exceeded, most reporting continued via internal channels, further preventing effective national and multinational response. **Recommendations:** To improve pre-crisis resiliency, establish reporting channels and procedures for TSOs to collaborate amongst themselves regarding events which do not rise to national emergency or crisis levels. Low-level, cross-agency and cross-nation information sharing will permit the Baltic states and their allies to identify potential attacks more rapidly and respond more precisely, neutralizing single aspects in isolation (where possible). The channels should be exercised during multinational exercises at ministry and TSO levels. Pre-crisis resiliency also depends on the level of uncertainty regarding the functioning of the Belarusian NPP that was built in close proximity to the Baltic States in violation of the international nuclear and environmental safety requirements. The high level of uncertainty stemming from low safety standards and secrecy around the Belarusian NPP could motivate adversary to include a nuclear energy aspect in the hybrid attacks expecting that it will act as a strong force multiplier. In order to diminish the hybrid threat potential, the Baltic States and their allies should continue their

multilateral and bilateral efforts with the aim to ensure that Belarus implements the highest international nuclear safety standards and strictly follows the principles of openness and transparency. In order to improve preparedness and response, it is important to increase awareness on how to deal with the situations when a nuclear element is used as a part of a hybrid activity toolbox.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [4].

Coherent Resilience 2023 – Baltic (CORE 23-B) was a Tabletop Exercise on the energy system of the Baltic States with a focus on maritime critical energy infrastructure protection against hybrid threats. The Tabletop Exercise took place on 13-17 November 2023 in Riga, Latvia. The aim of the exercise was to support national authorities and key energy system stakeholders of the Baltic States and partnering nations with increasing the resiliency of their maritime energy installations and associated distribution networks in the Baltic Sea against hybrid threats. A spectrum of threats was introduced in the exercise scenario ranging from hybrid attacks and terrorism activities to conventional maritime operations. This exercise served as a collaborative venue to improve national contingency plans and procedures and develop NATO and the European Union capacity to support national authorities. CORE 23-B was a five-day regional, multilateral, interagency, and public-private sector event that was executed with an academic seminar, a three-day exercise, and a distinguished visitors' day that included after-action briefings. This report focuses largely on syndicate responses to the exercise scenario vignettes and injects to include capturing key takeaways and recommendations. The event brought together over 120 participants from 12 NATO and European Union countries or partner nations, who came from 45 different organizations representing maritime, energy supply and security stakeholders.

In the face of evolving hybrid threats to critical energy infrastructure, mechanisms for coordination, cooperation, and response between government/military/industry should also evolve across the EU. There are ambiguities and limitations in international law when it comes to classifying and responding to hybrid threats to energy systems. These ambiguities need to be addressed in part through exercises which examine specific likely threats. The broader syndicate team beyond their specific syndicates identifies the following key takeaway and recommendation of the exercise:

There is a need for increased awareness and understanding of critical energy infrastructure. There is currently no common understanding of what, exactly, constitutes critical energy infrastructure (CEI). The EU Directive defines CEI in generic way and attempts to standardize methods to identify and protect CEI are hindered by varying definitions of CEI and by individual approaches that may not be effective in a larger, collective context. While trends towards cross border energy distribution and interconnectedness are positive and do increase the resilience and redundancy of our collective energy posture, they also bring risks if countries have varying definition of what energy infrastructure is. Furthermore, there is no common practice for instituting measures to protect CEI. This most certainly leads to weak points in the collective systems, which can be exploited by an adversary to achieve exponential effects across the whole system. **Recommendation:** Formal guidelines to learn how to determine which aspects of a country or region's energy infrastructure is critical is needed, probably followed by training and modelling. In addition to assessing the infrastructure and thinking about risks, the guidelines would also instruct participants regarding what steps are needed to protect CI, with the objective of increasing security, resilience, and redundancy.

A number of key takeaways was identified by each of 4 syndicates and these are provided in the corresponding sections of the final exercise report [5].

Concluding remarks

Looking backwards, we can clearly conclude that CORE19 TTX has stimulated and actually paved the way to signatures of inter-governmental agreements on natural gas solidarity among the Baltic States. While we could not identify such an obvious outcome from other two exercises, they clearly improved trans-national exchange on best practices, helped to identify gaps and missing procedures and proposed regional measures for further actions.

It is important to note that exercise reports – ideally – do not end exercises, for the region, nations, agencies and organizations that participated in those TTXs. They should each develop an Improvement Plan based on the

relevant key takeaways identified. Each institution is to further analyse the key takeaways pertinent to them in order to identify the best means to facilitate improvements and develop the corresponding plan of action.

The participant's surveys conducted by NPS at the end of each exercise indicate the need and importance of such exercises. This need is in particular evident in this time of threats and attacks becoming more and more realistic.

We do believe that three exercises, all taking more than 6 months effort to organise and arrange, will contribute to the energy security and resilience improvements of the Baltic Sea region.

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Interactive Session Posters and Outcomes

FEMA funding for critical infrastructure upgrades

MDT MARYLAND DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION Department of Transportation Port Administration

Baltimore Harbor Safety and Coordination Committee

AASHTO American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials protection requirements for newly-built bridges, guidance for retrofitting old structures

U.S. DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION publishes technical advisories on pier protection

Federal Highway Administration

THE GRENFELL 'WEB OF BLAME'

Deepwater Horizon: 17 "parties in interest" in trial

Requirements for responsible decision-making concerning safety

- Acceptance of a duty
- Accountability for the duty
- Capability to fulfil the duty
 - authority & resources to implement changes
 - data concerning risks
 - institutional memory
 - competency

(Inter-)organizational complexity and diffusion of responsibility make accidents inevitable in the long term

Interorganizational complexity

- Work processes often require collaboration & coordination across organizational boundaries
 - outsourcing, network orgs
- Leads to
 - different sets of rules for same activity
 - obstacles to flow of information
 - unclear accountability structures

Diffusion of responsibility

People feel less responsibility for taking action in a given situation, because there are other people who could also be responsible for taking action.

→ **accountability mismatches**

"It's obvious that the lines of authority are not clear, or not well understood... It looks like everybody's passing the buck."

Your views?

Corporate blindness to unmanaged risk: when ignorance isn't bliss

Wilful blindness stops needed upgrades

What makes wilful blindness more likely?

1. Downplay negative information
2. Suppress dissent or criticism
3. Emphasise loyalty and conformity
4. Avoid transparency
5. Avoid conflict
6. Punish or ignore whistleblowers
7. Succeed at any cost
8. Create ambiguity (plausible deniability)
9. Reward silence, support the status quo
10. Normalise ethical lapses and small acts of misconduct
11. Prioritise short-term gains over long-term risks
12. Leaders visibly ignore problems
13. Groupthink and herd mentality
14. Fear of repercussions
15. Weak accountability for safety issues
16. Poor awareness of risk

Your views?

How can you detect blindness and find EWS?

Examples of poor link between knowledge and decision making

Example 1: Blind spot on the bridge side

EWS:

- Several ship collisions
- Expansion of Panama Canal

Issues:

- Failure to update infrastructure due to increased risk (larger ships)
- Grandfathering (systemic dysfunction)

Example 2 Blind spot on the ship side

EWS:

- Two power outages while docked in Baltimore

Issues:

- Failure to carry out a deeper investigation on outages
- Sailing out without solving the problem - (information asymmetry)

Did you use any of these tools ? ? Why did you choose them?

What were the result(s) ?

Do you see other possible effective tools ?

How to make more efficient the link between knowledge and decision making?

Your views?

- Knowledge is domain dependent
- Decision-maker's expertise is within another discipline
- Perception of hazards differ from person to person but especially when raised in another discipline
- To drive change, safety professionals should communicate differently: Tailor the message
- Talk finance to accountants, governance to admins, technology to engineering

To shift a belief is hard labour for both parties
To drive an organizational change, a multitude of effort will be needed

ipcc approach of communicating

- Build confidence by substantiation of your reports
- Periodic reports show trends in time
- A true story: assumptions, uncertainties, knowledge gaps
- Discuss tradeoffs and alternative measures

Your views?

Missing links: Understanding blindness to safety risks

**John Kingston, Peter Kouwenhoven, Eric Marsden, Sever Paul, Tuuli Tulonen,
Frank Verschueren, Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano, Maria Luisa Villani**

Outcomes from the interactive session of the ESReDA Athens seminar

This executive summary is an output from the interactive session organised by the ESReDA project group on Risk, Knowledge and Management at the ESReDA seminar held in Athens in November 2024. The seminar included a poster session with four posters, each with a claim concerning organisational blindness to safety risks. As part of the seminar, the audience was divided into four groups, and each group was asked to spend 20 minutes with a poster, then move on to the next one. At the poster, the audience was given a short presentation of the claim on the poster, and the background to it, and asked about their thoughts concerning the claim.

The objective of this summary is to thank the audience for their participation, and to give all participants a reminder of what the posters claimed, feedback on what was discussed in the interactive sessions, and information on what conclusions were then made. This executive summary does not claim to be the truth, but instead we hope it rouses thoughts and ideas on potential ways to reduce organisational blindness, better identify safety problems and ensure that the decisions required to reduce risks are not buried by the myriad of other pressures that affect every organisation.

The posters addressed different facets of organisational (and organised) blindness: (1) how complexity contributes to the blindness of organisations, (2) how you can be wilfully blind, (3) how to detect that you may be blind to issues, and (4) how you can tackle blindness with smarter communication. The discussions helped identify concepts and practices that can help reinforce the link that should exist between knowledge of threats to safety and the allocation of organisational resources to prevent accidents.

The first poster was about the dissemination of responsibility in complex systems in which people belonging to multiple organisations have to collaborate and coordinate to make decisions about safety management. In such systems, awareness concerning risks tends to be distributed, and accountability for safety is spread across several people and therefore weakened. We see this across multiple accidents including the Key Bridge accident (Baltimore, 2024), the Deepwater Horizon catastrophe, and the Grenfell Tower fire. These complex organisational structures are becoming increasingly common for multi-stakeholder systems and infrastructures, so we need to be aware of the associated challenges.

Several points were raised by the audience of the Athens seminar: First of all, this may often be seen in particular in systems which involve public and private partnership, and in which multiple stakeholders need to participate in the system governance. A “pass-the-buck” phenomenon is often seen when investigating accidents in such systems. Second, a strong regulatory framework can help avoid certain problems which appear with these complex organisational structures, but the strength of the regulatory system is very variable depending on the industry sector concerned. It is necessary to find effective collaboration and decision-making mechanisms despite the presence of silos, and

despite diverging interests from stakeholders. Finally, the participants pointed out that monolithic systems are not immune to these challenges because obstacles to information sharing and to clear accountability are also present inside systems run by a single organisation.

The second poster claimed that needed upgrades to engineering are sometimes stopped by wilful blindness. The participants agreed on that, noting a lack of strategies to deal with it. Wilful blindness was, however, expected to be more likely in some settings than others. The optimism of small business owners can be seen as an exercise in wilful blindness. Several participants pointed out that, beyond the usual adage *'if it ain't broke, don't fix it'*, the IT sector tightly embraces a culture of *'if it works, don't touch it'* and *'it's good enough'*. Hence, even if the client is mindful of risks, an overly pragmatic software development team might not be.

Our participants also noted that wilful blindness seems to be at work in discussions of reasonable practicability. These included: how experts are selected, how good practice is determined, how standard-setting bodies are governed, and how risks themselves are (subsequently) framed.

Foresight, one participant noted, gets worse gradually and is not easily restored. The concept of ethical fading implies a similar incrementalism. A participant noted that this dynamic has a social inertia. In practice, a group that migrates in increments to a new deviant norm is very reluctant to reverse its steps. A *'don't ask, don't tell'* culture is hard to undo once embedded. Stakeholder engagement, we would expect, should help to reduce wilful blindness, making it less likely or more easily countered. Likewise, if the relationships between the employer and the workforce are poor, as one of our participants noted, it can be hard for a manager to distinguish between valid concerns and the flexing of an agenda.

One of the participants spoke of his disappointment to find, on returning to his country after twenty years away, that some problems were unchanged. It was noted that, when one level of government is challenged, they are adept at blaming the level above. Wilful blindness can create its own *metarisk* of fueling mistrust in institutions and wider political processes.

The third poster was about early warning signs. We propose that detecting and acting on EWS are very important to get both knowledge management and risk management to a higher level of efficiency and effectiveness. Starting from the notion that an EWS is early, and warns of escalation, we build on past experience that if the EWS is not acted on, the disturbance-scenario will escalate and have a bigger impact leading up to a major accident. Therefore, the solution is to stop this escalation as soon as possible by detecting EWS and acting upon them with knowledge-based and evidence-based risk management. The main approach is to identify the components of the normal/abnormal flow which starts with an observation of reality and which - after e.g. data analysis, interpretation, information, knowledge, and decision making - should end with an action on that reality.

To progress to a solution it is very important to learn the boundaries of the safe region of operation, and that transgressing the boundaries is in fact an early warning sign that should prompt action. For example, the Key Bridge accident included several early warning signs - elements that were known concerning both the status of the bridge and the situation on the vessel - examples which were used to kick off discussion with the interactive session participants.

The insights gained in from this interaction included that promoting diversity in teams (including shop-floor workers) is essential to support the interpretation of signals; that information overload can hide the critical information; that fostering a culture of feedback and learning is critical; that if the data is partial, incomplete, or influenced by biases, the conclusions drawn from it may be misleading, hindering the ability to detect warning signs.

The fourth poster was about communication: are accidents due to bad communication of the risk that is understood by the safety professional but not by the decision-maker who remains blind to it? How should the available knowledge be communicated so that it leads to the decision-maker both understanding the issues and acting upon them? Complex matters may lead to decision-makers focusing on only their own field of expertise and omitting the rest, or the decision-maker may already have decided and is not motivated to change.

According to the seminar discussions with the audience, smart communication is about defining what is the content, objective, and best method and timing of the communication, what evidence should be used, and identifying who should communicate to whom: to drive change, safety professionals should tailor the message to match the perception and judgement capabilities of the audience. At the same time, both the person sharing the information and the person receiving it need to understand that it takes effort to shift beliefs and gain understanding.

In conclusion, as key takeaways from the interactive session of the seminar, we now understand that we can treat corporations as entities, and individuals as entities, but we cannot treat a team or the system as an entity. When discussing blindness, we pick on individuals even though it is a team function, and could even be a corporate function. When everyone is responsible, no one is responsible. How organisations are organised internally for accountability, is important. Here, the framework to regulate how stakeholders engage and collaborate is of importance to help organisations 'do governance' and gain foresight.

Blindness can involve bad behaviour but usually the behaviour is within the normal range, but with a bad consequence. Perhaps this is a subject which like others is a matter of fitting the task to the person. Do we need to design our processes to more closely fit how people are, how they work together? Still, people are really reluctant to talk about blindness. Why: fear; denial? This has made the problem more or less undiscussable. We need to recognise that there are some rule sets that are lacking in the workplace. And sometimes a decision has to be made to slow down, think, and make more deliberate choices.

In the scope of blindness, early warning signs are an important element. Signals need to be identified and managed, not suppressed. Here, early warning signs are identifiable only if networks function: for example, by trouble-free collaboration between stakeholders, which would avoid signals being lost. We need something where early warning signs are talked about and acted upon. This does not happen sometimes, maybe because the decision-making process is unwieldy. Here, a more agile process might be the answer, to avoid shortcuts and the blindness that comes with it.

There are ways to communicate that actually create blindness. Your message is also competing with other messages, and we probably do not think about communication as much as we should. You can always blame 'poor' communication after the fact, and you would be right, but that is not helpful. You

need to think more concretely about the way you are communicating: you need to think strategically to get the best possible chance to gain results that make the difference in safety.

The poster sessions, and reflections since, make it clear that blindness is an issue to which we lack answers. However, blindness is usually discussed only in hindsight, and surrounded by negative emotions and recrimination. In the workplace, blindness is feared for its punishing consequences. To make progress, the subject first needs to be brought to light and made discussable.

A full paper with more detailed results and conclusions is planned to be released during 2025.

Conclusions

The 65th ESReDA Seminar aimed to address the intricate relationships between risk, knowledge and management, in order to find new ideas for preventing accidents and improving safety management with better utilisation of knowledge. Although we are told that we live and work in ‘information and knowledge’ society, preventing accidents and enhancing resilience, by using the relevant safety knowledge and expertise, is not granted and requires continuous efforts to overcome the hurdles in an ‘age of uncertainty’.

The seminar followed the successful 58th ESReDA Seminar on ‘Using Knowledge to Manage Risks and Threats: Practices and Challenges’ organised by JRC Institute of Energy (Petten, the Netherlands, held virtually in June 2021), and fulfilled its objective to furnish pertinent information, from both theoretical and practical perspectives, about the convergence of risk management, knowledge management, and decision-making related to safety concerns, based on contemporary practices and the prevailing level of scientific knowledge.

Given the well balanced scientific and professional audience which shared views from both the academic and the industrial field, we believe that the 65th ESReDA Seminar provided different answers to the question posed at its beginning: “What does a management team, a regulator or a front-line operator need to know and can use to manage risks effectively?” and based on them to contribute to further research works, also within ESReDA activities.

Appendix: Seminar Programme

NATIONAL CENTRE FOR
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH "DEMOKRITOS"

ESReDA | European Safety, Reliability &
Data Association

65th ESReDA Seminar

on

From risk imagination to safety intervention - Managing risks with knowledge

Programme

November 14th - 15th, 2024

NCSR Demokritos, Athens, Greece

With the kind support of: **ESRA** European Safety and Reliability Association and

AGENDA

Day 1 – Thursday, 14 November 2024

Start	End	Agenda item
8:30	9:00	Registration
9:00	9:30	<p>Welcome words from:</p> <p>Mohamed Eid, ESReDA president</p> <p>Konstantinos Eleftheriadis, NCSR Demokritos, INRASTES Director</p> <p>Myrto Konstantinidou, PG Leader- Seminar Chair</p>
9:30	10:15	<p>KEYNOTE 1. It is the assumption that kills you</p> <p><i>Prof. John Stoop</i></p> <p>Chairs: Mohamed Eid and Myrto Konstantinidou</p>
10:15	11:00	<p>SESSION 1. Knowledge and Management</p> <p>Chairs: Eric Marsden and Sever Paul</p>
10:15	10:30	<p>1. Management system for regulatory requirements applicable to environmentally classified industrial facilities</p> <p><i>Emmanuel Plot, Vassishtasai Ramany, Christophe Coll, Frederic Baudequin</i></p>
10:30	10:45	<p>2. Risk management in a complex multirisk unregulated environment</p> <p><i>Dan Serbanescu</i></p>
10:45	11:00	<p>3. Knowledge creation for resilient cyber-socio-technical systems: framing recent research</p> <p><i>Maria Luisa Villani and Antonio De Nicola</i></p>
11:00	11:30	Coffee break
11:30	12:15	<p>KEYNOTE 2 (online). Technical Language Processing – unlocking information in safety data</p> <p><i>Prof. Melinda Hodkiewicz</i></p> <p>Chairs: Maria Luisa Villani and Antonio Guillen</p>
12:15	13:00	<p>SESSION 2. BAG-INTEL project</p> <p>Chairs: John Stoop and Panayiotis Michael</p>
12:15	12:30	<p>4. Risk-based Customs' Intrusive Inspection Decision Making: Algorithm & Preliminary Case study</p> <p><i>Lamia Hammadi, Eduardo Souza de Cursi, Mohamed Eid, and Henrik Larsen</i></p>

12:30	12:45	<p>5. Processing heterogeneous data sources for risk management by knowledge graph databases: the case of BAG-INTEL research project</p> <p><i>Bartolome Ortiz-Viso, Karel Gutierrez-Batista, M. Dolores Ruiz and Maria J. Martin-Bautista</i></p>
12:45	13:00	<p>6. BAG-INTEL: A Hierarchical Multi-Cloud IoT-Edge-Cloud Architecture for Enhanced Airport Security and Operation</p> <p><i>George Bardas, Panayiotis Michael, Panayiotis Tsanakas, George Lalas and Henrik Larsen</i></p>
13:00	14:00	Lunch Break
14:00	15:30	<p>Interactive Session</p> <p>What does a management team, a regulator or a front-line operator need to know and can use in order to manage risks effectively?</p>
15:30	16:00	Coffee break
16:00	17:00	ESReDA Board Meeting (different room)
16:00	17:00	<p>SESSION 3. Risk Assessment</p> <p>Chairs: Effie Marcoulaki and Frank Verschueren</p>
16:00	16:15	<p>7. Quantitative Assessment of Landslide Risk to Residents on the Slope of a Hazardous Area in Malaysia.</p> <p><i>Kwan Ben Sim, Min Lee Lee, Rasa Remenyte-Prescott, Soon Yee Wong</i></p>
16:15	16:30	<p>8. Risk Assessment of Liquid Hydrogen in Transfer Operations</p> <p><i>Olga Aneziris</i></p>
16:30	16:45	<p>9. Road Tunnel Fire Safety: Introducing a new risk assessment framework as a response to the existing challenges</p> <p><i>Panagiotis Ntzeremes and Konstantinos Kirytopoulos</i></p>
16:45	17:00	<p>10. What roles for risk imagination in risk assessment?</p> <p><i>Sever Paul</i></p>
17:00	18:00	Meeting of Project Group
		End of Day 1

Day 2 – Friday, 15 November 2024

<i>Start</i>	<i>End</i>	<i>Agenda item</i>
9:15	9:30	Logistics from Seminar chair
9:30	10:15	<p>KEYNOTE 3. Industry talk <i>Asterios Lialios, Elefsis Refinery HSE Director, Safety Manager of the year 2024, Helleniq Energy S.A.</i></p> <p>Chairs: Myrto Konstantinidou and Vytis Kopustinskas</p>
10:15	10:45	<p>SESSION 4. Materials Chairs: Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano and Tuuli Tulonen</p>
10:15	10:30	<p>11. Vulnerabilities and disruption risks for the supply chains of the Critical Materials necessary for the clean energy transition <i>Michalis Christou, Samuel Carrara, Patricia Alves Dias, Angel Prior Arce, Theodor Kuzov, Nicola Magnani</i></p>
10:30	10:45	<p>12. Safe and sustainable-by-design: The case of nanomaterials <i>Effie Marcoulaki</i></p>
10:45	11:15	Coffee break
11:15	12:00	<p>KEYNOTE 4. A science of professional engineering practice: our next step towards a safer engineering industry. <i>Bill Hewlett, MA CEng FICE FIET</i></p> <p>Chairs: John Kingston and Peter Kouwenhoven</p>
12:00	13:00	<p>SESSION 5. Critical infrastructures Chairs: Olga Aneziris and Michalis Christou</p>
12:00	12:15	<p>13. Enhancing Cross-Border Risk Assessment for Critical Infrastructure: Challenges, Tools and Recommendations <i>Monica Cardarilli, Frédéric Petit, Georgios Valsamos, Ana Lisa Vetere Arellano</i></p>
12:15	12:30	<p>14. Critical Gas-Fired Power Plants in Integrated Natural Gas and Electricity Systems <i>Ricardo Fernández-Blanco, David Pozo, and Ricardo Bolado-Lavín</i></p>
12:30	12:45	<p>15. Enhancing resilience in critical infrastructures through innovative pathways – The FIRELOGUE and STRATEGY projects approaches in emergency management <i>Georgios Sakkas, Nikolaos Kalapodis, Danai Kazantzidou-Firtinidou</i></p>

12:45	13:00	16. Lessons Learned from Coherent Resilience Tabletop Exercises in the Baltic Region <i>Vytis Kopustinskas, Evaldas Dirginčius, Charles Lynn, Isabel Asensio Bermejo, Lawrence Walzer, Darius Aukščionis, Hrvoje Foretić</i>
13:00	14:00	Lunch
14:00	14:30	KEYNOTE 5 (online). Collaborative intelligence and human in the loop for the future of safety critical systems. A human-centred perspective. <i>Maria Chiara Leva</i> Chairs: Zoe Nivolianiti an Mohamed Eid
14:30	15:00	Results of the Interactive Session – audience opinions
15:00	15:30	Closing session - "Seminar takeaways" PG and TPC members
15:30	16:00	Coffee and discussions
16:00		End of seminar